

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 4258–4354

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0039

Cover photo

MAHLI view of a target called Erin Lake after being brushed by Curiosity's DRT (dust removal tool), located at McDonald Pass in the Arc Pass channel region, acquired on Sol 4294 in full shadow. This is MAHLI focus merge product 4294MH0001630001503088R00.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 4258th and 4354th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 4258 and 4354.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA’s MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator’s Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook: Sols 4258–4354*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 38 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 29 July 2024 through 04 November 2024.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report’s period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 4258 through 4354 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4258 – 4354						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
At Kings Canyon Drill Site	01 Aug 24	4261	5	7	0	During the day, MAHLI imaged Kings_Canyon after a drill bit preload test. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	03 Aug 24	4263	1	2	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Kings_Canyon sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Kings_Canyon sample discard pile.
	17 Aug 24/ 18 Aug 24	4277	7	19	1	During the day, MAHLI imaged the Kings_Canyon drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were merged as well. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	18 Aug 24	4278	1	2	0	MAHLI imaged the Kings_Canyon drill cuttings.
	21 Aug 24	4280	6	36	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Gabbot_Pass.
	22 Aug 24	4281	1	2	3	MAHLI imaged the Kings_Canyon drill cuttings. Focus stack images from Sol 4280 were merged.
	22 Aug 24	4282	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Marck_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.
Heading back towards Fairview_Dome	30 Aug 24	4289	7	65	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Eichorn_Pinnacle and the target Thousand_Island_Lake. The focus stack images were also merged.
At Fairview_Dome	01 Sep 24	4291	8	64	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed targets Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake and Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake.
Heading towards McDonald_Pass	03 Sep 24	4293	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4291 were merged.
At McDonald_Pass	04 Sep 24	4294	7	62	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Erin_Lake and the target Picture_Puzzle. The focus stack images were also merged.
	05 Sep 24	4295	7	70	7	MAHLI imaged the targets Campfire_Lake and Gemini. The focus stack images were also merged.
Heading towards Tungsten_Hills	07 Sep 24	4297	6	60	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Big_Bird_Lake and Big_Baldy.
	08 Sep 24	4298	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 4297 were merged.
At Tungsten_Hills	10 Sep 24	4300	9	82	0	MAHLI acquired a 3x1 mosaic on Window_Cliffs. MAHLI also imaged the DRT-brushed target Pond_Lily_Lake and the target Boneyard_Meadow.
Heading towards Corral_Meadow	11 Sep 24	4301	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4300 were merged.
	12 Sep 24	4302	5	51	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Lucys_Foot_Pass and Sandy_Meadow. The focus stack images were also merged.
At Corral_Meadow	14 Sep 24	4304	11	86	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Wales_Rock and the target College_Rock.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 4258 – 4354						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Heading towards the West side of Arc Pass channel	16 Sep 24	4306	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4304 were merged.
	17 Sep 24	4307	7	59	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Grasshopper_Flat and Frog_Lake. The focus stack images were merged as well.
	19 Sep 24	4309	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target The_Minster and the focus stack images were merged.
	21 Sep 24	4311	9	77	0	MAHLI imaged the target Aeolian_Buttes, the DRT-brushed target Cherry_Ridge, and the REMS UV Sensor.
	22 Sep 24	4312	20	20	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4311 were merged. MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.
Heading towards Sheep_Creek	24 Sep 24	4314	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Burst_Rock and the focus stack images were merged.
At Sheep_Creek	26 Sep 24	4316	6	60	6	MAHLI imaged the targets Aster_Lake and Beryl_Lake. The focus stack images were also merged.
	28 Sep 24/ 29 Sep 24	4318	15	111	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Angora_Mountain, Moonlight_Lake and Cloud_Canyon. MAHLI also imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets.
	29 Sep 24	4319	0	0	9	Focus stack images from Sol 4318 were merged.
Exiting Arc Pass Channel	01 Oct 24/ 02 Oct 24	4321	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Flat_Note_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.
Traversing Northwest along channel edge	03 Oct 24	4323	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Sub_Dome and the focus stack images were merged.
	06 Oct 24	4325	8	60	0	MAHLI imaged the target Kidney_Lake, the target Pumice_Flat and the DRT-brushed target Ribbon_Fall.
	07 Oct 24	4326	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 4325 were merged.
	08 Oct 24	4327	8	48	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Pincushion_Peak.
	09 Oct 24	4328	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4327 were merged.
	12 Oct 24	4331	8	48	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Midnight_Lake.
	13 Oct 24	4332	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4331 were merged.
	15 Oct 24	4334	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Dollar_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.
	17 Oct 24	4336	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Jumble_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.
	19 Oct 24	4338	10	84	0	MAHLI imaged the target Polly_Dome, the target Noble_Canyon, and the DRT-brushed target Chapel_Lake.
	20 Oct 24	4339	0	0	8	Focus stack images from Sol 4338 were merged.
	22 Oct 24	4341	5	42	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Chuck_Pass.
	23 Oct 24	4342	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 4341 were merged.
	26 Oct 24	4345	8	72	0	MAHLI acquired a 3x1 mosaic on Reef_Lake and MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Mount_Brewer.
	27 Oct 24	4346	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 4345 were merged.
29 Oct 24	4348	0	0	3	Focus stack images from Sol 4345 were merged again; this happened because a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the DRT-brushed target Reds_Meadow.	
31 Oct 24	4350	8	64	6	MAHLI imaged the target Ladder_Lake and the DRT-brushed target Reds_Meadow (brushed on Sol 4348). The focus stack images were also merged.	
Traversing Northwest along channel edge	02 Nov 24	4352	10	92	0	MAHLI imaged the target Stag_Dome, the DRT-brushed target Eureka_Valley and the target Black_Bear_Lake.
	03 Nov 24	4353	0	0	9	Focus stack images from Sol 4352 were merged.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 4258–4354 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 4261, 4263, 4277, 4278, 4280, 4281, 4282, 4289, 4291, 4294, 4295, 4297, 4300, 4302, 4304, 4307, 4309, 4311, 4312, 4314, 4316, 4318, 4321, 4323, 4325, 4327, 4331, 4334, 4336, 4338, 4341, 4345, 4350, 4352.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{\text{uncertainty}} = (p_{\text{far}} + p_{\text{near}})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

UPDATED: 01_August_2024

SOL 4261 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended drill target named **Kings_Canyon** – after sols 4257 and 4261 drill bit pre-load tests

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100465	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 35 cm									
	4261MH0004650011502750C00	2750	12893	36.7	34.8	-3.3	4.0	136.1	12.8	1608	1198	21.9	16.3

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT			INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm									
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4261MH0003120001502751C00	2751	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH			INTENDED DISTANCE TO MESH: 12.4 cm									
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4261MH0003120011502752C00	2752	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT			INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm									
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4261MH0003260001502753C00	2753	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl100326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT			INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm									
	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4261MH0003260001502754C00	2754	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet – at night with its cover open – overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl100228	MANUAL FOCUS			INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm									
	4261MH0002280001502755C00	2755	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 05_August_2024

SOL 4263 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

intended sample discard site for planned Kings_Canyon drill sample

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhli00190	CONTEXT VIEW 4263MH0001900011502757C00	2757	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7

SOL 4277 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Kings_Canyon drill hole

mhl00197	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	4277MH0001970011502759C00	2759	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00774	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 10 cm											
	4277MH0007740011502761C00	2761	13518	11.6	9.7	-0.4	0.4	47.7	1.3	1608	1198	7.7	5.7

Kings_Canyon drill hole cuttings

mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm													
	4277MH0002240011502763C00	2763	14182	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4277MH0002580001502772R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4277MH0002580001502773S00	

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO MESH IS 12.4 cm; TO FUNNEL THROAT IS 16.3 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl00312	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 1 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
mhl00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT MESH												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO MESH: 12.4 cm											
mhl00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 2 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											
mhl00326	IMAGE FOCUSED AT FUNNEL THROAT (~4 cm BELOW MESH) – POSITION 3 OF 3 TO INSPECT FUNNEL THROAT												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO FUNNEL THROAT: 16.3 cm											

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet

INTENDED WORKING DISTANCE TO INLET IS ~19 cm – FOR SCALE, NOTE THAT MESH DIAMETER IS 3.5 cm

mhl00228	MANUAL FOCUS												
	INTENDED DISTANCE: ~19 cm												
mhl00228	MANUAL FOCUS												
	4277MH0002280001502778C00	2778	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

UPDATED: 19_August_2024

SOL 4278 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Kings_Canyon drill hole cuttings

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhl00122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4278MH0001220011502780C00	2780	14167	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3

UPDATED: 22_August_2024

SOL 4280 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Gabbot_Pass – before DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE (NEAR/FAR)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm								
	4280MH0001900011502782C00	2782	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8 2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhlI00122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm								
	4280MH0001220011502784C00	2784	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2 0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named Gabbot_Pass – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE (NEAR/FAR)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm								
	4280MH0001900011502786C00	2786	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8 2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm								
	4280MH0003360011502788C00	2788	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2 0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4281MH0001930001502823R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4281MH0001930001502824S00				
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm								
	4280MH0003360011502798C00	2798	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2 0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4281MH0001930001502821R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4281MH0001930001502822S00				
mhlI00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm								
	4280MH0008480011502808C00	2808	15088	2.9	1.0	-0.1 0.1	17.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4281MH0001930001502819R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4281MH0001930001502820S00				

UPDATED: 22_August_2024

SOL 4281 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

Kings_Canyon drill hole cuttings													
mhl00122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
		4281MH0001220011502818C00	2818	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0

UPDATED: 23_August_2024

SOL 4282 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Marck_Lake – after DRT													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm									
	4282MH0001900011502826C00	2826	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4282MH0003360011502828C00	2828	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4282MH0001930001502861R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4282MH0001930001502862S00					
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm									
	4282MH0003360011502838C00	2838	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4282MH0001930001502859R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4282MH0001930001502860S00					
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm									
	4282MH0008480011502848C00	2848	15150	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.5	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:			BEST FOCUS PRODUCT: 4282MH0001930001502857R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4282MH0001930001502858S00					

SOL 4289 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Eichorn_Pinnacle – after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4289MH0001900011502864C00	2864	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4289MH0003360011502866C00	2866	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4289MH0001630001502938R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4289MH0001630001502939S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4289MH0003360011502876C00	2876	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4289MH0001630001502936R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4289MH0001630001502937S00
mhl100873	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	4289MH0008730011502886C00	2886	14738	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4289MH0001630001502934R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4289MH0001630001502935S00

target named **Thousand_Island_Lake**

mhl100862	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4289MH0008620011502896C00	2896	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4289MH0001630001502932R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4289MH0001630001502933S00	
mhl100885	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm													
	4289MH0008850011502907C00	2907	13268	16.5	14.6	-0.7	0.7	64.9	2.6	1608	1198	10.4	7.8		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4289MH0001630001502930R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4289MH0001630001502931S00	
mhl100885	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 cm													
	4289MH0008850011502918C00	2918	13287	16.0	14.1	-0.7	0.7	63.2	2.4	1608	1198	10.2	7.6		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4289MH0001630001502928R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4289MH0001630001502929S00	

SOL 4291 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake – after DRT														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4291MH0001900011502941C00	2941	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4291MH0003360011502943C00	2943	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503014R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4293MH0001630001503015S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4291MH0003360011502953C00	2953	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503012R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4293MH0001630001503013S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													
	4291MH0008640011502963C00	2963	14915	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503010R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4293MH0001630001503011S00

target named Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake – after DRT														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW													
	4291MH0001900011502973C00	2973	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1													
	4291MH0003360011502975C00	2975	13981	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503008R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4293MH0001630001503009S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2													
	4291MH0003360011502985C00	2985	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503006R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4293MH0001630001503007S00
mhl100873	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW													
	4291MH0008730011502995C00	2995	14631	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503004R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4293MH0001630001503005S00

SOL 4294 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Erin_Lake – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4294MH0001900011503017C00	3017	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4294MH0001680011503019C00	3019	14045	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503088R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4294MH0001630001503089S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4294MH0001680011503029C00	3029	14047	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503086R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4294MH0001630001503087S00
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 2 cm												
	4294MH0003020011503039C00	3039	14788	3.5	1.6	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.1	2.3	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503084R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4294MH0001630001503085S00

target named Picture_Puzzle

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4294MH0003590011503049C00	3049	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503082R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4294MH0001630001503083S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4294MH0002240011503059C00	3059	14338	5.1	3.2	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.0	3.0		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503080R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4294MH0001630001503081S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	4294MH0002240011503069C00	3069	14351	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503078R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4294MH0001630001503079S00	

SOL 4295 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Campfire_Lake**

mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4295MH0003590011503091C00	3091	13009	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4295MH0001710001503172R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4295MH0001710001503173S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
4295MH0002240011503101C00	3101	13940	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9			
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4295MH0001710001503170R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4295MH0001710001503171S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
4295MH0002240011503111C00	3111	13921	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9			
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4295MH0001710001503168R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4295MH0001710001503169S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
4295MH0002240011503121C00	3121	13931	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9			
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4295MH0001710001503166R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4295MH0001710001503167S00	

target named **Gemini**

mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4295MH0003590011503131C00	3131	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4295MH0001710001503164R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4295MH0001710001503165S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
4295MH0002240011503141C00	3141	13996	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4295MH0001710001503162R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4295MH0001710001503163S00	
mhl00224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
4295MH0002240011503151C00	3151	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:			4295MH0001710001503160R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:					4295MH0001710001503161S00	

SOL 4297 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Big_Bird_Lake													
mhl100865	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm										
	4297MH0008650011503175C00	3175	13035	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4298MH0001630001503244R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4298MH0001630001503245S00					
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4297MH0003060011503185C00	3185	14234	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4298MH0001630001503242R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4298MH0001630001503243S00					
mhl100306	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4297MH0003060011503195C00	3195	14274	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4298MH0001630001503240R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4298MH0001630001503241S00					

target named Big_Baldy													
mhl100855	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm										
	4297MH0008550011503205C00	3205	13034	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.7	6.1	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4298MH0001630001503238R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4298MH0001630001503239S00					
mhl100383	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4297MH0003830011503215C00	3215	14186	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4298MH0001630001503236R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4298MH0001630001503237S00					
mhl100383	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4297MH0003830011503225C00	3225	14167	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4298MH0001630001503234R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT: 4298MH0001630001503235S00					

SOL 4300 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Window_Cliffs - a 3 x 1 mosaic

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
POSITION 1 OF 3 INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm														
mhli00887	4300MH0008870011503247C00		3247	13257	16.8	14.9	-0.7	0.8	66.0	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503342R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503343S00						
POSITION 2 OF 3 INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm														
mhli00887	4300MH0008870011503257C00		3257	13177	19.2	17.3	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	1608	1198	12.0	8.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503340R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503341S00						
POSITION 3 OF 3 INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 cm														
mhli00887	4300MH0008870011503267C00		3267	13206	18.3	16.4	-0.9	0.9	71.2	3.2	1608	1198	11.5	8.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503338R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503339S00						

target named Pond_Lily_Lake - after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
CONTEXT VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm														
mhli00190	4300MH0001900011503277C00		3277	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503336R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503337S00						
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1 INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm														
mhli00336	4300MH0003360011503279C00		3279	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503334R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503335S00						
MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2 INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm														
mhli00336	4300MH0003360011503289C00		3289	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503334R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503335S00						
HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm														
mhli00848	4300MH0008480011503299C00		3299	15126	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503332R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503333S00						

target named Boneyard_Meadow

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)	IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)				
CONTEXT STEREO-1 INTENDED STANDOFF - 35 cm														
mhli00886	4300MH0008860011503309C00		3309	12894	36.6	34.7	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	1608	1198	21.8	16.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503330R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503331S00						
CONTEXT STEREO-2 INTENDED STANDOFF - 35 cm														
mhli00886	4300MH0008860011503319C00		3319	12892	36.8	34.9	-3.3	4.0	136.5	12.9	1608	1198	21.9	16.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503328R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503329S00						

UPDATED: 12_September_2024

SOL 4302 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Lucys_Foot_Pass

mhl100855	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	4302MH0008550011503345C00	3345	13004	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	1608	1198	16.6	12.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4302MH0008880001503403R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4302MH0008880001503404S00	
mhl100308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4302MH0003080011503355C00	3355	13898	7.6	5.7	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	1608	1198	5.4	4.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4302MH0008880001503401R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4302MH0008880001503402S00	
mhl100308	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4302MH0003080011503365C00	3365	13907	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.4	4.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4302MH0008880001503399R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4302MH0008880001503400S00	
mhl100357	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 2 cm											
	4302MH0003570011503375C00	3375	14473	4.5	2.6	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.7	2.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4302MH0008880001503397R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4302MH0008880001503398S00	

target named Sandy_Meadow

mhl100862	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	4302MH0008620011503385C00	3385	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4302MH0008880001503395R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4302MH0008880001503396S00	

SOL 4304 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Wales_Lake** – before DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4304MH0001900011503406C00	3406	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhlI00122	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4304MH0001220011503408C00	3408	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7

target named **Wales_Lake** – after DRT

mhlI00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4304MH0001900011503410C00	3410	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4304MH0003360011503412C00	3412	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503505R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503506S00	
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4304MH0003360011503422C00	3422	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503503R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503504S00	
mhlI00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4304MH0008480011503432C00	3432	15117	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503501R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503502S00	
mhlI00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4304MH0003360011503442C00	3442	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503499R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503500S00	

target named **College_Rock**

mhlI00855	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4304MH0008550011503452C00	3452	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503497R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503498S00	
mhlI00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4304MH0002970011503462C00	3462	14007	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503495R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503496S00	
mhlI00297	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4304MH0002970011503472C00	3472	14006	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503493R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503494S00	
mhlI00406	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4304MH0004060011503482C00	3482	14903	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4306MH0001700001503491R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4306MH0001700001503492S00	

SOL 4307 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Grasshopper_Flat															
mhl100678	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4307MH0006780011503508C00	3508	12989	28.3	26.4	-2.0	2.3	106.6	7.6	1608	1198	17.1	12.8		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4307MH0002270001503574R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4307MH0002270001503575S00	
mhl100698	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4307MH0006980011503519C00	3519	14063	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4307MH0002270001503572R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4307MH0002270001503573S00	
mhl100698	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4307MH0006980011503530C00	3530	14162	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4307MH0002270001503570R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4307MH0002270001503571S00	

target named Frog_Lake – a 2 x 1 mosaic from 25 cm															
mhl100706	POSITION 1 OF 2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4307MH0007060011503541C00	3541	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4307MH0002270001503568R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4307MH0002270001503569S00	
mhl100706	POSITION 2 OF 2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4307MH0007060011503544C00	3544	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4307MH0002270001503568R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4307MH0002270001503569S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4307MH0002990011503547C00	3547	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4307MH0002270001503566R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4307MH0002270001503567S00	
mhl100299	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4307MH0002990011503557C00	3557	14043	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4307MH0002270001503566R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4307MH0002270001503567S00	

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4309 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named The_Minster – after DRT															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4309MH0001900011503577C00	3577	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4309MH0001680011503579C00	3579	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4309MH0001930001503612R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4309MH0001930001503613S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4309MH0001680011503589C00	3589	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4309MH0001930001503610R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4309MH0001930001503611S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm												
	4309MH0007430011503599C00	3599	14848	3.4	1.5	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.3		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4309MH0001930001503608R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4309MH0001930001503609S00

SOL 4311 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <u>Aeolian_Buttes</u>															
mhl100889	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4311MH0008890011503615C00	3615	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4312MH0008900001503703R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4312MH0008900001503704S00	
mhl100723	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4311MH0007230011503626C00	3626	14161	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4312MH0008900001503701R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4312MH0008900001503702S00	
mhl100723	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	4311MH0007230011503637C00	3637	14165	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4312MH0008900001503699R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4312MH0008900001503700S00	

target named <u>Cherry_Ridge - after DRT</u>															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm												
	4311MH0001900011503648C00	3648	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	4311MH0001680011503650C00	3650	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4312MH0008900001503697R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4312MH0008900001503698S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	4311MH0001680011503660C00	3660	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4312MH0008900001503695R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4312MH0008900001503696S00	
mhl100302	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 2 cm												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	4311MH0003020011503670C00	3670	14697	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4312MH0008900001503693R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4312MH0008900001503694S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1	4311MH0001680011503680C00	3680	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4312MH0008900001503691R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:								4312MH0008900001503692S00	

REMS UV sensor													
mhl100095	STANDARD VIEWING POSITION		INTENDED STANDOFF: ~15 cm										
	4311MH0000950011503690C00	3690	13262	16.6	14.7	-0.7	0.8	65.5	2.6	1608	1198	10.5	7.8

SOL 4312 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 4312)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4312MH0007690011503705E01	3705	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4312MH0007700011503706E01	3706	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4312MH0007710011503707E01	3707	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4312MH0007720011503708E01	3708	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 4312)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4312MH0007690011503709E01	3709	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4312MH0007700011503710E01	3710	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4312MH0007710011503711E01	3711	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4312MH0007720011503712E01	3712	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 4312)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4312MH0007690011503713E01	3713	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4312MH0007700011503714E01	3714	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4312MH0007710011503715E01	3715	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4312MH0007720011503716E01	3716	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 4312)

mhl100769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4312MH0007690011503717E01	3717	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl100770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4312MH0007700011503718E01	3718	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl100771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4312MH0007710011503719E01	3719	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl100772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4312MH0007720011503720E01	3720	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

CONTINUED ON NEXT PAGE..

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 4312)													
mhl00769	LEFT (PORT) REAR WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~170 cm											
	4312MH0007690011503721E01	3721	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~-612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	LEFT (PORT) MIDDLE WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~112 cm											
	4312MH0007700011503722E01	3722	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~-408	~-137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	LEFT (PORT) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~135 cm											
	4312MH0007710011503723E01	3723	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~-489	~-210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	RIGHT (STARBOARD) FRONT WHEEL												
	MANUAL FOCUS	INTENDED DISTANCE TO TOP OF WHEEL: ~124 cm											
	4312MH0007720011503724E01	3724	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~-450	~-175	1608	1198	~72	~54

UPDATED: 25_September_2024

SOL 4314 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGEY ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Burst_Rock													
mhl00359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm										
	4314MH0003590011503726C00	3726	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4314MH0001930001503759R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4314MH0001930001503760S00					
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4314MH0001680011503736C00	3736	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4314MH0001930001503757R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4314MH0001930001503758S00					
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm										
	4314MH0001680011503746C00	3746	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4314MH0001930001503755R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4314MH0001930001503756S00					

SOL 4316 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Aster_Lake

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	4316MH0003590011503762C00	3762	13029	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4316MH0001630001503831R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4316MH0001630001503832S00	
mhl100878	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 10 cm											
	4316MH0008780011503772C00	3772	13569	10.9	9.0	-0.3	0.3	45.2	1.2	1608	1198	7.3	5.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4316MH0001630001503829R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4316MH0001630001503830S00	
mhl100878	INTERMEDIATE-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 10 cm											
	4316MH0008780011503782C00	3782	13560	11.0	9.1	-0.4	0.3	45.6	1.2	1608	1198	7.3	5.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4316MH0001630001503827R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4316MH0001630001503828S00	

target named Beryl_Lake

mhl100865	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 25 cm											
	4316MH0008650011503792C00	3792	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4316MH0001630001503825R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4316MH0001630001503826S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4316MH0001520011503802C00	3802	14063	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4316MH0001630001503823R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4316MH0001630001503824S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF ~ 5 cm											
	4316MH0001520011503812C00	3812	14082	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4316MH0001630001503821R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4316MH0001630001503822S00	

SOL 4318 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Angora_Mountain													
mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4318MH000760011503834C00	3834	13041	25.1	23.2	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	1608	1198	15.3	11.4
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503960R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503951S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4318MH0002240011503844C00	3844	14368	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503958R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503959S00					
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4318MH0002240011503854C00	3854	14347	5.0	3.1	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503956R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503957S00					

target named Moonlight_Lake													
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4318MH0007060011503864C00	3864	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhl100740	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4318MH0007400011503867C00	3867	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503954R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503955S00					
mhl100740	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4318MH0007400011503878C00	3878	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503952R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503953S00					
mhl100710	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 15 mm										
	4318MH0007100011503889C00	3889	14931	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503950R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503951S00					

target named Cloud_Canyon													
mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm										
	4318MH0007060011503900C00	3900	13010	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2
mhl100699	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4318MH0006990011503903C00	3903	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503948R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503949S00					
mhl100699	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm										
	4318MH0006990011503914C00	3914	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503946R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503947S00					
mhl100794	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm										
	4318MH0007940011503925C00	3925	15177	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503944R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4319MH0005360001503945S00					

MAHLI calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGES TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGES.													
mhl100371	BAR TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4318MH0003710011503936C00	3936	14373	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100372	CENT TARGET - 5 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4318MH0003720011503938C00	3938	14365	4.9	3.0	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	1608	1198	3.9	2.9
mhl100374	CALIBRATION TARGET + FRONT LEFT WHEEL + SURFACE - 30 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	AUTOFOCUS ON CALIBRATION TARGET												
	4318MH0003740011503940C00	3940	12963	30.2	28.3	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	1608	1198	18.2	13.6
mhl100374	MANUAL INFINITY FOCUS												
	4318MH0003740021503941C00	3941	12552	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)	1608	1198	(INFINITY)	(INFINITY)

APXS calibration target													
NOTE: ONE CAN ALSO USE FEATURES IN THESE IMAGE(S) TO DETERMINE SCALE; THE SCALE INFORMATION PRESENTED HERE IS BASED ON MOTOR COUNT, NOT ANALYSIS OF THE IMAGE(S).													
mhl100373	6.9 cm WORKING DISTANCE												
	4318MH0003730011503943C00	3943	13944	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

UPDATED: 02_October_2024

SOL 4321 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Flat_Note_Lake													
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm									
	4321MH0001900011503963C00	3963	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4321MH0003360011503965C00	3965	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4321MH0001930001503996R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4321MH0001930001503995S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm									
	4321MH0003360011503975C00	3975	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4321MH0001930001503996R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4321MH0001930001503997S00	
mhl00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF - 1 cm									
	4321MH0008480011503985C00	3985	15118	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4321MH0001930001503994R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:				4321MH0001930001503995S00	

UPDATED: 04_October_2024

SOL 4323 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named <u>Sub_Dome</u>														
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4323MH0001900011504001C00	4001	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4323MH0001680011504003C00	4003	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4323MH0002650001504024R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4323MH0002650001504025S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4323MH0001680011504013C00	4013	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4323MH0002650001504022R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4323MH0002650001504023S00

UPDATED: 08_October_2024

SOL 4325 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Kidney_Lake**

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4325MH0007060011504027C00	4027	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
mhl100699	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4325MH0006990011504030C00	4030	14166	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4326MH0008910001504094R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4326MH0008910001504095S00	

target named **Pumice_Flat**

mhl100706	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4325MH0007060011504041C00	4041	13038	25.3	23.4	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.5		
mhl100834	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4325MH0008340011504044C00	4044	14253	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4326MH0008910001504092R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4326MH0008910001504093S00	

target named **Ribbon_Fall – after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4325MH0001900011504055C00	4055	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4325MH0003360011504057C00	4057	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4326MH0008910001504090R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4326MH0008910001504091S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4325MH0003360011504067C00	4067	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4326MH0008910001504088R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4326MH0008910001504089S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm												
	4325MH0008480011504077C00	4077	15183	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4326MH0008910001504086R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4326MH0008910001504087S00	

SOL 4327 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)
target named Pincushion_Peak – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data													
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW												
	4327MH0001900011504097C00	4097	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl100336	MED RES – STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4327MH0003360011504099C00	4099	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:												
		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504150R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504151S00			
mhl100336	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4327MH0003360011504109C00	4109	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:												
		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504148R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504149S00			
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4327MH0007050011504119C00	4119	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4327MH0007050011504121C00	4121	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4327MH0007050011504123C00	4123	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2												
	4327MH0008480011504125C00	4125	15052	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:												
		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504146R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504147S00			
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW												
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1												
	4327MH0003360011504135C00	4135	13979	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:												
		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504144R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4328MH0001530001504145S00			

SOL 4331 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Midnight_Lake** – after DRT – quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4331MH0001900011504153C00	4153	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00336	MED RES – STEREO-1 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4331MH0003360011504155C00	4155	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4332MH0001530001504206R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4332MH0001530001504207S00	
mhl00336	MED RES – STEREO-2 & RELIEF MODEL POSITION 2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4331MH0003360011504165C00	4165	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4332MH0001530001504204R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4332MH0001530001504205S00	
mhl00705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4331MH0007050011504175C00	4175	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
mhl00705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 4	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4331MH0007050011504177C00	4177	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
mhl00705	MED RES – RELIEF MODEL POSITION 5	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4331MH0007050011504179C00	4179	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
mhl00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4331MH0008480011504181C00	4181	15181	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4332MH0001530001504202R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4332MH0001530001504203S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4331MH0003360011504191C00	4191	14224	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4332MH0001530001504200R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4332MH0001530001504201S00	

UPDATED: 15_October_2024

SOL 4334 - MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Dollar_Lake															
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF - 25 cm												
	4334MH001900011504209C00	4209	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4334MH003360011504211C00	4211	14076	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4334MH0002650001504232R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4334MH0002650001504233S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF - 5 cm												
	4334MH003360011504221C00	4221	14094	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4334MH0002650001504230R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4334MH0002650001504231S00

UPDATED: 17_October_2024

SOL 4336 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA _PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE ($\mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY ($\pm \mu\text{m}/\text{pixel}$)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ- ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Jumble_Lake															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm												
	4336MH0001900011504235C00	4235	13038	25.3	23.4	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.5		
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4336MH0001820011504237C00	4237	14231	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4336MH0002650001504258R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4336MH0002650001504259S00
mhl00182	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm												
	4336MH0001820011504247C00	4247	14208	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4336MH0002650001504256R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4336MH0002650001504257S00

SOL 4338 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13148/R6.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Polly_Dome

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4339MH0001900011504261C00	4261	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7		
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4339MH0001680011504263C00	4263	14124	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504358R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504359S00	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4339MH0001680011504273C00	4273	14135	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.4		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504356R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504357S00	

target named Noble_Canyon

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4339MH0003590011504283C00	4283	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504354R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504355S00	
mhl100673	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4339MH0006730011504293C00	4293	14081	6.3	4.4	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504352R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504353S00	
mhl100673	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4339MH0006730011504303C00	4303	14194	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504350R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504351S00	

target named Chapel_Lake – after DRT

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4339MH0001900011504313C00	4313	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4339MH0003360011504315C00	4315	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504348R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504349S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	4339MH0003360011504325C00	4325	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504346R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504347S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	4339MH0008480011504335C00	4335	15135	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4339MH0001700001504344R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4339MH0001700001504345S00	

UPDATED: 20_January_2025

SOL 4341 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Chuck_Pass – after DRT															
mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm													
	4341MH0001900011504361C00	4361	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4341MH0003360011504363C00	4363	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4342MH0001530001504408R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4342MH0001530001504409S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4341MH0003360011504373C00	4373	14019	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4342MH0001530001504406R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4342MH0001530001504407S00	
mhl00848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2														
	4341MH0008480011504383C00	4383	14911	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4342MH0001530001504404R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4342MH0001530001504405S00	
mhl00336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm													
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1														
	4341MH0003360011504393C00	4393	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4342MH0001530001504402R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4342MH0001530001504403S00	

SOL 4345 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

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 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Reef_Lake – a 3 x 1 mosaic

mhl00855	POSITION 1 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4345MH0008550011504411C00	4411	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504494R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504495S00					
mhl00855	POSITION 2 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4345MH0008550011504421C00	4421	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504492R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504493S00					
mhl00855	POSITION 3 OF 3	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4345MH0008550011504431C00	4431	13039	25.2	23.3	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.5
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504490R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504491S00					

target named Mount_Brewer – after DRT

mhl00190	CONTEXT VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm											
	4345MH0001900011504441C00	4441	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	4345MH0001680011504443C00	4443	13979	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504488R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504489S00					
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	4345MH0001680011504453C00	4453	13984	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504486R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504487S00					
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4348MH0001930001504500R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4348MH0001930001504501S00					
mhl00743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 2	4345MH0007430011504463C00	4463	15006	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.8
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504484R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504485S00					
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4348MH0001930001504498R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4348MH0001930001504499S00					
mhl00168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION VIEW	INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm											
	APXS RASTER SPOT 1	4345MH0001680011504473C00	4473	13977	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504482R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4346MH0001710001504483S00					
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4348MH0001930001504496R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4348MH0001930001504497S00					

SOL 4350 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named Ladder_Lake

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4350MH0001900011504503C00	4503	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4350MH0001680011504505C00	4505	14042	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4350MH0001630001504576R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4350MH0001630001504577S00
mhl100168	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4350MH0001680011504515C00	4515	14046	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4350MH0001630001504574R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4350MH0001630001504575S00
mhl100743	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4350MH0007430011504525C00	4525	15243	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4350MH0001630001504572R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4350MH0001630001504573S00

target named Reds_Meadow – after DRT

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)	PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)	
mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4350MH0001900011504535C00	4535	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4350MH0003360011504537C00	4537	14010	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4350MH0001630001504570R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4350MH0001630001504571S00
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2			INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4350MH0003360011504547C00	4547	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4350MH0001630001504568R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4350MH0001630001504569S00
mhl100864	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW			INTENDED STANDOFF – 15 mm										
	4350MH0008640011504557C00	4557	14917	3.2	1.3	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.2	
	CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:	BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4350MH0001630001504566R00				RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4350MH0001630001504567S00

SOL 4352 – MAHLI IMAGE RANGE & SCALE INFORMATION*

NOTE THAT OTHER IMAGES MIGHT HAVE BEEN ACQUIRED; THIS TABLE DOES NOT DESCRIBE ALL IMAGES; IT DESCRIBES EACH CAMERA POSITIONING.
 WORKING DISTANCE IS A PHOTOGRAPHY TERM; IT IS THE RANGE FROM THE MAHLI FRONT LENS ELEMENT(SAPPHIRE WINDOW) TO THE TARGET.
 STANDOFF DISTANCE IS MEASURED FROM THE PLANE DEFINED BY THE TIPS OF THE MAHLI CONTACT SENSOR PROBES TO THE TARGET.
 RANGE, SCALE AND DOF ARE COMPUTED FROM MOTOR COUNT USING THE EQUATIONS FROM VERSION 2 OF EDGETT ET AL. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

SEQUENCE	IMAGE ID*	MSL: CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE OR WORKING DISTANCE FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	STANDOFF (MAHLI TOOLFRAME +X) FROM MOTOR COUNT (cm)	DEPTH OF FIELD ESTIMATE		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (± µm/pixel)	ILLUMINATED PIXELS ON CCD (APPROXIMATE)		IMAGE DIMENSIONS (cm) (APPROXIMATE)	
						NEAR (cm)	FAR (cm)			HORIZ-ONTAL	VERTICAL	HORIZONTAL (CCD COLUMNS)	VERTICAL (CCD ROWS)

target named **Stag_Dome**

mhl100876	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4352MH0008760011504579C00	4579	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404686R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404687S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4352MH0002240011504589C00	4589	14197	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404684R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404685S00	
mhl100224	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4352MH0002240011504599C00	4599	14196	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404682R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404683S00	

target named **Eureka_Valley – after DRT**

mhl100190	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4352MH0001900011504609C00	4609	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404680R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404681S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4352MH0003360011504611C00	4611	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404680R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404681S00	
mhl100336	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4352MH0003360011504621C00	4621	14001	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404678R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404679S00	
mhl100848	HIGH RESOLUTION VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 1 cm										
	4352MH0008480011504631C00	4631	15116	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404676R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404677S00	

target named **Black_Bear_Lake**

mhl100359	CONTEXT VIEW		INTENDED STANDOFF – 25 cm										
	4352MH0003590011504641C00	4641	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404674R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404675S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-1		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4352MH0001520011504651C00	4651	14163	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404672R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404673S00	
mhl100152	MEDIUM-RESOLUTION STEREO-2		INTENDED STANDOFF – 5 cm										
	4352MH0001520011504661C00	4661	14158	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
CORRESPONDING FOCUS MERGE PRODUCTS:		BEST FOCUS PRODUCT:		4353MH0005360001404670R00		RANGE MAP PRODUCT:						4353MH0005360001404671S00	

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 4258–4354 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 4277, 4280, 4282, 4289, 4291, 4294, 4295, 4297, 4300, 4302, 4304, 4307, 4309, 4311, 4314, 4316, 4318, 4321, 4323, 4325, 4327, 4331, 4334, 4336, 4338, 4341, 4345, 4350, 4352**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That

motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3, Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN

values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocusing (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2**

(**Equations 1 and 3**, respectively). Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

UPDATED: 19_August_2024

SOL 4277 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4277MH0002240011502763C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4277MH0002580001502772R00	2772	MOTOR COUNT:		14182	RANGE (cm):		5.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4277MH0002580001502773S00	2773	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhl100224		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Aug-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhl100258		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4277		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4277
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4277MH0002240021502764C00	2764	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	255	1
4277MH0002240021502765C00	2765	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
4277MH0002240021502766C00	2766	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3
4277MH0002240021502767C00	2767	14140	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
4277MH0002240021502768C00	2768	14182	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
4277MH0002240021502769C00	2769	14224	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	95	6
4277MH0002240021502770C00	2770	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	63	7
4277MH0002240021502771C00	2771	14308	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 26_August_2024

SOL 4280 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Gabbot_Pass - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4280MH0003360011502788C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4281MH0001930001502823R00	2823	MOTOR COUNT:		13997	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4281MH0001930001502824S00	2824	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4280	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4281	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4280MH0003360021502789C00	2789	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4280MH0003360021502790C00	2790	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4280MH0003360021502791C00	2791	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4280MH0003360021502792C00	2792	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4280MH0003360021502793C00	2793	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4280MH0003360021502794C00	2794	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4280MH0003360021502795C00	2795	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4280MH0003360021502796C00	2796	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 26_August_2024

SOL 4280 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Gabbot_Pass - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4280MH0003360011502798C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4281MH0001930001502821R00	2821	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4281MH0001930001502822S00	2822	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4280	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4281	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4280MH0003360021502799C00	2799	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4280MH0003360021502800C00	2800	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4280MH0003360021502801C00	2801	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4280MH0003360021502802C00	2802	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4280MH0003360021502803C00	2803	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4280MH0003360021502804C00	2804	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4280MH0003360021502805C00	2805	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4280MH0003360021502806C00	2806	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 26_August_2024

SOL 4280 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Gabbot_Pass - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4280MH0008480011502808C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4281MH0001930001502819R00	2819	MOTOR COUNT:		15088	RANGE (cm):		2.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4281MH0001930001502820S00	2820	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Aug-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4280		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4281
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4280MH0008480021502809C00	2809	14992	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
4280MH0008480021502810C00	2810	15016	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
4280MH0008480021502811C00	2811	15040	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
4280MH0008480021502812C00	2812	15064	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
4280MH0008480021502813C00	2813	15088	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	127	5
4280MH0008480021502814C00	2814	15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
4280MH0008480021502815C00	2815	15136	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	63	7
4280MH0008480021502816C00	2816	15160	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 26_August_2024

SOL 4282 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Marck_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4282MH0003360011502828C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4282MH0001930001502861R00	2861	MOTOR COUNT:		14013	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4282MH0001930001502862S00	2862	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4282	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4282		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4282MH0003360021502829C00	2829	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4282MH0003360021502830C00	2830	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4282MH0003360021502831C00	2831	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4282MH0003360021502832C00	2832	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4282MH0003360021502833C00	2833	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4282MH0003360021502834C00	2834	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4282MH0003360021502835C00	2835	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4282MH0003360021502836C00	2836	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_August_2024

SOL 4282 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Marck_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4282MH0003360011502838C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4282MH0001930001502859R00	2859	MOTOR COUNT:		14020	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4282MH0001930001502860S00	2860	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4282	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4282		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4282MH0003360021502839C00	2839	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4282MH0003360021502840C00	2840	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4282MH0003360021502841C00	2841	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4282MH0003360021502842C00	2842	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4282MH0003360021502843C00	2843	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4282MH0003360021502844C00	2844	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4282MH0003360021502845C00	2845	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4282MH0003360021502846C00	2846	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 26_August_2024

SOL 4282 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Marck_Lake – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4282MH0008480011502848C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4282MH0001930001502857R00	2857	MOTOR COUNT:		15150	RANGE (cm):		2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4282MH0001930001502858S00	2858	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Aug-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4282		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4282
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4282MH0008480021502849C00	2849	15054	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	255	1
4282MH0008480021502850C00	2850	15078	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	223	2
4282MH0008480021502851C00	2851	15102	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	191	3
4282MH0008480021502852C00	2852	15126	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4282MH0008480021502853C00	2853	15150	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	127	5
4282MH0008480021502854C00	2854	15174	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
4282MH0008480021502855C00	2855	15198	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	63	7
4282MH0008480021502856C00	2856	15222	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 05_September_2024

SOL 4289 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4289MH0003360011502866C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4289MH0001630001502938R00	2938	MOTOR COUNT:		14012	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4289MH0001630001502939S00	2939	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4289	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4289		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4289MH0003360021502867C00	2867	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4289MH0003360021502868C00	2868	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
4289MH0003360021502869C00	2869	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4289MH0003360021502870C00	2870	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4289MH0003360021502871C00	2871	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4289MH0003360021502872C00	2872	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4289MH0003360021502873C00	2873	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4289MH0003360021502874C00	2874	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_September_2024

SOL 4289 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4289MH0003360011502876C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4289MH0001630001502936R00	2936	MOTOR COUNT:		14025	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4289MH0001630001502937S00	2937	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4289	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4289		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4289MH0003360021502877C00	2877	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4289MH0003360021502878C00	2878	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4289MH0003360021502879C00	2879	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
4289MH0003360021502880C00	2880	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
4289MH0003360021502881C00	2881	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4289MH0003360021502882C00	2882	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
4289MH0003360021502883C00	2883	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4289MH0003360021502884C00	2884	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 05_September_2024

SOL 4289 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eichorn_Pinnacle – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4289MH0008730011502886C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4289MH0001630001502934R00	2934	MOTOR COUNT:		14738	RANGE (cm):	3.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4289MH0001630001502935S00	2935	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00873	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4289	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4289	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4289MH0008730021502887C00	2887	14642	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	255	1
4289MH0008730021502888C00	2888	14666	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	223	2
4289MH0008730021502889C00	2889	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	191	3
4289MH0008730021502890C00	2890	14714	3.74	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	159	4
4289MH0008730021502891C00	2891	14738	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	127	5
4289MH0008730021502892C00	2892	14762	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	95	6
4289MH0008730021502893C00	2893	14786	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
4289MH0008730021502894C00	2894	14810	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 05_September_2024

SOL 4289 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Thousand_Island_Lake – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4289MH0008620011502896C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4289MH0001630001502932R00	2932	MOTOR COUNT:		13011	RANGE (cm):	26.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4289MH0001630001502933S00	2933	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00862	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Aug-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4289	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4289	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4289MH0008620031502898C00	2898	12939	32.19	-2.6	3.0	120.2	9.8	255	1
4289MH0008620031502899C00	2899	12957	30.69	-2.3	2.7	114.9	8.9	223	2
4289MH0008620031502900C00	2900	12975	29.32	-2.2	2.5	110.1	8.1	191	3
4289MH0008620031502901C00	2901	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	159	4
4289MH0008620031502902C00	2902	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	127	5
4289MH0008620031502903C00	2903	13029	25.81	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	95	6
4289MH0008620031502904C00	2904	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	63	7
4289MH0008620031502905C00	2905	13065	23.87	-1.5	1.6	90.9	5.4	31	8

UPDATED: 05_September_2024

SOL 4289 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - ~15 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4289MH0008850011502907C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4289MH0001630001502930R00	2930	MOTOR COUNT:		13268	RANGE (cm):	16.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4289MH0001630001502931S00	2931	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00885	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Aug-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4289	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4289	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4289MH0008850031502909C00	2909	13172	19.39	-1.0	1.0	75.2	3.6	255	1
4289MH0008850031502910C00	2910	13196	18.59	-0.9	1.0	72.3	3.3	223	2
4289MH0008850031502911C00	2911	13220	17.84	-0.8	0.9	69.7	3.0	191	3
4289MH0008850031502912C00	2912	13244	17.14	-0.8	0.8	67.2	2.8	159	4
4289MH0008850031502913C00	2913	13268	16.49	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	127	5
4289MH0008850031502914C00	2914	13292	15.88	-0.7	0.7	62.8	2.4	95	6
4289MH0008850031502915C00	2915	13316	15.30	-0.6	0.6	60.8	2.2	63	7
4289MH0008850031502916C00	2916	13340	14.76	-0.6	0.6	58.9	2.1	31	8

UPDATED: 05_September_2024

SOL 4289 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - ~14 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4289MH0008850011502918C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4289MH0001630001502928R00	2928	MOTOR COUNT:		13287	RANGE (cm):	16.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4289MH0001630001502929S00	2929	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00885	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	30-Aug-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4289	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4289	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4289MH0008850031502920C00	2920	13191	18.75	-0.9	1.0	72.9	3.3	255	1
4289MH0008850031502921C00	2921	13215	17.99	-0.9	0.9	70.2	3.1	223	2
4289MH0008850031502922C00	2922	13239	17.28	-0.8	0.8	67.7	2.8	191	3
4289MH0008850031502923C00	2923	13263	16.62	-0.7	0.8	65.4	2.6	159	4
4289MH0008850031502924C00	2924	13287	16.00	-0.7	0.7	63.2	2.5	127	5
4289MH0008850031502925C00	2925	13311	15.42	-0.6	0.7	61.2	2.3	95	6
4289MH0008850031502926C00	2926	13335	14.87	-0.6	0.6	59.3	2.1	63	7
4289MH0008850031502927C00	2927	13359	14.36	-0.6	0.6	57.4	2.0	31	8

UPDATED: 15_May_2025

SOL 4291 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4291MH0003360011502943C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4293MH0001630001503014R00	3014	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4293MH0001630001503015S00	3015	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4291	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4293	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4291MH0003360021502944C00	2944	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4291MH0003360021502945C00	2945	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4291MH0003360021502946C00	2946	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4291MH0003360021502947C00	2947	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4291MH0003360021502948C00	2948	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4291MH0003360021502949C00	2949	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4291MH0003360021502950C00	2950	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4291MH0003360021502951C00	2951	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 15_May_2025

SOL 4291 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4291MH0003360011502953C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4293MH0001630001503012R00	3012	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4293MH0001630001503013S00	3013	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4291	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4293	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4291MH0003360021502954C00	2954	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4291MH0003360021502955C00	2955	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4291MH0003360021502956C00	2956	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4291MH0003360021502957C00	2957	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4291MH0003360021502958C00	2958	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4291MH0003360021502959C00	2959	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4291MH0003360021502960C00	2960	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4291MH0003360021502961C00	2961	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 15_May_2025

SOL 4291 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4291MH0008640011502963C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4293MH0001630001503010R00	3010	MOTOR COUNT:		14915	RANGE (cm):	3.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4293MH0001630001503011S00	3011	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4291	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4293		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4291MH0008640021502964C00	2964	14795	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	255	1
4291MH0008640021502965C00	2965	14825	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	223	2
4291MH0008640021502966C00	2966	14855	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	191	3
4291MH0008640021502967C00	2967	14885	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	159	4
4291MH0008640021502968C00	2968	14915	3.23	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	127	5
4291MH0008640021502969C00	2969	14945	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	95	6
4291MH0008640021502970C00	2970	14975	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	63	7
4291MH0008640021502971C00	2971	15005	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 15_May_2025

SOL 4291 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4291MH0003360011502975C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4293MH0001630001503008R00	3008	MOTOR COUNT:		13981	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4293MH0001630001503009S00	3009	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4291	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4293		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4291MH0003360021502976C00	2976	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4291MH0003360021502977C00	2977	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4291MH0003360021502978C00	2978	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4291MH0003360021502979C00	2979	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
4291MH0003360021502980C00	2980	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4291MH0003360021502981C00	2981	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
4291MH0003360021502982C00	2982	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4291MH0003360021502983C00	2983	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 15_May_2025

SOL 4291 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4291MH0003360011502985C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4293MH0001630001503006R00		3006		MOTOR COUNT:		13978		RANGE (cm): 7.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503007S00		3007		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4291		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4293	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4291MH0003360021502986C00	2986	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1		
4291MH0003360021502987C00	2987	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2		
4291MH0003360021502988C00	2988	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3		
4291MH0003360021502989C00	2989	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4		
4291MH0003360021502990C00	2990	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5		
4291MH0003360021502991C00	2991	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6		
4291MH0003360021502992C00	2992	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7		
4291MH0003360021502993C00	2993	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	31	8		

UPDATED: 15_May_2025

SOL 4291 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake – after DRT – ~2 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4291MH0008730011502995C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4293MH0001630001503004R00		3004		MOTOR COUNT:		14631		RANGE (cm): 4.0	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4293MH0001630001503005S00		3005		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00873		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		1-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4291		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4293	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4291MH0008730021502996C00	2996	14535	4.30	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	255	1		
4291MH0008730021502997C00	2997	14559	4.22	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	223	2		
4291MH0008730021502998C00	2998	14583	4.14	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	191	3		
4291MH0008730021502999C00	2999	14607	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4		
4291MH0008730021503000C00	3000	14631	3.99	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	127	5		
4291MH0008730021503001C00	3001	14655	3.92	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	95	6		
4291MH0008730021503002C00	3002	14679	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	63	7		
4291MH0008730021503003C00	3003	14703	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_September_2024

SOL 4294 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Erin_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4294MH0001680011503019C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4294MH0001630001503088R00	3088	MOTOR COUNT:		14045	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4294MH0001630001503089S00	3089	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4294	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4294		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4294MH0001680021503020C00	3020	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4294MH0001680021503021C00	3021	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4294MH0001680021503022C00	3022	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4294MH0001680021503023C00	3023	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4294MH0001680021503024C00	3024	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4294MH0001680021503025C00	3025	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4294MH0001680021503026C00	3026	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4294MH0001680021503027C00	3027	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_September_2024

SOL 4294 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Erin_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4294MH0001680011503029C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4294MH0001630001503086R00	3086	MOTOR COUNT:		14047	RANGE (cm):	6.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4294MH0001630001503087S00	3087	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4294	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4294		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4294MH0001680021503030C00	3030	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4294MH0001680021503031C00	3031	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4294MH0001680021503032C00	3032	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
4294MH0001680021503033C00	3033	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
4294MH0001680021503034C00	3034	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
4294MH0001680021503035C00	3035	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4294MH0001680021503036C00	3036	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4294MH0001680021503037C00	3037	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_September_2024

SOL 4294 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Erin_Lake - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4294MH0003020011503039C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4294MH0001630001503084R00	3084	MOTOR COUNT:		14788	RANGE (cm):	3.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4294MH0001630001503085S00	3085	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4294	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4294		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4294MH0003020021503040C00	3040	14668	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	255	1
4294MH0003020021503041C00	3041	14698	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	223	2
4294MH0003020021503042C00	3042	14728	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	191	3
4294MH0003020021503043C00	3043	14758	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	159	4
4294MH0003020021503044C00	3044	14788	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	127	5
4294MH0003020021503045C00	3045	14818	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	95	6
4294MH0003020021503046C00	3046	14848	3.39	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	63	7
4294MH0003020021503047C00	3047	14878	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 09_September_2024

SOL 4294 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Picture_Puzzle - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4294MH0003590011503049C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4294MH0001630001503082R00	3082	MOTOR COUNT:		13031	RANGE (cm):	25.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4294MH0001630001503083S00	3083	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	4-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4294	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4294		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4294MH0003590021503050C00	3050	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	255	1
4294MH0003590021503051C00	3051	12977	29.18	-2.1	2.4	109.6	8.0	223	2
4294MH0003590021503052C00	3052	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	191	3
4294MH0003590021503053C00	3053	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	159	4
4294MH0003590021503054C00	3054	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
4294MH0003590021503055C00	3055	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	95	6
4294MH0003590021503056C00	3056	13067	23.77	-1.4	1.6	90.6	5.3	63	7
4294MH0003590021503057C00	3057	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 09_September_2024

SOL 4294 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4294MH0002240011503059C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4294MH0001630001503080R00		3080		MOTOR COUNT:		14338		RANGE (cm):	5.1
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503081S00		3081		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4294		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4294	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4294MH0002240021503060C00	3060	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	255	1		
4294MH0002240021503061C00	3061	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	223	2		
4294MH0002240021503062C00	3062	14254	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	191	3		
4294MH0002240021503063C00	3063	14296	5.24	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	159	4		
4294MH0002240021503064C00	3064	14338	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	127	5		
4294MH0002240021503065C00	3065	14380	4.88	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	95	6		
4294MH0002240021503066C00	3066	14422	4.71	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	63	7		
4294MH0002240021503067C00	3067	14464	4.55	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_September_2024

SOL 4294 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4294MH0002240011503069C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4294MH0001630001503078R00		3078		MOTOR COUNT:		14351		RANGE (cm):	5.0
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4294MH0001630001503079S00		3079		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		4-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4294		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4294	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4294MH0002240021503070C00	3070	14183	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	255	1		
4294MH0002240021503071C00	3071	14225	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	223	2		
4294MH0002240021503072C00	3072	14267	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	191	3		
4294MH0002240021503073C00	3073	14309	5.18	-0.1	0.1	25.1	0.4	159	4		
4294MH0002240021503074C00	3074	14351	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	127	5		
4294MH0002240021503075C00	3075	14393	4.83	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	95	6		
4294MH0002240021503076C00	3076	14435	4.66	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	63	7		
4294MH0002240021503077C00	3077	14477	4.51	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	31	8		

UPDATED: 10_September_2024

SOL 4295 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Campfire_Lake - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4295MH0003590011503091C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4295MH0001710001503172R00	3172	MOTOR COUNT:		13009	RANGE (cm):	27.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4295MH0001710001503173S00	3173	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4295	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4295	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4295MH0003590021503092C00	3092	12937	32.36	-2.6	3.1	120.8	9.9	255	1
4295MH0003590021503093C00	3093	12955	30.85	-2.4	2.8	115.5	9.0	223	2
4295MH0003590021503094C00	3094	12973	29.47	-2.2	2.5	110.6	8.2	191	3
4295MH0003590021503095C00	3095	12991	28.19	-2.0	2.3	106.1	7.5	159	4
4295MH0003590021503096C00	3096	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	127	5
4295MH0003590021503097C00	3097	13027	25.93	-1.7	1.9	98.2	6.3	95	6
4295MH0003590021503098C00	3098	13045	24.91	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.8	63	7
4295MH0003590021503099C00	3099	13063	23.97	-1.5	1.6	91.3	5.4	31	8

UPDATED: 10_September_2024

SOL 4295 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4295MH0002240011503101C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4295MH0001710001503170R00	3170	MOTOR COUNT:		13940	RANGE (cm):	7.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4295MH0001710001503171S00	3171	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4295	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4295	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4295MH0002240021503102C00	3102	13772	8.62	-0.2	0.2	37.3	0.8	255	1
4295MH0002240021503103C00	3103	13814	8.25	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2
4295MH0002240021503104C00	3104	13856	7.89	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	191	3
4295MH0002240021503105C00	3105	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	159	4
4295MH0002240021503106C00	3106	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	127	5
4295MH0002240021503107C00	3107	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
4295MH0002240021503108C00	3108	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4295MH0002240021503109C00	3109	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_September_2024

SOL 4295 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4295MH0002240011503111C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4295MH0001710001503168R00		3168		MOTOR COUNT:		13921		RANGE (cm): 7.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4295MH0001710001503169S00		3169		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4295		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4295	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4295MH0002240021503112C00	3112	13753	8.80	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1		
4295MH0002240021503113C00	3113	13795	8.41	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	223	2		
4295MH0002240021503114C00	3114	13837	8.05	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3		
4295MH0002240021503115C00	3115	13879	7.71	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	159	4		
4295MH0002240021503116C00	3116	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	127	5		
4295MH0002240021503117C00	3117	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	95	6		
4295MH0002240021503118C00	3118	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7		
4295MH0002240021503119C00	3119	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 10_September_2024

SOL 4295 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - ~55 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4295MH0002240011503121C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4295MH0001710001503166R00		3166		MOTOR COUNT:		13931		RANGE (cm): 7.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4295MH0001710001503167S00		3167		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		5-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4295		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4295	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4295MH0002240021503122C00	3122	13763	8.71	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1		
4295MH0002240021503123C00	3123	13805	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2		
4295MH0002240021503124C00	3124	13847	7.97	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	191	3		
4295MH0002240021503125C00	3125	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	159	4		
4295MH0002240021503126C00	3126	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	127	5		
4295MH0002240021503127C00	3127	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6		
4295MH0002240021503128C00	3128	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7		
4295MH0002240021503129C00	3129	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 10_September_2024

SOL 4295 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Gemini - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4295MH0003590011503131C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4295MH0001710001503164R00	3164	MOTOR COUNT:		13014	RANGE (cm):	26.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4295MH0001710001503165S00	3165	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4295	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4295		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4295MH0003590021503132C00	3132	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	255	1
4295MH0003590021503133C00	3133	12960	30.46	-2.3	2.7	114.1	8.8	223	2
4295MH0003590021503134C00	3134	12978	29.10	-2.1	2.4	109.4	8.0	191	3
4295MH0003590021503135C00	3135	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	159	4
4295MH0003590021503136C00	3136	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	127	5
4295MH0003590021503137C00	3137	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	95	6
4295MH0003590021503138C00	3138	13050	24.64	-1.5	1.7	93.7	5.7	63	7
4295MH0003590021503139C00	3139	13068	23.72	-1.4	1.6	90.4	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 10_September_2024

SOL 4295 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Gemini - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4295MH0002240011503141C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4295MH0001710001503162R00	3162	MOTOR COUNT:		13996	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4295MH0001710001503163S00	3163	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4295	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4295		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4295MH0002240021503142C00	3142	13828	8.13	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	255	1
4295MH0002240021503143C00	3143	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
4295MH0002240021503144C00	3144	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
4295MH0002240021503145C00	3145	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
4295MH0002240021503146C00	3146	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4295MH0002240021503147C00	3147	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4295MH0002240021503148C00	3148	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4295MH0002240021503149C00	3149	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 10_September_2024

SOL 4295 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Gemini – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4295MH0002240011503151C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4295MH0001710001503160R00	3160	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4295MH0001710001503161S00	3161	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	5-Sep-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4295		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4295
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4295MH0002240021503152C00	3152	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	255	1
4295MH0002240021503153C00	3153	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
4295MH0002240021503154C00	3154	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
4295MH0002240021503155C00	3155	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4295MH0002240021503156C00	3156	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4295MH0002240021503157C00	3157	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4295MH0002240021503158C00	3158	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4295MH0002240021503159C00	3159	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4297 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Bird_Lake - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4297MH0008650011503175C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4298MH0001630001503244R00	3244	MOTOR COUNT:		13035	RANGE (cm):	25.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4298MH0001630001503245S00	3245	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4297	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4298		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4297MH0008650021503176C00	3176	12939	32.19	-2.6	3.0	120.2	9.8	255	1
4297MH0008650021503177C00	3177	12963	30.22	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	223	2
4297MH0008650021503178C00	3178	12987	28.47	-2.0	2.3	107.1	7.7	191	3
4297MH0008650021503179C00	3179	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	159	4
4297MH0008650021503180C00	3180	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	127	5
4297MH0008650021503181C00	3181	13059	24.17	-1.5	1.6	92.0	5.5	95	6
4297MH0008650021503182C00	3182	13083	22.99	-1.4	1.5	87.8	5.0	63	7
4297MH0008650021503183C00	3183	13107	21.91	-1.2	1.3	84.0	4.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4297 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4297MH0003060011503185C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4298MH0001630001503242R00	3242	MOTOR COUNT:		14234	RANGE (cm):	5.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4298MH0001630001503243S00	3243	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4297	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4298		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4297MH0003060021503186C00	3186	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
4297MH0003060021503187C00	3187	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
4297MH0003060021503188C00	3188	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3
4297MH0003060021503189C00	3189	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	159	4
4297MH0003060021503190C00	3190	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	127	5
4297MH0003060021503191C00	3191	14288	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	95	6
4297MH0003060021503192C00	3192	14342	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	63	7
4297MH0003060021503193C00	3193	14396	4.81	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4297 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4297MH0003060011503195C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4298MH0001630001503240R00	3240	MOTOR COUNT:		14274	RANGE (cm):		5.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4298MH0001630001503241S00	3241	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00306		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Sep-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4297	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4298	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4297MH0003060021503196C00	3196	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	255	1
4297MH0003060021503197C00	3197	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	223	2
4297MH0003060021503198C00	3198	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	191	3
4297MH0003060021503199C00	3199	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	159	4
4297MH0003060021503200C00	3200	14274	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	127	5
4297MH0003060021503201C00	3201	14328	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	95	6
4297MH0003060021503202C00	3202	14382	4.87	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	63	7
4297MH0003060021503203C00	3203	14436	4.66	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4297 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Baldy - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4297MH0008550011503205C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4298MH0001630001503238R00	3238	MOTOR COUNT:		13034	RANGE (cm):		25.5	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4298MH0001630001503239S00	3239	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Sep-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4297	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4298	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4297MH0008550021503206C00	3206	12914	34.50	-2.9	3.5	128.4	11.3	255	1
4297MH0008550021503207C00	3207	12944	31.76	-2.5	2.9	118.7	9.6	223	2
4297MH0008550021503208C00	3208	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	191	3
4297MH0008550021503209C00	3209	13004	27.34	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	159	4
4297MH0008550021503210C00	3210	13034	25.52	-1.7	1.8	96.7	6.1	127	5
4297MH0008550021503211C00	3211	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	95	6
4297MH0008550021503212C00	3212	13094	22.49	-1.3	1.4	86.1	4.8	63	7
4297MH0008550021503213C00	3213	13124	21.20	-1.2	1.3	81.5	4.2	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4297 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4297MH0003830011503215C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4298MH0001630001503236R00	3236	MOTOR COUNT:		14186	RANGE (cm):	5.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4298MH0001630001503237S00	3237	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00383	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		90	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4297	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4298		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4297MH0003830021503216C00	3216	13826	8.14	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	255	1
4297MH0003830021503217C00	3217	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
4297MH0003830021503218C00	3218	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4297MH0003830021503219C00	3219	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	159	4
4297MH0003830021503220C00	3220	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
4297MH0003830021503221C00	3221	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	95	6
4297MH0003830021503222C00	3222	14366	4.94	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	63	7
4297MH0003830021503223C00	3223	14456	4.58	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4297 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4297MH0003830011503225C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4298MH0001630001503234R00	3234	MOTOR COUNT:		14167	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4298MH0001630001503235S00	3235	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00383	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	7-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		90	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4297	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4298		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4297MH0003830021503226C00	3226	13807	8.31	-0.2	0.2	36.1	0.8	255	1
4297MH0003830021503227C00	3227	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
4297MH0003830021503228C00	3228	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4297MH0003830021503229C00	3229	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	159	4
4297MH0003830021503230C00	3230	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	127	5
4297MH0003830021503231C00	3231	14257	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6
4297MH0003830021503232C00	3232	14347	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	63	7
4297MH0003830021503233C00	3233	14437	4.65	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~15 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0008870011503247C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4301MH0001700001503342R00	3342	MOTOR COUNT:		13257	RANGE (cm):		16.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4301MH0001700001503343S00	3343	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00887	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4300MH0008870021503248C00	3248	13065	23.87	-1.5	1.6	90.9	5.4	255	1
4300MH0008870021503249C00	3249	13113	21.66	-1.2	1.3	83.1	4.4	223	2
4300MH0008870021503250C00	3250	13161	19.78	-1.0	1.1	76.5	3.7	191	3
4300MH0008870021503251C00	3251	13209	18.18	-0.9	0.9	70.9	3.1	159	4
4300MH0008870021503252C00	3252	13257	16.78	-0.8	0.8	66.0	2.7	127	5
4300MH0008870021503253C00	3253	13305	15.56	-0.7	0.7	61.7	2.3	95	6
4300MH0008870021503254C00	3254	13353	14.49	-0.6	0.6	57.9	2.0	63	7
4300MH0008870021503255C00	3255	13401	13.53	-0.5	0.5	54.5	1.8	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~17 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0008870011503257C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4301MH0001700001503340R00	3340	MOTOR COUNT:		13177	RANGE (cm):		19.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4301MH0001700001503341S00	3341	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00887	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4300MH0008870021503258C00	3258	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	255	1
4300MH0008870021503259C00	3259	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	223	2
4300MH0008870021503260C00	3260	13081	23.09	-1.4	1.5	88.2	5.0	191	3
4300MH0008870021503261C00	3261	13129	21.00	-1.1	1.2	80.8	4.2	159	4
4300MH0008870021503262C00	3262	13177	19.22	-1.0	1.0	74.6	3.5	127	5
4300MH0008870021503263C00	3263	13225	17.69	-0.8	0.9	69.2	3.0	95	6
4300MH0008870021503264C00	3264	13273	16.36	-0.7	0.7	64.5	2.6	63	7
4300MH0008870021503265C00	3265	13321	15.19	-0.6	0.6	60.4	2.2	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~16 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0008870011503267C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4301MH0001700001503338R00		3338		MOTOR COUNT:		13206		RANGE (cm): 18.3	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503339S00		3339		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00887		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4300MH0008870021503268C00	3268	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	255	1		
4300MH0008870021503269C00	3269	13062	24.02	-1.5	1.6	91.5	5.4	223	2		
4300MH0008870021503270C00	3270	13110	21.78	-1.2	1.3	83.6	4.5	191	3		
4300MH0008870021503271C00	3271	13158	19.89	-1.0	1.1	76.9	3.8	159	4		
4300MH0008870021503272C00	3272	13206	18.27	-0.9	0.9	71.2	3.2	127	5		
4300MH0008870021503273C00	3273	13254	16.87	-0.8	0.8	66.3	2.7	95	6		
4300MH0008870021503274C00	3274	13302	15.64	-0.7	0.7	61.9	2.3	63	7		
4300MH0008870021503275C00	3275	13350	14.55	-0.6	0.6	58.1	2.0	31	8		

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pond_Lily_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0003360011503279C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4301MH0001700001503336R00		3336		MOTOR COUNT:		14004		RANGE (cm): 6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4301MH0001700001503337S00		3337		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		10-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4300MH0003360021503280C00	3280	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1		
4300MH0003360021503281C00	3281	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2		
4300MH0003360021503282C00	3282	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3		
4300MH0003360021503283C00	3283	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4		
4300MH0003360021503284C00	3284	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5		
4300MH0003360021503285C00	3285	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6		
4300MH0003360021503286C00	3286	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7		
4300MH0003360021503287C00	3287	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8		

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pond_Lily_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0003360011503289C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4301MH0001700001503334R00	3334	MOTOR COUNT:		14003	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4301MH0001700001503335S00	3335	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4300MH0003360021503290C00	3290	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4300MH0003360021503291C00	3291	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4300MH0003360021503292C00	3292	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4300MH0003360021503293C00	3293	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4300MH0003360021503294C00	3294	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4300MH0003360021503295C00	3295	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4300MH0003360021503296C00	3296	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4300MH0003360021503297C00	3297	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pond_Lily_Lake - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0008480011503299C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4301MH0001700001503332R00	3332	MOTOR COUNT:		15126	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4301MH0001700001503333S00	3333	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4300MH0008480021503300C00	3300	15030	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	255	1
4300MH0008480021503301C00	3301	15054	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	223	2
4300MH0008480021503302C00	3302	15078	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4300MH0008480021503303C00	3303	15102	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
4300MH0008480021503304C00	3304	15126	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
4300MH0008480021503305C00	3305	15150	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
4300MH0008480021503306C00	3306	15174	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4300MH0008480021503307C00	3307	15198	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - ~35 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0008860011503309C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4301MH0001700001503330R00	3330	MOTOR COUNT:		12894	RANGE (cm):	36.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4301MH0001700001503331S00	3331	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00886	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4300MH0008860021503310C00	3310	12798	51.10	-6.2	8.2	186.8	25.3	255	1
4300MH0008860021503311C00	3311	12822	46.55	-5.2	6.7	170.7	20.9	223	2
4300MH0008860021503312C00	3312	12846	42.71	-4.4	5.5	157.2	17.5	191	3
4300MH0008860021503313C00	3313	12870	39.43	-3.8	4.7	145.7	14.9	159	4
4300MH0008860021503314C00	3314	12894	36.59	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	127	5
4300MH0008860021503315C00	3315	12918	34.11	-2.9	3.4	127.0	11.1	95	6
4300MH0008860021503316C00	3316	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	63	7
4300MH0008860021503317C00	3317	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_September_2024

SOL 4300 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - ~35 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4300MH0008860011503319C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4301MH0001700001503328R00	3328	MOTOR COUNT:		12892	RANGE (cm):	36.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4301MH0001700001503329S00	3329	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00886	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	10-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4300	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4301	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4300MH0008860021503320C00	3320	12796	51.52	-6.3	8.3	188.3	25.7	255	1
4300MH0008860021503321C00	3321	12820	46.90	-5.3	6.8	172.0	21.2	223	2
4300MH0008860021503322C00	3322	12844	43.00	-4.5	5.6	158.3	17.7	191	3
4300MH0008860021503323C00	3323	12868	39.68	-3.8	4.7	146.6	15.0	159	4
4300MH0008860021503324C00	3324	12892	36.81	-3.3	4.0	136.5	12.9	127	5
4300MH0008860021503325C00	3325	12916	34.31	-2.9	3.5	127.7	11.2	95	6
4300MH0008860021503326C00	3326	12940	32.10	-2.6	3.0	119.9	9.8	63	7
4300MH0008860021503327C00	3327	12964	30.15	-2.3	2.6	113.0	8.6	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4302 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lucys_Foot_Pass – ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4302MH0008550011503345C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4302MH0008880001503403R00	3403	MOTOR COUNT:		13004	RANGE (cm):	27.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4302MH0008880001503404S00	3404	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00888	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4302	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4302		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4302MH0008550021503346C00	3346	12884	37.72	-3.5	4.2	139.7	13.6	255	1
4302MH0008550021503347C00	3347	12914	34.50	-2.9	3.5	128.4	11.3	223	2
4302MH0008550021503348C00	3348	12944	31.76	-2.5	2.9	118.7	9.6	191	3
4302MH0008550021503349C00	3349	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	159	4
4302MH0008550021503350C00	3350	13004	27.34	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	127	5
4302MH0008550021503351C00	3351	13034	25.52	-1.7	1.8	96.7	6.1	95	6
4302MH0008550021503352C00	3352	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	63	7
4302MH0008550021503353C00	3353	13094	22.49	-1.3	1.4	86.1	4.8	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4302 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lucys_Foot_Pass – stereo-1 – ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4302MH0003080011503355C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4302MH0008880001503401R00	3401	MOTOR COUNT:		13898	RANGE (cm):	7.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4302MH0008880001503402S00	3402	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00888	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4302	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4302		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4302MH0003080021503356C00	3356	13634	10.06	-0.3	0.3	42.3	1.0	255	1
4302MH0003080021503357C00	3357	13700	9.33	-0.3	0.3	39.7	0.9	223	2
4302MH0003080021503358C00	3358	13766	8.68	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	191	3
4302MH0003080021503359C00	3359	13832	8.09	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	159	4
4302MH0003080021503360C00	3360	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	127	5
4302MH0003080021503361C00	3361	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	95	6
4302MH0003080021503362C00	3362	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4302MH0003080021503363C00	3363	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4302 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lucys_Foot_Pass – stereo-2 – ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4302MH0003080011503365C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4302MH0008880001503399R00	3399	MOTOR COUNT:		13907	RANGE (cm):	7.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4302MH0008880001503400S00	3400	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00308	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00888	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		66	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4302	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4302		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4302MH0003080021503366C00	3366	13643	9.96	-0.3	0.3	41.9	1.0	255	1
4302MH0003080021503367C00	3367	13709	9.24	-0.3	0.3	39.4	0.9	223	2
4302MH0003080021503368C00	3368	13775	8.59	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	191	3
4302MH0003080021503369C00	3369	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	159	4
4302MH0003080021503370C00	3370	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	127	5
4302MH0003080021503371C00	3371	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	95	6
4302MH0003080021503372C00	3372	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4302MH0003080021503373C00	3373	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4302 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Lucys_Foot_Pass – ~25 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4302MH0003570011503375C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4302MH0008880001503397R00	3397	MOTOR COUNT:		14473	RANGE (cm):	4.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4302MH0008880001503398S00	3398	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00357	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00888	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		84	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4302	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4302		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4302MH0003570021503376C00	3376	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	255	1
4302MH0003570021503377C00	3377	14221	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	223	2
4302MH0003570021503378C00	3378	14305	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	191	3
4302MH0003570021503379C00	3379	14389	4.84	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	159	4
4302MH0003570021503380C00	3380	14473	4.52	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	127	5
4302MH0003570021503381C00	3381	14557	4.23	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	95	6
4302MH0003570021503382C00	3382	14641	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	63	7
4302MH0003570021503383C00	3383	14725	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 23_September_2024

SOL 4302 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sandy_Meadow - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4302MH0008620011503385C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4302MH0008880001503395R00	3395	MOTOR COUNT:		13023	RANGE (cm):		26.2	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4302MH0008880001503396S00	3396	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00862	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00888	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4302	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4302	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4302MH0008620031503387C00	3387	12951	31.18	-2.4	2.8	116.6	9.2	255	1
4302MH0008620031503388C00	3388	12969	29.77	-2.2	2.6	111.7	8.4	223	2
4302MH0008620031503389C00	3389	12987	28.47	-2.0	2.3	107.1	7.7	191	3
4302MH0008620031503390C00	3390	13005	27.27	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	159	4
4302MH0008620031503391C00	3391	13023	26.16	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	127	5
4302MH0008620031503392C00	3392	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	95	6
4302MH0008620031503393C00	3393	13059	24.17	-1.5	1.6	92.0	5.5	63	7
4302MH0008620031503394C00	3394	13077	23.28	-1.4	1.5	88.8	5.1	31	8

UPDATED: 02_October_2024

SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wales_Lake - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0003360011503412C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503505R00	3505	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503506S00	3506	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4306	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0003360021503413C00	3413	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4304MH0003360021503414C00	3414	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4304MH0003360021503415C00	3415	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4304MH0003360021503416C00	3416	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4304MH0003360021503417C00	3417	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4304MH0003360021503418C00	3418	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4304MH0003360021503419C00	3419	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4304MH0003360021503420C00	3420	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Wales_Lake - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0003360011503422C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503503R00	3503	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503504S00	3504	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4306	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0003360021503423C00	3423	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4304MH0003360021503424C00	3424	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4304MH0003360021503425C00	3425	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4304MH0003360021503426C00	3426	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4304MH0003360021503427C00	3427	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4304MH0003360021503428C00	3428	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4304MH0003360021503429C00	3429	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4304MH0003360021503430C00	3430	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Wales_Lake - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0008480011503432C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503501R00	3501	MOTOR COUNT:		15117	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503502S00	3502	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4306	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0008480021503433C00	3433	15021	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	255	1
4304MH0008480021503434C00	3434	15045	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
4304MH0008480021503435C00	3435	15069	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
4304MH0008480021503436C00	3436	15093	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
4304MH0008480021503437C00	3437	15117	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4304MH0008480021503438C00	3438	15141	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
4304MH0008480021503439C00	3439	15165	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4304MH0008480021503440C00	3440	15189	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

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SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Wales_Lake - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0003360011503442C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503499R00	3499	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503500S00	3500	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4306	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0003360021503443C00	3443	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4304MH0003360021503444C00	3444	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4304MH0003360021503445C00	3445	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4304MH0003360021503446C00	3446	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4304MH0003360021503447C00	3447	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4304MH0003360021503448C00	3448	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4304MH0003360021503449C00	3449	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4304MH0003360021503450C00	3450	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 02_October_2024

SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target College_Rock - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0008550011503452C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503497R00	3497	MOTOR COUNT:		13015	RANGE (cm):	26.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503498S00	3498	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4306		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0008550021503453C00	3453	12895	36.48	-3.3	3.9	135.3	12.7	255	1
4304MH0008550021503454C00	3454	12925	33.45	-2.8	3.3	124.6	10.6	223	2
4304MH0008550021503455C00	3455	12955	30.85	-2.4	2.8	115.5	9.0	191	3
4304MH0008550021503456C00	3456	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	159	4
4304MH0008550021503457C00	3457	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	127	5
4304MH0008550021503458C00	3458	13045	24.91	-1.6	1.8	94.6	5.8	95	6
4304MH0008550021503459C00	3459	13075	23.37	-1.4	1.5	89.2	5.1	63	7
4304MH0008550021503460C00	3460	13105	22.00	-1.2	1.4	84.3	4.6	31	8

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SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target College_Rock - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0002970011503462C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503495R00	3495	MOTOR COUNT:		14007	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503496S00	3496	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4306		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0002970021503463C00	3463	13767	8.67	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1
4304MH0002970021503464C00	3464	13827	8.13	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	223	2
4304MH0002970021503465C00	3465	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	191	3
4304MH0002970021503466C00	3466	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
4304MH0002970021503467C00	3467	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4304MH0002970021503468C00	3468	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4304MH0002970021503469C00	3469	14127	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
4304MH0002970021503470C00	3470	14187	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target College_Rock - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0002970011503472C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503493R00	3493	MOTOR COUNT:	14006	RANGE (cm):	6.8			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503494S00	3494	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00297	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		60	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4306			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0002970021503473C00	3473	13766	8.68	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1
4304MH0002970021503474C00	3474	13826	8.14	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	223	2
4304MH0002970021503475C00	3475	13886	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	191	3
4304MH0002970021503476C00	3476	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
4304MH0002970021503477C00	3477	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4304MH0002970021503478C00	3478	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6
4304MH0002970021503479C00	3479	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
4304MH0002970021503480C00	3480	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 02_October_2024

SOL 4304 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target College_Rock - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4304MH0004060011503482C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4306MH0001700001503491R00	3491	MOTOR COUNT:	14903	RANGE (cm):	3.3			
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4306MH0001700001503492S00	3492	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:	mhli00406	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE			
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	14-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		96	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4304	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:	4306			
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4304MH0004060021503483C00	3483	14519	4.36	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	255	1
4304MH0004060021503484C00	3484	14615	4.04	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
4304MH0004060021503485C00	3485	14711	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	191	3
4304MH0004060021503486C00	3486	14807	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	159	4
4304MH0004060021503487C00	3487	14903	3.26	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	127	5
4304MH0004060021503488C00	3488	14999	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	95	6
4304MH0004060021503489C00	3489	15095	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	63	7
4304MH0004060021503490C00	3490	15191	2.66	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4307 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Grasshopper_Flat - ~26 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4307MH0006780011503508C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4307MH0002270001503574R00	3574	MOTOR COUNT:		12989	RANGE (cm):	28.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4307MH0002270001503575S00	3575	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00678	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4307	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4307	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4307MH0006780031503510C00	3510	12893	36.70	-3.3	4.0	136.1	12.8	255	1
4307MH0006780031503511C00	3511	12917	34.21	-2.9	3.4	127.3	11.1	223	2
4307MH0006780031503512C00	3512	12941	32.02	-2.5	3.0	119.6	9.7	191	3
4307MH0006780031503513C00	3513	12965	30.07	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	159	4
4307MH0006780031503514C00	3514	12989	28.33	-2.0	2.3	106.6	7.6	127	5
4307MH0006780031503515C00	3515	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	95	6
4307MH0006780031503516C00	3516	13037	25.35	-1.6	1.8	96.2	6.1	63	7
4307MH0006780031503517C00	3517	13061	24.07	-1.5	1.6	91.6	5.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4307 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4307MH0006980011503519C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4307MH0002270001503572R00	3572	MOTOR COUNT:		14063	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4307MH0002270001503573S00	3573	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00698	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		72	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4307	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4307	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4307MH0006980031503521C00	3521	13775	8.59	-0.2	0.2	37.2	0.8	255	1
4307MH0006980031503522C00	3522	13847	7.97	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
4307MH0006980031503523C00	3523	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	191	3
4307MH0006980031503524C00	3524	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4307MH0006980031503525C00	3525	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	127	5
4307MH0006980031503526C00	3526	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	95	6
4307MH0006980031503527C00	3527	14207	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	63	7
4307MH0006980031503528C00	3528	14279	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4307 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4307MH0006980011503530C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4307MH0002270001503570R00	3570	MOTOR COUNT:		14162	RANGE (cm):		5.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4307MH0002270001503571S00	3571	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00698	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		72	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4307	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4307	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4307MH0006980031503532C00	3532	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
4307MH0006980031503533C00	3533	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4307MH0006980031503534C00	3534	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
4307MH0006980031503535C00	3535	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	159	4
4307MH0006980031503536C00	3536	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4307MH0006980031503537C00	3537	14234	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	95	6
4307MH0006980031503538C00	3538	14306	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	63	7
4307MH0006980031503539C00	3539	14378	4.89	-0.1	0.1	24.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4307 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4307MH0002990011503547C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4307MH0002270001503568R00	3568	MOTOR COUNT:		14020	RANGE (cm):		6.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4307MH0002270001503569S00	3569	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4307	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4307	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4307MH0002990021503548C00	3548	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
4307MH0002990021503549C00	3549	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
4307MH0002990021503550C00	3550	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4307MH0002990021503551C00	3551	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4307MH0002990021503552C00	3552	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4307MH0002990021503553C00	3553	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4307MH0002990021503554C00	3554	14092	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
4307MH0002990021503555C00	3555	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4307 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4307MH0002990011503557C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4307MH0002270001503566R00	3566	MOTOR COUNT:		14043	RANGE (cm):		6.6	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4307MH0002270001503567S00	3567	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00299	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00227	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4307	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4307	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4307MH0002990021503558C00	3558	13899	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
4307MH0002990021503559C00	3559	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4307MH0002990021503560C00	3560	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4307MH0002990021503561C00	3561	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4307MH0002990021503562C00	3562	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4307MH0002990021503563C00	3563	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	95	6
4307MH0002990021503564C00	3564	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
4307MH0002990021503565C00	3565	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4309 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Minster - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4309MH0001680011503579C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4309MH0001930001503612R00	3612	MOTOR COUNT:		13992	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4309MH0001930001503613S00	3613	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4309	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4309		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4309MH0001680021503580C00	3580	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4309MH0001680021503581C00	3581	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4309MH0001680021503582C00	3582	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4309MH0001680021503583C00	3583	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4309MH0001680021503584C00	3584	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
4309MH0001680021503585C00	3585	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4309MH0001680021503586C00	3586	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4309MH0001680021503587C00	3587	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4309 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Minster - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4309MH0001680011503589C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4309MH0001930001503610R00	3610	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4309MH0001930001503611S00	3611	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4309	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4309		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4309MH0001680021503590C00	3590	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
4309MH0001680021503591C00	3591	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4309MH0001680021503592C00	3592	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
4309MH0001680021503593C00	3593	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4309MH0001680021503594C00	3594	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4309MH0001680021503595C00	3595	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4309MH0001680021503596C00	3596	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4309MH0001680021503597C00	3597	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 03_October_2024

SOL 4309 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target The_Minster – after DRT – ~15 mm standoff									
		CDPID		CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4309MH0007430011503599C00					
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:		4309MH0001930001503608R00		3608		MOTOR COUNT:		14848		RANGE (cm): 3.4	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:		4309MH0001930001503609S00		3609		ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743		STACK TYPE: RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:		19-Sep-24				MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE: BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:			36		ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4309		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL: 4309		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8		
				NEAR	FAR						
4309MH0007430021503600C00	3600	14704	3.77	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	255	1		
4309MH0007430021503601C00	3601	14740	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	223	2		
4309MH0007430021503602C00	3602	14776	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	191	3		
4309MH0007430021503603C00	3603	14812	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	159	4		
4309MH0007430021503604C00	3604	14848	3.39	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	127	5		
4309MH0007430021503605C00	3605	14884	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	95	6		
4309MH0007430021503606C00	3606	14920	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	63	7		
4309MH0007430021503607C00	3607	14956	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	31	8		

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4311 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aeolian_Buttles - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4311MH0008890011503615C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4312MH0008900001503703R00	3703	MOTOR COUNT:		13030	RANGE (cm):	25.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4312MH0008900001503704S00	3704	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00889	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00890	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4311	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4312	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4311MH0008890031503617C00	3617	12982	28.82	-2.1	2.4	108.3	7.9	255	1
4311MH0008890031503618C00	3618	12994	27.99	-2.0	2.2	105.4	7.4	223	2
4311MH0008890031503619C00	3619	13006	27.21	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	191	3
4311MH0008890031503620C00	3620	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	159	4
4311MH0008890031503621C00	3621	13030	25.75	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	127	5
4311MH0008890031503622C00	3622	13042	25.08	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	95	6
4311MH0008890031503623C00	3623	13054	24.43	-1.5	1.7	92.9	5.6	63	7
4311MH0008890031503624C00	3624	13066	23.82	-1.4	1.6	90.7	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4311 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aeolian_Buttles - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4311MH0007230011503626C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4312MH0008900001503701R00	3701	MOTOR COUNT:		14161	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4312MH0008900001503702S00	3702	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00723	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00890	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4311	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4312	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4311MH0007230031503628C00	3628	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
4311MH0007230031503629C00	3629	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	223	2
4311MH0007230031503630C00	3630	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	191	3
4311MH0007230031503631C00	3631	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	159	4
4311MH0007230031503632C00	3632	14161	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4311MH0007230031503633C00	3633	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	95	6
4311MH0007230031503634C00	3634	14233	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	63	7
4311MH0007230031503635C00	3635	14269	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4311 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aeolian_Buttles - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4311MH0007230011503637C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4312MH0008900001503699R00	3699	MOTOR COUNT:		14165	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4312MH0008900001503700S00	3700	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00723	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00890	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4311	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4312	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4311MH0007230031503639C00	3639	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	255	1
4311MH0007230031503640C00	3640	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
4311MH0007230031503641C00	3641	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
4311MH0007230031503642C00	3642	14129	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	159	4
4311MH0007230031503643C00	3643	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4311MH0007230031503644C00	3644	14201	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	95	6
4311MH0007230031503645C00	3645	14237	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	63	7
4311MH0007230031503646C00	3646	14273	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4311 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cherry_Ridge - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4311MH0001680011503650C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4312MH0008900001503697R00	3697	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4312MH0008900001503698S00	3698	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00890	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4311	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4312	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4311MH0001680021503651C00	3651	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4311MH0001680021503652C00	3652	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
4311MH0001680021503653C00	3653	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4311MH0001680021503654C00	3654	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4311MH0001680021503655C00	3655	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4311MH0001680021503656C00	3656	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
4311MH0001680021503657C00	3657	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
4311MH0001680021503658C00	3658	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4311 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cherry_Ridge - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4311MH0001680011503660C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4312MH0008900001503695R00	3695	MOTOR COUNT:		14008	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4312MH0008900001503696S00	3696	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00890	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4311	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4312	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4311MH0001680021503661C00	3661	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4311MH0001680021503662C00	3662	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
4311MH0001680021503663C00	3663	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4311MH0001680021503664C00	3664	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4311MH0001680021503665C00	3665	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4311MH0001680021503666C00	3666	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4311MH0001680021503667C00	3667	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4311MH0001680021503668C00	3668	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4311 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cherry_Ridge - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4311MH0003020011503670C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4312MH0008900001503693R00	3693	MOTOR COUNT:		14697	RANGE (cm):	3.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4312MH0008900001503694S00	3694	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00302	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00890	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4311	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4312	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4311MH0003020021503671C00	3671	14577	4.16	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	255	1
4311MH0003020021503672C00	3672	14607	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	223	2
4311MH0003020021503673C00	3673	14637	3.97	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	191	3
4311MH0003020021503674C00	3674	14667	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
4311MH0003020021503675C00	3675	14697	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
4311MH0003020021503676C00	3676	14727	3.71	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
4311MH0003020021503677C00	3677	14757	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	63	7
4311MH0003020021503678C00	3678	14787	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4311 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cherry_Ridge – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4311MH0001680011503680C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4312MH0008900001503691R00	3691	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):		6.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4312MH0008900001503692S00	3692	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	21-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00890	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4311	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4312	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4311MH0001680021503681C00	3681	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
4311MH0001680021503682C00	3682	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4311MH0001680021503683C00	3683	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
4311MH0001680021503684C00	3684	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
4311MH0001680021503685C00	3685	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4311MH0001680021503686C00	3686	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4311MH0001680021503687C00	3687	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
4311MH0001680021503688C00	3688	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4314 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burst_Rock - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4314MH0003590011503726C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4314MH0001930001503759R00	3759	MOTOR COUNT:		13019	RANGE (cm):	26.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4314MH0001930001503760S00	3760	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4314	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4314		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4314MH0003590021503727C00	3727	12947	31.51	-2.5	2.9	117.8	9.4	255	1
4314MH0003590021503728C00	3728	12965	30.07	-2.3	2.6	112.7	8.6	223	2
4314MH0003590021503729C00	3729	12983	28.75	-2.1	2.4	108.1	7.8	191	3
4314MH0003590021503730C00	3730	13001	27.53	-1.9	2.2	103.8	7.2	159	4
4314MH0003590021503731C00	3731	13019	26.40	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	127	5
4314MH0003590021503732C00	3732	13037	25.35	-1.6	1.8	96.2	6.1	95	6
4314MH0003590021503733C00	3733	13055	24.38	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	63	7
4314MH0003590021503734C00	3734	13073	23.47	-1.4	1.6	89.5	5.2	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4314 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4314MH0001680011503736C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4314MH0001930001503757R00	3757	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4314MH0001930001503758S00	3758	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4314	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4314		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4314MH0001680021503737C00	3737	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4314MH0001680021503738C00	3738	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4314MH0001680021503739C00	3739	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4314MH0001680021503740C00	3740	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4314MH0001680021503741C00	3741	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4314MH0001680021503742C00	3742	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4314MH0001680021503743C00	3743	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4314MH0001680021503744C00	3744	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 09_October_2024

SOL 4314 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4314MH0001680011503746C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4314MH0001930001503755R00	3755	MOTOR COUNT:		14004	RANGE (cm):		6.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4314MH0001930001503756S00	3756	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	24-Sep-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4314		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4314
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4314MH0001680021503747C00	3747	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
4314MH0001680021503748C00	3748	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
4314MH0001680021503749C00	3749	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4314MH0001680021503750C00	3750	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4314MH0001680021503751C00	3751	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4314MH0001680021503752C00	3752	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4314MH0001680021503753C00	3753	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4314MH0001680021503754C00	3754	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 17_October_2024

SOL 4316 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aster_Lake - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4316MH0003590011503762C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4316MH0001630001503831R00	3831	MOTOR COUNT:		13029	RANGE (cm):	25.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4316MH0001630001503832S00	3832	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4316	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4316	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4316MH0003590021503763C00	3763	12957	30.69	-2.3	2.7	114.9	8.9	255	1
4316MH0003590021503764C00	3764	12975	29.32	-2.2	2.5	110.1	8.1	223	2
4316MH0003590021503765C00	3765	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	191	3
4316MH0003590021503766C00	3766	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	159	4
4316MH0003590021503767C00	3767	13029	25.81	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	127	5
4316MH0003590021503768C00	3768	13047	24.81	-1.6	1.7	94.2	5.8	95	6
4316MH0003590021503769C00	3769	13065	23.87	-1.5	1.6	90.9	5.4	63	7
4316MH0003590021503770C00	3770	13083	22.99	-1.4	1.5	87.8	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 17_October_2024

SOL 4316 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4316MH0008780011503772C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4316MH0001630001503829R00	3829	MOTOR COUNT:		13569	RANGE (cm):	10.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4316MH0001630001503830S00	3830	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00878	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4316	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4316	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4316MH0008780021503773C00	3773	13497	11.90	-0.4	0.4	48.8	1.4	255	1
4316MH0008780021503774C00	3774	13515	11.63	-0.4	0.4	47.8	1.4	223	2
4316MH0008780021503775C00	3775	13533	11.36	-0.4	0.4	46.9	1.3	191	3
4316MH0008780021503776C00	3776	13551	11.11	-0.4	0.4	46.0	1.3	159	4
4316MH0008780021503777C00	3777	13569	10.87	-0.3	0.3	45.2	1.2	127	5
4316MH0008780021503778C00	3778	13587	10.64	-0.3	0.3	44.3	1.1	95	6
4316MH0008780021503779C00	3779	13605	10.41	-0.3	0.3	43.5	1.1	63	7
4316MH0008780021503780C00	3780	13623	10.19	-0.3	0.3	42.8	1.1	31	8

UPDATED: 17_October_2024

SOL 4316 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4316MH0008780011503782C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4316MH0001630001503827R00	3827	MOTOR COUNT:		13560	RANGE (cm):	11.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4316MH0001630001503828S00	3828	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00878	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4316	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4316	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4316MH0008780021503783C00	3783	13488	12.03	-0.4	0.4	49.3	1.4	255	1
4316MH0008780021503784C00	3784	13506	11.76	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	223	2
4316MH0008780021503785C00	3785	13524	11.49	-0.4	0.4	47.4	1.3	191	3
4316MH0008780021503786C00	3786	13542	11.24	-0.4	0.4	46.5	1.3	159	4
4316MH0008780021503787C00	3787	13560	10.99	-0.4	0.3	45.6	1.2	127	5
4316MH0008780021503788C00	3788	13578	10.75	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	95	6
4316MH0008780021503789C00	3789	13596	10.52	-0.3	0.3	43.9	1.1	63	7
4316MH0008780021503790C00	3790	13614	10.30	-0.3	0.3	43.2	1.1	31	8

UPDATED: 17_October_2024

SOL 4316 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Beryl_Lake - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4316MH0008650011503792C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4316MH0001630001503825R00	3825	MOTOR COUNT:		13022	RANGE (cm):	26.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4316MH0001630001503826S00	3826	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00865	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4316	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4316	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4316MH0008650021503793C00	3793	12926	33.35	-2.8	3.3	124.3	10.6	255	1
4316MH0008650021503794C00	3794	12950	31.26	-2.4	2.8	116.9	9.3	223	2
4316MH0008650021503795C00	3795	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	191	3
4316MH0008650021503796C00	3796	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	159	4
4316MH0008650021503797C00	3797	13022	26.22	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	127	5
4316MH0008650021503798C00	3798	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	95	6
4316MH0008650021503799C00	3799	13070	23.62	-1.4	1.6	90.0	5.3	63	7
4316MH0008650021503800C00	3800	13094	22.49	-1.3	1.4	86.1	4.8	31	8

UPDATED: 17_October_2024

SOL 4316 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Beryl_Lake - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4316MH0001520011503802C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4316MH0001630001503823R00	3823	MOTOR COUNT:		14063	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4316MH0001630001503824S00	3824	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4316	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4316		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4316MH0001520021503803C00	3803	13871	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
4316MH0001520021503804C00	3804	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
4316MH0001520021503805C00	3805	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4316MH0001520021503806C00	3806	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4316MH0001520021503807C00	3807	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	127	5
4316MH0001520021503808C00	3808	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	95	6
4316MH0001520021503809C00	3809	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7
4316MH0001520021503810C00	3810	14207	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 17_October_2024

SOL 4316 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Beryl_Lake - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4316MH0001520011503812C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4316MH0001630001503821R00	3821	MOTOR COUNT:		14082	RANGE (cm):	6.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4316MH0001630001503822S00	3822	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4316	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4316		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4316MH0001520021503813C00	3813	13890	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
4316MH0001520021503814C00	3814	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4316MH0001520021503815C00	3815	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4316MH0001520021503816C00	3816	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
4316MH0001520021503817C00	3817	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	127	5
4316MH0001520021503818C00	3818	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	95	6
4316MH0001520021503819C00	3819	14178	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	63	7
4316MH0001520021503820C00	3820	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Angora_Mountain - ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0008760011503834C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503960R00	3960	MOTOR COUNT:		13041	RANGE (cm):	25.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503961S00	3961	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0008760021503835C00	3835	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	255	1
4318MH0008760021503836C00	3836	13005	27.27	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	223	2
4318MH0008760021503837C00	3837	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	191	3
4318MH0008760021503838C00	3838	13029	25.81	-1.7	1.9	97.8	6.3	159	4
4318MH0008760021503839C00	3839	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	127	5
4318MH0008760021503840C00	3840	13053	24.49	-1.5	1.7	93.1	5.7	95	6
4318MH0008760021503841C00	3841	13065	23.87	-1.5	1.6	90.9	5.4	63	7
4318MH0008760021503842C00	3842	13077	23.28	-1.4	1.5	88.8	5.1	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0002240011503844C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503958R00	3958	MOTOR COUNT:		14368	RANGE (cm):	4.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503959S00	3959	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0002240021503845C00	3845	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	255	1
4318MH0002240021503846C00	3846	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	223	2
4318MH0002240021503847C00	3847	14284	5.29	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	191	3
4318MH0002240021503848C00	3848	14326	5.10	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	159	4
4318MH0002240021503849C00	3849	14368	4.93	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	127	5
4318MH0002240021503850C00	3850	14410	4.76	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	95	6
4318MH0002240021503851C00	3851	14452	4.60	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	63	7
4318MH0002240021503852C00	3852	14494	4.44	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - ~3 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0002240011503854C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503956R00	3956	MOTOR COUNT:		14347	RANGE (cm):	5.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503957S00	3957	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	28-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0002240021503855C00	3855	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	255	1
4318MH0002240021503856C00	3856	14221	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	223	2
4318MH0002240021503857C00	3857	14263	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	191	3
4318MH0002240021503858C00	3858	14305	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	159	4
4318MH0002240021503859C00	3859	14347	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	127	5
4318MH0002240021503860C00	3860	14389	4.84	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	95	6
4318MH0002240021503861C00	3861	14431	4.68	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	63	7
4318MH0002240021503862C00	3862	14473	4.52	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0007400011503867C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503954R00	3954	MOTOR COUNT:		14000	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503955S00	3955	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00740	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0007400031503869C00	3869	13784	8.51	-0.2	0.2	36.9	0.8	255	1
4318MH0007400031503870C00	3870	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
4318MH0007400031503871C00	3871	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	191	3
4318MH0007400031503872C00	3872	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
4318MH0007400031503873C00	3873	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4318MH0007400031503874C00	3874	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4318MH0007400031503875C00	3875	14108	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	63	7
4318MH0007400031503876C00	3876	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0007400011503878C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503952R00	3952	MOTOR COUNT:		14009	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503953S00	3953	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00740	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		54	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0007400031503880C00	3880	13793	8.43	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	255	1
4318MH0007400031503881C00	3881	13847	7.97	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
4318MH0007400031503882C00	3882	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
4318MH0007400031503883C00	3883	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
4318MH0007400031503884C00	3884	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4318MH0007400031503885C00	3885	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4318MH0007400031503886C00	3886	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
4318MH0007400031503887C00	3887	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Moonlight_Lake - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0007100011503889C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503950R00	3950	MOTOR COUNT:		14931	RANGE (cm):	3.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503951S00	3951	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00710	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		78	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0007100031503891C00	3891	14619	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	255	1
4318MH0007100031503892C00	3892	14697	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	223	2
4318MH0007100031503893C00	3893	14775	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	191	3
4318MH0007100031503894C00	3894	14853	3.38	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	159	4
4318MH0007100031503895C00	3895	14931	3.19	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	127	5
4318MH0007100031503896C00	3896	15009	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	95	6
4318MH0007100031503897C00	3897	15087	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	63	7
4318MH0007100031503898C00	3898	15165	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0006990011503903C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503948R00	3948	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503949S00	3949	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00699	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0006990031503905C00	3905	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
4318MH0006990031503906C00	3906	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
4318MH0006990031503907C00	3907	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4318MH0006990031503908C00	3908	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4318MH0006990031503909C00	3909	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4318MH0006990031503910C00	3910	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4318MH0006990031503911C00	3911	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4318MH0006990031503912C00	3912	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0006990011503914C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503946R00	3946	MOTOR COUNT:		14025	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503947S00	3947	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00699	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0006990031503916C00	3916	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4318MH0006990031503917C00	3917	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
4318MH0006990031503918C00	3918	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
4318MH0006990031503919C00	3919	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4318MH0006990031503920C00	3920	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4318MH0006990031503921C00	3921	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
4318MH0006990031503922C00	3922	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
4318MH0006990031503923C00	3923	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4318 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Cloud_Canyon - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4318MH0007940011503925C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4319MH0005360001503944R00	3944	MOTOR COUNT:		15177	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4319MH0005360001503945S00	3945	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00794	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	29-Sep-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4318	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4319	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4318MH0007940031503927C00	3927	14985	3.07	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
4318MH0007940031503928C00	3928	15033	2.97	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	223	2
4318MH0007940031503929C00	3929	15081	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4318MH0007940031503930C00	3930	15129	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	159	4
4318MH0007940031503931C00	3931	15177	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	127	5
4318MH0007940031503932C00	3932	15225	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6
4318MH0007940031503933C00	3933	15273	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7
4318MH0007940031503934C00	3934	15321	2.44	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 17_June_2025

SOL 4321 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4321MH0003360011503965C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4321MH0001930001503998R00	3998	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4321MH0001930001503999S00	3999	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4321	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4321		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4321MH0003360021503966C00	3966	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4321MH0003360021503967C00	3967	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4321MH0003360021503968C00	3968	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4321MH0003360021503969C00	3969	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4321MH0003360021503970C00	3970	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4321MH0003360021503971C00	3971	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4321MH0003360021503972C00	3972	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4321MH0003360021503973C00	3973	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 17_June_2025

SOL 4321 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4321MH0003360011503975C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4321MH0001930001503996R00	3996	MOTOR COUNT:		13998	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4321MH0001930001503997S00	3997	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4321	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4321		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4321MH0003360021503976C00	3976	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4321MH0003360021503977C00	3977	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4321MH0003360021503978C00	3978	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4321MH0003360021503979C00	3979	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4321MH0003360021503980C00	3980	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4321MH0003360021503981C00	3981	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4321MH0003360021503982C00	3982	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4321MH0003360021503983C00	3983	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 17_June_2025

SOL 4321 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Flat_Note_Lake - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4321MH0008480011503985C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4321MH0001930001503994R00	3994	MOTOR COUNT:		15118	RANGE (cm):		2.8	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4321MH0001930001503995S00	3995	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	1-Oct-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00193		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4321		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4321
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4321MH0008480021503986C00	3986	15022	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	255	1
4321MH0008480021503987C00	3987	15046	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
4321MH0008480021503988C00	3988	15070	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
4321MH0008480021503989C00	3989	15094	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
4321MH0008480021503990C00	3990	15118	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4321MH0008480021503991C00	3991	15142	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
4321MH0008480021503992C00	3992	15166	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4321MH0008480021503993C00	3993	15190	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4323 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4323MH0001680011504003C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4323MH0002650001504024R00	4024	MOTOR COUNT:		14011	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4323MH0002650001504025S00	4025	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4323	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4323		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4323MH0001680021504004C00	4004	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4323MH0001680021504005C00	4005	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4323MH0001680021504006C00	4006	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4323MH0001680021504007C00	4007	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4323MH0001680021504008C00	4008	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4323MH0001680021504009C00	4009	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4323MH0001680021504010C00	4010	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4323MH0001680021504011C00	4011	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4323 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4323MH0001680011504013C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4323MH0002650001504022R00	4022	MOTOR COUNT:		14011	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4323MH0002650001504023S00	4023	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	3-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4323	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4323		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4323MH0001680021504014C00	4014	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
4323MH0001680021504015C00	4015	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4323MH0001680021504016C00	4016	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4323MH0001680021504017C00	4017	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4323MH0001680021504018C00	4018	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
4323MH0001680021504019C00	4019	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4323MH0001680021504020C00	4020	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4323MH0001680021504021C00	4021	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4325 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Kidney_Lake - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4325MH0006990011504030C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4326MH0008910001504094R00	4094	MOTOR COUNT:		14166	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4326MH0008910001504095S00	4095	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00699	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00891	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4325	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4326	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4325MH0006990031504032C00	4032	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	255	1
4325MH0006990031504033C00	4033	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	223	2
4325MH0006990031504034C00	4034	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
4325MH0006990031504035C00	4035	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
4325MH0006990031504036C00	4036	14166	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4325MH0006990031504037C00	4037	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	95	6
4325MH0006990031504038C00	4038	14226	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	63	7
4325MH0006990031504039C00	4039	14256	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4325 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Pumice_Flat - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4325MH0008340011504044C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4326MH0008910001504092R00	4092	MOTOR COUNT:		14253	RANGE (cm):	5.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4326MH0008910001504093S00	4093	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00834	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00891	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4325	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4326	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4325MH0008340031504046C00	4046	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	255	1
4325MH0008340031504047C00	4047	14199	5.70	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	223	2
4325MH0008340031504048C00	4048	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	191	3
4325MH0008340031504049C00	4049	14235	5.52	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	159	4
4325MH0008340031504050C00	4050	14253	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	127	5
4325MH0008340031504051C00	4051	14271	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	95	6
4325MH0008340031504052C00	4052	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	63	7
4325MH0008340031504053C00	4053	14307	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4325 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ribbon_Fall - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4325MH0003360011504057C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4326MH0008910001504090R00	4090	MOTOR COUNT:		14027	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4326MH0008910001504091S00	4091	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00891	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4325	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4326	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4325MH0003360021504058C00	4058	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
4325MH0003360021504059C00	4059	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4325MH0003360021504060C00	4060	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4325MH0003360021504061C00	4061	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4325MH0003360021504062C00	4062	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
4325MH0003360021504063C00	4063	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4325MH0003360021504064C00	4064	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
4325MH0003360021504065C00	4065	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4325 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ribbon_Fall - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4325MH0003360011504067C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4326MH0008910001504088R00	4088	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4326MH0008910001504089S00	4089	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00891	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4325	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4326	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4325MH0003360021504068C00	4068	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4325MH0003360021504069C00	4069	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4325MH0003360021504070C00	4070	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4325MH0003360021504071C00	4071	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4325MH0003360021504072C00	4072	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4325MH0003360021504073C00	4073	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4325MH0003360021504074C00	4074	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4325MH0003360021504075C00	4075	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4325 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ribbon_Fall - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4325MH0008480011504077C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4326MH0008910001504086R00	4086	MOTOR COUNT:		15183	RANGE (cm):		2.7	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4326MH0008910001504087S00	4087	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE	
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	6-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00891	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4325	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4326	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4325MH0008480021504078C00	4078	15087	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
4325MH0008480021504079C00	4079	15111	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2
4325MH0008480021504080C00	4080	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	191	3
4325MH0008480021504081C00	4081	15159	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
4325MH0008480021504082C00	4082	15183	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
4325MH0008480021504083C00	4083	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
4325MH0008480021504084C00	4084	15231	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
4325MH0008480021504085C00	4085	15255	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4327 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Pincushion_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4327MH0003360011504099C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4328MH0001530001504150R00	4150	MOTOR COUNT:		13994	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4328MH0001530001504151S00	4151	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4327	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4328	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4327MH0003360021504100C00	4100	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4327MH0003360021504101C00	4101	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4327MH0003360021504102C00	4102	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4327MH0003360021504103C00	4103	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4327MH0003360021504104C00	4104	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4327MH0003360021504105C00	4105	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4327MH0003360021504106C00	4106	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4327MH0003360021504107C00	4107	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4327 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Pincushion_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4327MH0003360011504109C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4328MH0001530001504148R00	4148	MOTOR COUNT:		13995	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4328MH0001530001504149S00	4149	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4327	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4328	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4327MH0003360021504110C00	4110	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
4327MH0003360021504111C00	4111	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
4327MH0003360021504112C00	4112	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
4327MH0003360021504113C00	4113	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
4327MH0003360021504114C00	4114	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
4327MH0003360021504115C00	4115	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
4327MH0003360021504116C00	4116	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4327MH0003360021504117C00	4117	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4327 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Pincushion_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4327MH0008480011504125C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4328MH0001530001504146R00	4146	MOTOR COUNT:		15052	RANGE (cm):	2.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4328MH0001530001504147S00	4147	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4327	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4328		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4327MH0008480021504126C00	4126	14956	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	255	1
4327MH0008480021504127C00	4127	14980	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	223	2
4327MH0008480021504128C00	4128	15004	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
4327MH0008480021504129C00	4129	15028	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
4327MH0008480021504130C00	4130	15052	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	127	5
4327MH0008480021504131C00	4131	15076	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	95	6
4327MH0008480021504132C00	4132	15100	2.83	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	63	7
4327MH0008480021504133C00	4133	15124	2.79	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4327 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Pincushion_Peak - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4327MH0003360011504135C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4328MH0001530001504144R00	4144	MOTOR COUNT:		13979	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4328MH0001530001504145S00	4145	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	8-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC			
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4327	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4328		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4327MH0003360021504136C00	4136	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
4327MH0003360021504137C00	4137	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4327MH0003360021504138C00	4138	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
4327MH0003360021504139C00	4139	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4327MH0003360021504140C00	4140	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4327MH0003360021504141C00	4141	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
4327MH0003360021504142C00	4142	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
4327MH0003360021504143C00	4143	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4331 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Midnight_Lake – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – stereo-1 – relief model position 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4331MH0003360011504155C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4332MH0001530001504206R00	4206	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4332MH0001530001504207S00	4207	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4331	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4332	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4331MH0003360021504156C00	4156	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4331MH0003360021504157C00	4157	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4331MH0003360021504158C00	4158	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4331MH0003360021504159C00	4159	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4331MH0003360021504160C00	4160	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4331MH0003360021504161C00	4161	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4331MH0003360021504162C00	4162	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4331MH0003360021504163C00	4163	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4331 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Midnight_Lake – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – stereo-2 – relief model position 2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4331MH0003360011504165C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4332MH0001530001504204R00	4204	MOTOR COUNT:		14029	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4332MH0001530001504205S00	4205	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4331	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4332	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4331MH0003360021504166C00	4166	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
4331MH0003360021504167C00	4167	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4331MH0003360021504168C00	4168	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4331MH0003360021504169C00	4169	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	159	4
4331MH0003360021504170C00	4170	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
4331MH0003360021504171C00	4171	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
4331MH0003360021504172C00	4172	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
4331MH0003360021504173C00	4173	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4331 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Midnight_Lake – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4331MH0008480011504181C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4332MH0001530001504202R00	4202	MOTOR COUNT:		15181	RANGE (cm):	2.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4332MH0001530001504203S00	4203	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4331	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4332	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4331MH0008480021504182C00	4182	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	255	1
4331MH0008480021504183C00	4183	15109	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	223	2
4331MH0008480021504184C00	4184	15133	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	191	3
4331MH0008480021504185C00	4185	15157	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4
4331MH0008480021504186C00	4186	15181	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
4331MH0008480021504187C00	4187	15205	2.64	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
4331MH0008480021504188C00	4188	15229	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	63	7
4331MH0008480021504189C00	4189	15253	2.55	-0.1	0.1	15.9	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4331 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Midnight_Lake – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4331MH0003360011504191C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4332MH0001530001504200R00	4200	MOTOR COUNT:		14224	RANGE (cm):	5.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4332MH0001530001504201S00	4201	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	12-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4331	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4332	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4331MH0003360021504192C00	4192	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	255	1
4331MH0003360021504193C00	4193	14188	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	223	2
4331MH0003360021504194C00	4194	14200	5.69	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	191	3
4331MH0003360021504195C00	4195	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	159	4
4331MH0003360021504196C00	4196	14224	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
4331MH0003360021504197C00	4197	14236	5.52	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	95	6
4331MH0003360021504198C00	4198	14248	5.46	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	63	7
4331MH0003360021504199C00	4199	14260	5.40	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4334 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4334MH0003360011504211C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4334MH0002650001504232R00	4232	MOTOR COUNT:		14076	RANGE (cm):	6.4		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4334MH0002650001504233S00	4233	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4334	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4334		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4334MH0003360021504212C00	4212	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	255	1
4334MH0003360021504213C00	4213	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	223	2
4334MH0003360021504214C00	4214	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	191	3
4334MH0003360021504215C00	4215	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	159	4
4334MH0003360021504216C00	4216	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	127	5
4334MH0003360021504217C00	4217	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
4334MH0003360021504218C00	4218	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
4334MH0003360021504219C00	4219	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 21_October_2024

SOL 4334 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4334MH0003360011504221C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4334MH0002650001504230R00	4230	MOTOR COUNT:		14094	RANGE (cm):	6.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4334MH0002650001504231S00	4231	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	15-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4334	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4334		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4334MH0003360021504222C00	4222	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	255	1
4334MH0003360021504223C00	4223	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	223	2
4334MH0003360021504224C00	4224	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	191	3
4334MH0003360021504225C00	4225	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	159	4
4334MH0003360021504226C00	4226	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	127	5
4334MH0003360021504227C00	4227	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	95	6
4334MH0003360021504228C00	4228	14118	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	63	7
4334MH0003360021504229C00	4229	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4336 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4336MH0001820011504237C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4336MH0002650001504258R00	4258	MOTOR COUNT:		14231	RANGE (cm):	5.5		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4336MH0002650001504259S00	4259	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4336	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4336	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4336MH0001820021504238C00	4238	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	255	1
4336MH0001820021504239C00	4239	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	223	2
4336MH0001820021504240C00	4240	14183	5.78	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	191	3
4336MH0001820021504241C00	4241	14207	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	159	4
4336MH0001820021504242C00	4242	14231	5.54	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	127	5
4336MH0001820021504243C00	4243	14255	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6
4336MH0001820021504244C00	4244	14279	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
4336MH0001820021504245C00	4245	14303	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 22_October_2024

SOL 4336 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4336MH0001820011504247C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4336MH0002650001504256R00	4256	MOTOR COUNT:		14208	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4336MH0002650001504257S00	4257	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00182	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	17-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00265	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4336	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4336	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4336MH0001820021504248C00	4248	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	255	1
4336MH0001820021504249C00	4249	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	223	2
4336MH0001820021504250C00	4250	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	191	3
4336MH0001820021504251C00	4251	14184	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	159	4
4336MH0001820021504252C00	4252	14208	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	127	5
4336MH0001820021504253C00	4253	14232	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	95	6
4336MH0001820021504254C00	4254	14256	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
4336MH0001820021504255C00	4255	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0001680011504263C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504358R00	4358	MOTOR COUNT:		14124	RANGE (cm):	6.1		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504359S00	4359	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0001680021504264C00	4264	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	255	1
4338MH0001680021504265C00	4265	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
4338MH0001680021504266C00	4266	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	191	3
4338MH0001680021504267C00	4267	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
4338MH0001680021504268C00	4268	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	127	5
4338MH0001680021504269C00	4269	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	95	6
4338MH0001680021504270C00	4270	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	63	7
4338MH0001680021504271C00	4271	14178	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0001680011504273C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504356R00	4356	MOTOR COUNT:		14135	RANGE (cm):	6.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504357S00	4357	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0001680021504274C00	4274	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
4338MH0001680021504275C00	4275	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	223	2
4338MH0001680021504276C00	4276	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	191	3
4338MH0001680021504277C00	4277	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	159	4
4338MH0001680021504278C00	4278	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	127	5
4338MH0001680021504279C00	4279	14153	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	95	6
4338MH0001680021504280C00	4280	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	63	7
4338MH0001680021504281C00	4281	14189	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Noble_Canyon - ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0003590011504283C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504354R00	4354	MOTOR COUNT:		13031	RANGE (cm):	25.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504355S00	4355	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0003590021504284C00	4284	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	255	1
4338MH0003590021504285C00	4285	12977	29.18	-2.1	2.4	109.6	8.0	223	2
4338MH0003590021504286C00	4286	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	191	3
4338MH0003590021504287C00	4287	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	159	4
4338MH0003590021504288C00	4288	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
4338MH0003590021504289C00	4289	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	95	6
4338MH0003590021504290C00	4290	13067	23.77	-1.4	1.6	90.6	5.3	63	7
4338MH0003590021504291C00	4291	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0006730011504293C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504352R00	4352	MOTOR COUNT:		14081	RANGE (cm):	6.3		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504353S00	4353	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00673	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		84	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0006730021504294C00	4294	13745	8.88	-0.3	0.2	38.1	0.8	255	1
4338MH0006730021504295C00	4295	13829	8.12	-0.2	0.2	35.5	0.7	223	2
4338MH0006730021504296C00	4296	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
4338MH0006730021504297C00	4297	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
4338MH0006730021504298C00	4298	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	127	5
4338MH0006730021504299C00	4299	14165	5.87	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	95	6
4338MH0006730021504300C00	4300	14249	5.45	-0.1	0.1	26.1	0.4	63	7
4338MH0006730021504301C00	4301	14333	5.07	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0006730011504303C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504350R00	4350	MOTOR COUNT:		14194	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504351S00	4351	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00673	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		84	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0006730021504304C00	4304	13858	7.88	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
4338MH0006730021504305C00	4305	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
4338MH0006730021504306C00	4306	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	191	3
4338MH0006730021504307C00	4307	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
4338MH0006730021504308C00	4308	14194	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	127	5
4338MH0006730021504309C00	4309	14278	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	95	6
4338MH0006730021504310C00	4310	14362	4.95	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	63	7
4338MH0006730021504311C00	4311	14446	4.62	-0.1	0.1	23.2	0.3	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chapel_Lake - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0003360011504315C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504348R00	4348	MOTOR COUNT:		14002	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504349S00	4349	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0003360021504316C00	4316	13954	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4338MH0003360021504317C00	4317	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4338MH0003360021504318C00	4318	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4338MH0003360021504319C00	4319	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4338MH0003360021504320C00	4320	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
4338MH0003360021504321C00	4321	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4338MH0003360021504322C00	4322	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4338MH0003360021504323C00	4323	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Chapel_Lake - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0003360011504325C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504346R00	4346	MOTOR COUNT:		14017	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504347S00	4347	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0003360021504326C00	4326	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4338MH0003360021504327C00	4327	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4338MH0003360021504328C00	4328	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4338MH0003360021504329C00	4329	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4338MH0003360021504330C00	4330	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4338MH0003360021504331C00	4331	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4338MH0003360021504332C00	4332	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4338MH0003360021504333C00	4333	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 28_October_2024

SOL 4338 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Chapel_Lake - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4338MH0008480011504335C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4339MH0001700001504344R00	4344	MOTOR COUNT:		15135	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4339MH0001700001504345S00	4345	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	19-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00170	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4338	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4339	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4338MH0008480021504336C00	4336	15039	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	255	1
4338MH0008480021504337C00	4337	15063	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	223	2
4338MH0008480021504338C00	4338	15087	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
4338MH0008480021504339C00	4339	15111	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	159	4
4338MH0008480021504340C00	4340	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
4338MH0008480021504341C00	4341	15159	2.72	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	95	6
4338MH0008480021504342C00	4342	15183	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
4338MH0008480021504343C00	4343	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 25_October_2024

SOL 4341 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chuck_Pass – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4341MH0003360011504363C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4342MH0001530001504408R00	4408	MOTOR COUNT:		14015	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4342MH0001530001504409S00	4409	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4341	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4342		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4341MH0003360021504364C00	4364	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4341MH0003360021504365C00	4365	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4341MH0003360021504366C00	4366	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4341MH0003360021504367C00	4367	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4341MH0003360021504368C00	4368	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4341MH0003360021504369C00	4369	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4341MH0003360021504370C00	4370	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4341MH0003360021504371C00	4371	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 25_October_2024

SOL 4341 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chuck_Pass – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4341MH0003360011504373C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4342MH0001530001504406R00	4406	MOTOR COUNT:		14019	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4342MH0001530001504407S00	4407	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00153	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4341	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4342		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4341MH0003360021504374C00	4374	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4341MH0003360021504375C00	4375	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4341MH0003360021504376C00	4376	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4341MH0003360021504377C00	4377	14007	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4341MH0003360021504378C00	4378	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4341MH0003360021504379C00	4379	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4341MH0003360021504380C00	4380	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4341MH0003360021504381C00	4381	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 25_October_2024

SOL 4341 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chuck_Pass – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – ~15 mm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4341MH0008480011504383C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4342MH0001530001504404R00			4404	MOTOR COUNT:		14911	RANGE (cm):	3.2
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4342MH0001530001504405S00			4405	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4341		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4342
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4341MH0008480021504384C00	4384	14815	3.47	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	255	1
4341MH0008480021504385C00	4385	14839	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	223	2
4341MH0008480021504386C00	4386	14863	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	191	3
4341MH0008480021504387C00	4387	14887	3.29	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	159	4
4341MH0008480021504388C00	4388	14911	3.24	-0.1	0.1	18.3	0.2	127	5
4341MH0008480021504389C00	4389	14935	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	95	6
4341MH0008480021504390C00	4390	14959	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	63	7
4341MH0008480021504391C00	4391	14983	3.08	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 25_October_2024

SOL 4341 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Chuck_Pass – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4341MH0003360011504393C00		
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4342MH0001530001504402R00			4402	MOTOR COUNT:		14016	RANGE (cm):	6.7
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4342MH0001530001504403S00			4403	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	22-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00153	MERGE TYPE: BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12		ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4341		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4342
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4341MH0003360021504394C00	4394	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4341MH0003360021504395C00	4395	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	223	2
4341MH0003360021504396C00	4396	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
4341MH0003360021504397C00	4397	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
4341MH0003360021504398C00	4398	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
4341MH0003360021504399C00	4399	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
4341MH0003360021504400C00	4400	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
4341MH0003360021504401C00	4401	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Reef_Lake – mosaic position 1 of 3 – ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0008550011504411C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4346MH0001710001504494R00	4494	MOTOR COUNT:		13023	RANGE (cm):	26.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4346MH0001710001504495S00	4495	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4346	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0008550021504412C00	4412	12903	35.62	-3.1	3.7	132.3	12.1	255	1
4345MH0008550021504413C00	4413	12933	32.72	-2.7	3.1	122.1	10.2	223	2
4345MH0008550021504414C00	4414	12963	30.22	-2.3	2.6	113.3	8.6	191	3
4345MH0008550021504415C00	4415	12993	28.06	-2.0	2.3	105.7	7.4	159	4
4345MH0008550021504416C00	4416	13023	26.16	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	127	5
4345MH0008550021504417C00	4417	13053	24.49	-1.5	1.7	93.1	5.7	95	6
4345MH0008550021504418C00	4418	13083	22.99	-1.4	1.5	87.8	5.0	63	7
4345MH0008550021504419C00	4419	13113	21.66	-1.2	1.3	83.1	4.4	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Reef_Lake – mosaic position 2 of 3 – ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0008550011504421C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4346MH0001710001504492R00	4492	MOTOR COUNT:		13028	RANGE (cm):	25.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4346MH0001710001504493S00	4493	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24	MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:		BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4346	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0008550021504422C00	4422	12908	35.11	-3.0	3.6	130.5	11.7	255	1
4345MH0008550021504423C00	4423	12938	32.28	-2.6	3.0	120.5	9.9	223	2
4345MH0008550021504424C00	4424	12968	29.84	-2.2	2.6	111.9	8.4	191	3
4345MH0008550021504425C00	4425	12998	27.73	-1.9	2.2	104.5	7.3	159	4
4345MH0008550021504426C00	4426	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	127	5
4345MH0008550021504427C00	4427	13058	24.22	-1.5	1.7	92.2	5.5	95	6
4345MH0008550021504428C00	4428	13088	22.76	-1.3	1.5	87.0	4.9	63	7
4345MH0008550021504429C00	4429	13118	21.45	-1.2	1.3	82.4	4.3	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Reef_Lake – mosaic position 3 of 3 – ~23 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0008550011504431C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4346MH0001710001504490R00	4490	MOTOR COUNT:		13039	RANGE (cm):	25.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4346MH0001710001504491S00	4491	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00855	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4346	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0008550021504432C00	4432	12919	34.02	-2.9	3.4	126.6	11.0	255	1
4345MH0008550021504433C00	4433	12949	31.34	-2.4	2.9	117.2	9.3	223	2
4345MH0008550021504434C00	4434	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	191	3
4345MH0008550021504435C00	4435	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	159	4
4345MH0008550021504436C00	4436	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	127	5
4345MH0008550021504437C00	4437	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	95	6
4345MH0008550021504438C00	4438	13099	22.26	-1.3	1.4	85.3	4.7	63	7
4345MH0008550021504439C00	4439	13129	21.00	-1.1	1.2	80.8	4.2	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Mount_Brewer – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0001680011504443C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4346MH0001710001504488R00	4488	MOTOR COUNT:		13979	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4346MH0001710001504489S00	4489	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC	
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4346	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0001680021504444C00	4444	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4345MH0001680021504445C00	4445	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
4345MH0001680021504446C00	4446	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4345MH0001680021504447C00	4447	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
4345MH0001680021504448C00	4448	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4345MH0001680021504449C00	4449	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
4345MH0001680021504450C00	4450	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
4345MH0001680021504451C00	4451	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		first merge of: target Mount_Brewer – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0001680011504453C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4346MH0001710001504486R00	4486	MOTOR COUNT:		13984	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4346MH0001710001504487S00	4487	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4346		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0001680021504454C00	4454	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
4345MH0001680021504455C00	4455	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
4345MH0001680021504456C00	4456	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4345MH0001680021504457C00	4457	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4345MH0001680021504458C00	4458	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4345MH0001680021504459C00	4459	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4345MH0001680021504460C00	4460	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4345MH0001680021504461C00	4461	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		second merge of: target Mount_Brewer – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 4348							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0001680011504453C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4348MH0001930001504500R00	4500	MOTOR COUNT:		13984	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4348MH0001930001504501S00	4501	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4348		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0001680021504454C00	4454	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
4345MH0001680021504455C00	4455	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
4345MH0001680021504456C00	4456	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
4345MH0001680021504457C00	4457	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
4345MH0001680021504458C00	4458	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
4345MH0001680021504459C00	4459	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
4345MH0001680021504460C00	4460	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4345MH0001680021504461C00	4461	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Mount_Brewer – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0007430011504463C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4346MH0001710001504484R00	4484	MOTOR COUNT:		15006	RANGE (cm):	3.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4346MH0001710001504485S00	4485	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4346		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0007430021504464C00	4464	14862	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	255	1
4345MH0007430021504465C00	4465	14898	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	223	2
4345MH0007430021504466C00	4466	14934	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	191	3
4345MH0007430021504467C00	4467	14970	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	159	4
4345MH0007430021504468C00	4468	15006	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	127	5
4345MH0007430021504469C00	4469	15042	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	95	6
4345MH0007430021504470C00	4470	15078	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	63	7
4345MH0007430021504471C00	4471	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Mount_Brewer – after DRT – APXS spot 2 – ~1 cm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 4348								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0007430011504463C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4348MH0001930001504498R00	4498	MOTOR COUNT:		15006	RANGE (cm):	3.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4348MH0001930001504499S00	4499	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4348		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0007430021504464C00	4464	14862	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	255	1
4345MH0007430021504465C00	4465	14898	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	223	2
4345MH0007430021504466C00	4466	14934	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	191	3
4345MH0007430021504467C00	4467	14970	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	159	4
4345MH0007430021504468C00	4468	15006	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	127	5
4345MH0007430021504469C00	4469	15042	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	95	6
4345MH0007430021504470C00	4470	15078	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	63	7
4345MH0007430021504471C00	4471	15114	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	first merge of: target Mount_Brewer – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0001680011504473C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4346MH0001710001504482R00	4482	MOTOR COUNT:		13977	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4346MH0001710001504483S00	4483	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00171	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4346		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0001680021504474C00	4474	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4345MH0001680021504475C00	4475	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
4345MH0001680021504476C00	4476	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4345MH0001680021504477C00	4477	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4345MH0001680021504478C00	4478	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4345MH0001680021504479C00	4479	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
4345MH0001680021504480C00	4480	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4345MH0001680021504481C00	4481	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 14_January_2025

SOL 4345 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	second merge of: target Mount_Brewer – after DRT – APXS spot 1 – ~5 cm standoff – merge was performed after a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented a new focus stack acquisition on Sol 4348								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4345MH0001680011504473C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4348MH0001930001504496R00	4496	MOTOR COUNT:		13977	RANGE (cm):	7.0		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4348MH0001930001504497S00	4497	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	26-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00193	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4345	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4348		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4345MH0001680021504474C00	4474	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
4345MH0001680021504475C00	4475	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
4345MH0001680021504476C00	4476	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
4345MH0001680021504477C00	4477	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
4345MH0001680021504478C00	4478	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
4345MH0001680021504479C00	4479	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	95	6
4345MH0001680021504480C00	4480	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	63	7
4345MH0001680021504481C00	4481	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4350 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4350MH0001680011504505C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4350MH0001630001504576R00	4576	MOTOR COUNT:		14042	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4350MH0001630001504577S00	4577	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4350	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4350		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4350MH0001680021504506C00	4506	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4350MH0001680021504507C00	4507	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
4350MH0001680021504508C00	4508	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
4350MH0001680021504509C00	4509	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4350MH0001680021504510C00	4510	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	127	5
4350MH0001680021504511C00	4511	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
4350MH0001680021504512C00	4512	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
4350MH0001680021504513C00	4513	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4350 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4350MH0001680011504515C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4350MH0001630001504574R00	4574	MOTOR COUNT:		14046	RANGE (cm):	6.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4350MH0001630001504575S00	4575	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00168	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4350	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4350		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4350MH0001680021504516C00	4516	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
4350MH0001680021504517C00	4517	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
4350MH0001680021504518C00	4518	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	191	3
4350MH0001680021504519C00	4519	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
4350MH0001680021504520C00	4520	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	127	5
4350MH0001680021504521C00	4521	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
4350MH0001680021504522C00	4522	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
4350MH0001680021504523C00	4523	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4350 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Ladder_Lake - ~5 mm standoff								
			CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4350MH0007430011504525C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4350MH0001630001504572R00	4572	MOTOR COUNT:		15243	RANGE (cm):	2.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4350MH0001630001504573S00	4573	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00743	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		36	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4350	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4350		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4350MH0007430021504526C00	4526	15099	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	255	1
4350MH0007430021504527C00	4527	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	223	2
4350MH0007430021504528C00	4528	15171	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3
4350MH0007430021504529C00	4529	15207	2.63	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	159	4
4350MH0007430021504530C00	4530	15243	2.57	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5
4350MH0007430021504531C00	4531	15279	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	95	6
4350MH0007430021504532C00	4532	15315	2.45	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	63	7
4350MH0007430021504533C00	4533	15351	2.39	0.0	0.1	15.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4350 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4350MH0003360011504537C00			
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4350MH0001630001504570R00	4570	MOTOR COUNT:		14010	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4350MH0001630001504571S00	4571	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4350	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4350		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4350MH0003360021504538C00	4538	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	255	1
4350MH0003360021504539C00	4539	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
4350MH0003360021504540C00	4540	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	191	3
4350MH0003360021504541C00	4541	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
4350MH0003360021504542C00	4542	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
4350MH0003360021504543C00	4543	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
4350MH0003360021504544C00	4544	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
4350MH0003360021504545C00	4545	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4350 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4350MH0003360011504547C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4350MH0001630001504568R00	4568	MOTOR COUNT:		14020	RANGE (cm):	6.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4350MH0001630001504569S00	4569	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4350	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4350		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4350MH0003360021504548C00	4548	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4350MH0003360021504549C00	4549	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	223	2
4350MH0003360021504550C00	4550	13996	6.87	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
4350MH0003360021504551C00	4551	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	159	4
4350MH0003360021504552C00	4552	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
4350MH0003360021504553C00	4553	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
4350MH0003360021504554C00	4554	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
4350MH0003360021504555C00	4555	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4350 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 DRT - ~15 mm standoff								
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4350MH0008640011504557C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4350MH0001630001504566R00	4566	MOTOR COUNT:		14917	RANGE (cm):	3.2		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4350MH0001630001504567S00	4567	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00864	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	31-Oct-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00163	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		30	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4350	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4350		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4350MH0008640021504558C00	4558	14797	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	255	1
4350MH0008640021504559C00	4559	14827	3.44	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	223	2
4350MH0008640021504560C00	4560	14857	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	191	3
4350MH0008640021504561C00	4561	14887	3.29	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	159	4
4350MH0008640021504562C00	4562	14917	3.22	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	127	5
4350MH0008640021504563C00	4563	14947	3.16	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	95	6
4350MH0008640021504564C00	4564	14977	3.09	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	63	7
4350MH0008640021504565C00	4565	15007	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Stag_Dome – ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0008760011504579C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404686R00	4686	MOTOR COUNT:		13032	RANGE (cm):	25.6		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404687S00	4687	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00876	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0008760021504580C00	4580	12984	28.68	-2.1	2.4	107.8	7.8	255	1
4352MH0008760021504581C00	4581	12996	27.86	-2.0	2.2	105.0	7.3	223	2
4352MH0008760021504582C00	4582	13008	27.08	-1.8	2.1	102.2	6.9	191	3
4352MH0008760021504583C00	4583	13020	26.34	-1.8	2.0	99.6	6.6	159	4
4352MH0008760021504584C00	4584	13032	25.64	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	127	5
4352MH0008760021504585C00	4585	13044	24.97	-1.6	1.8	94.8	5.9	95	6
4352MH0008760021504586C00	4586	13056	24.33	-1.5	1.7	92.5	5.6	63	7
4352MH0008760021504587C00	4587	13068	23.72	-1.4	1.6	90.4	5.3	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Stag_Dome – stereo-1 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0002240011504589C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404684R00	4684	MOTOR COUNT:		14197	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404685S00	4685	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0002240021504590C00	4590	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	255	1
4352MH0002240021504591C00	4591	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
4352MH0002240021504592C00	4592	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
4352MH0002240021504593C00	4593	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	159	4
4352MH0002240021504594C00	4594	14197	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	127	5
4352MH0002240021504595C00	4595	14239	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	95	6
4352MH0002240021504596C00	4596	14281	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
4352MH0002240021504597C00	4597	14323	5.12	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Stag_Dome – stereo-2 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0002240011504599C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404682R00	4682	MOTOR COUNT:		14196	RANGE (cm):	5.7		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404683S00	4683	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00224	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		42	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0002240021504600C00	4600	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	255	1
4352MH0002240021504601C00	4601	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
4352MH0002240021504602C00	4602	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
4352MH0002240021504603C00	4603	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	159	4
4352MH0002240021504604C00	4604	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	127	5
4352MH0002240021504605C00	4605	14238	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	95	6
4352MH0002240021504606C00	4606	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	63	7
4352MH0002240021504607C00	4607	14322	5.12	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eureka_Valley – after DRT – stereo-1 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0003360011504611C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404680R00	4680	MOTOR COUNT:		13999	RANGE (cm):	6.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404681S00	4681	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24			MERGE SEQUENCE:	mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:	4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353		
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0003360021504612C00	4612	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
4352MH0003360021504613C00	4613	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2
4352MH0003360021504614C00	4614	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
4352MH0003360021504615C00	4615	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
4352MH0003360021504616C00	4616	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4352MH0003360021504617C00	4617	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4352MH0003360021504618C00	4618	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
4352MH0003360021504619C00	4619	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	31	8

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SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eureka_Valley – after DRT – stereo-2 – ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0003360011504621C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404678R00	4678	MOTOR COUNT:		14001	RANGE (cm):	6.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404679S00	4679	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00336	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		12	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0003360021504622C00	4622	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	255	1
4352MH0003360021504623C00	4623	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
4352MH0003360021504624C00	4624	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
4352MH0003360021504625C00	4625	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
4352MH0003360021504626C00	4626	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
4352MH0003360021504627C00	4627	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
4352MH0003360021504628C00	4628	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	63	7
4352MH0003360021504629C00	4629	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	31	8

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SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Eureka_Valley – after DRT – ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0008480011504631C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404676R00	4676	MOTOR COUNT:		15116	RANGE (cm):	2.8		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404677S00	4677	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00848	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		24	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0008480021504632C00	4632	15020	3.00	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	255	1
4352MH0008480021504633C00	4633	15044	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
4352MH0008480021504634C00	4634	15068	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
4352MH0008480021504635C00	4635	15092	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
4352MH0008480021504636C00	4636	15116	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
4352MH0008480021504637C00	4637	15140	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
4352MH0008480021504638C00	4638	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
4352MH0008480021504639C00	4639	15188	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Bear_Lake – ~24 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0003590011504641C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404674R00	4674	MOTOR COUNT:		13028	RANGE (cm):	25.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404675S00	4675	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00359	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		18	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0003590021504642C00	4642	12956	30.77	-2.4	2.7	115.2	9.0	255	1
4352MH0003590021504643C00	4643	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	223	2
4352MH0003590021504644C00	4644	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	191	3
4352MH0003590021504645C00	4645	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	159	4
4352MH0003590021504646C00	4646	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	127	5
4352MH0003590021504647C00	4647	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	95	6
4352MH0003590021504648C00	4648	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	63	7
4352MH0003590021504649C00	4649	13082	23.04	-1.4	1.5	88.0	5.0	31	8

UPDATED: 19_November_2024

SOL 4352 – MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Bear_Lake – stereo-1 – ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0001520011504651C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404672R00	4672	MOTOR COUNT:		14163	RANGE (cm):	5.9		
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404673S00	4673	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152	STACK TYPE:	RELATIVE		
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536	MERGE TYPE:	BASIC		
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4352	FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353	
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0001520021504652C00	4652	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
4352MH0001520021504653C00	4653	14019	6.72	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	223	2
4352MH0001520021504654C00	4654	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	191	3
4352MH0001520021504655C00	4655	14115	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	159	4
4352MH0001520021504656C00	4656	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	127	5
4352MH0001520021504657C00	4657	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6
4352MH0001520021504658C00	4658	14259	5.41	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
4352MH0001520021504659C00	4659	14307	5.19	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8

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SOL 4352 - MAHLI ONBOARD FOCUS MERGE PRODUCT INFORMATION

		target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	CORRESPONDING FRAME:		4352MH0001520011504661C00				
BEST FOCUS IMAGE:	4353MH0005360001404670R00	4670	MOTOR COUNT:		14158	RANGE (cm):		5.9	
RANGE MAP PRODUCT:	4353MH0005360001404671S00	4671	ACQUIRED SEQUENCE:		mhli00152		STACK TYPE:		RELATIVE
ACQUIRED ON DATE:	2-Nov-24		MERGE SEQUENCE:		mhli00536		MERGE TYPE:		BASIC
MOTOR COUNT INTERVAL:		48	ACQUIRED ON SOL:		4352		FOCUS MERGED ON SOL:		4353
INDIVIDUAL FOCUS STACK IMAGES	CDPID	MOTOR COUNT	RANGE (cm)	RANGE UNCERTAINTY (cm)		PIXEL SCALE (µm/pixel)	PIXEL SCALE UNCERTAINTY (µm/pixel)	DN IN RANGE MAP	IMAGE N OF 8
				NEAR	FAR				
4352MH0001520021504662C00	4662	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
4352MH0001520021504663C00	4663	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	223	2
4352MH0001520021504664C00	4664	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	191	3
4352MH0001520021504665C00	4665	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
4352MH0001520021404666C00	4666	14158	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	127	5
4352MH0001520021404667C00	4667	14206	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	95	6
4352MH0001520021404668C00	4668	14254	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
4352MH0001520021404669C00	4669	14302	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 4258–4354. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 4261, 4263, 4277, 4278, 4280, 4281, 4282, 4289, 4291, 4293, 4294, 4295, 4297, 4298, 4300, 4301, 4302, 4304, 4306, 4307, 4309, 4311, 4312, 4314, 4316, 4318, 4319, 4321, 4323, 4325, 4326, 4327, 4328, 4331, 4332, 4334, 4336, 4338, 4339, 4341, 4342, 4345, 4346, 4348, 4350, 4352, 4353.**

updated: 01_August_2024

Sol 4261 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0_Aug_24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	7
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	7

image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: During the day, MAHLI imaged Kings_Canyon after a drill bit preload test. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the ChemMin inlet for cleanliness.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00465	Kings_Canyon after sol 4257 DRT after sol 4257 and 4261 drill bit preload tests ~15 cm standoff	4261MH0004650001502749C00	2749	autofocus sub-frame for intended Kings_Canyon drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload on sol 4261 - after sol 4257 dust removal tool (DRT) - after sol 4257 drill bit preload test - standoff near 35 cm
		4261MH0004650001502750C00	2750	intended Kings_Canyon drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload on sol 4261 - after sol 4257 dust removal tool (DRT) - after sol 4257 drill bit preload test - standoff near 35 cm
mN00312	MAHLI 12.3 cm working distance above ChemMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	4261MH0003120001502751C00	2751	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	4261MH0003120001502752C00	2752	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mN00326	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	4261MH0003120001502754C00	2754	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00228	~19 cm above open ChemMin inlet	4261MH0002280001502755C00	2755	ChemMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 05_August_2024

Sol 4263 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	8 Aug 24			
camera positions:	0	Image ID:		
total parent images:	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed:	0	CDPID:		
total focus merge products:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products:	2			
summary of MAHLI activities: Drill preparation activities at the planned Kings_Canyon sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Kings_Canyon sample discard pile.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N002190	Intended Kings_Canyon Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~24 cm standoff	4263MH001900011502756C00	2756	autoFocus sub-frame for intended Kings_Canyon drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 24 cm
		4263MH001900011502757C00	2757	intended Kings_Canyon drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 24 cm

updated: 21_August_2024

Sol 4277 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		Image ID		Image ID	
Camera position:		2		Image ID:	
total parent images:		19		black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
focus merges performed:		1		CDPID:	
total focus merge products:		2		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total parent images + focus merge products:		21			
summary of MAHLI activities: During the day, MAHLI imaged the Kings_Canyon drill hole and cuttings. The focus stack images were merged as well. At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.					
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN002197	Kings_Canyon drill hole drilled on Sol 4263 ~24 cm standoff	4277MH0001970001502758C00	2758	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Kings_Canyon - drilled sol 4263 - standoff near 24 cm	
		4277MH0001970001502759C00	2759	drill hole in rock named Kings_Canyon - drilled sol 4263 - standoff near 24 cm	
mN002774	Kings_Canyon drill hole drilled on Sol 4263 ~95 mm standoff	4277MH0007740001502760C00	2760	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Kings_Canyon - drilled sol 4263 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 95 mm	
		4277MH0007740001502761C00	2761	drill hole in rock named Kings_Canyon - drilled sol 4263 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 95 mm	
mN00224	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings ~4 cm standoff	4277MH0002240001502762C00	2762	autofocus sub-frame for Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm	
		4277MH0002240001502763C00	2763	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm	
		4277MH0002240001502764C00	2764	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4277MH0002240001502765C00	2765	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4277MH0002240001502766C00	2766	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4277MH0002240001502767C00	2767	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4277MH0002240001502768C00	2768	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4277MH0002240001502769C00	2769	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4277MH0002240001502770C00	2770	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN002258	Focus Merge	4277MH0002240001502771C00	2771	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		4277MH0002240001502772C00	2772	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - Focus stack acquired sol 4277 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2764-2771 - best focus image product	
mN00312	MAHLI 12.3 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	4277MH0003120001502773C00	2773	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm - Focus stack acquired sol 4277 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2764-2771 - range map product	
		4277MH0003120001502774C00	2774	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance	
mN00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	4277MH0003120001502775C00	2775	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance	
		4277MH0003120001502776C00	2776	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance	
mN00326	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	4277MH0003120001502777C00	2777	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance	
		4277MH0003120001502778C00	2778	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance	

updated: 19_August_2024

Sol 4278 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	18-Aug-24	Image ID:		
camera position:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
total parent images:	2	CDPID:		
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total focus merge products:	0			
total parent images + focus merge products:	2			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Kings_Canyon drill cuttings.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings ~4 cm standoff	4278MH00122001502779C00	2779	autoFocus sub-frame for Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm
		4278MH001220011502780C00	2780	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm

updated: 16_January_2025

Sol 4280 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-Aug-24
camera positions	6
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	35

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Gabbot_Pass.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Gabbot_Pass before DRT ~25 cm standoff	4280MH001900011502781C0D	2781	autoFocus sub-frame for target Gabbot_Pass - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4280MH001900011502782C0D	2782	target Gabbot_Pass - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Gabbot_Pass before DRT ~5 cm standoff	4280MH001220011502783C0D	2783	autoFocus sub-frame for target Gabbot_Pass - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
		4280MH001220011502784C0D	2784	target Gabbot_Pass - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	Gabbot_Pass after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4280MH001900011502785C0D	2785	autoFocus sub-frame for target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4280MH001900011502786C0D	2786	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Gabbot_Pass after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4280MH003360011502787C0D	2787	autoFocus sub-frame for target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4280MH003360011502788C0D	2788	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4280MH003360011502789C0D	2789	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502790C0D	2790	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502791C0D	2791	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502792C0D	2792	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502793C0D	2793	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502794C0D	2794	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502795C0D	2795	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502796C0D	2796	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Gabbot_Pass after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4280MH003360011502797C0D	2797	autoFocus sub-frame for target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4280MH003360011502798C0D	2798	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4280MH003360011502799C0D	2799	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502800C0D	2800	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502801C0D	2801	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502802C0D	2802	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502803C0D	2803	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502804C0D	2804	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502805C0D	2805	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH003360011502806C0D	2806	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Gabbot_Pass after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4280MH008480011502807C0D	2807	autoFocus sub-frame for target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4280MH008480011502808C0D	2808	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4280MH008480011502809C0D	2809	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH008480011502810C0D	2810	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH008480011502811C0D	2811	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH008480011502812C0D	2812	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH008480011502813C0D	2813	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH008480011502814C0D	2814	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH008480011502815C0D	2815	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4280MH008480011502816C0D	2816	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 22_August_2024

Sol 4281 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		MAHLI imaged the Kings_Canyon drill cuttings. Focus stack images from Sol 4280 were merged.		
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
acquired/performed date(s)		22-Aug-24		
camera positions		3		image ID:
total parent images		2		black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed		3		CDPID:
total focus merge products		6		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products		8		
mN00122	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings ~5 cm standoff	4281MH00122001502817C00	2817	autoFocus sub-frame for Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
		4281MH001220011502818C00	2818	Kings_Canyon drill cuttings - standoff near 5 cm
mN00289	Focus Merges	4281MH00193001502819R00	2819	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2809-2816 - best focus image product
		4281MH00193001502820S00	2820	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2809-2816 - range map product
		4281MH00193001502821R00	2821	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2799-2806 - best focus image product
		4281MH00193001502822S00	2822	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2799-2806 - range map product
		4281MH00193001502823R00	2823	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2789-2796 - best focus image product
		4281MH00193001502824S00	2824	target Gabbot_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4280 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2789-2796 - range map product

updated: 26_August_2024

Sol 4282 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	22-Aug-24	
		camera positions	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target March_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	March_Lake after DRT ~24 cm standoff	482MH0019000115028250D	2825	autoFocus sub-frame for target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		482MH0019000115028260D	2826	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00196	March_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	482MH0033600115028270D	2827	autoFocus sub-frame for target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		482MH0033600115028280D	2828	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		482MH0033600115028290D	2829	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028300D	2830	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028310D	2831	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028320D	2832	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028330D	2833	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028340D	2834	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028350D	2835	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028360D	2836	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00196	March_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	482MH0033600115028370D	2837	autoFocus sub-frame for target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		482MH0033600115028380D	2838	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		482MH0033600115028390D	2839	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028400D	2840	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028410D	2841	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028420D	2842	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028430D	2843	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028440D	2844	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028450D	2845	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0033600115028460D	2846	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	March_Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff	482MH0084800115028470D	2847	autoFocus sub-frame for target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		482MH0084800115028480D	2848	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		482MH0084800115028490D	2849	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0084800115028500D	2850	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0084800115028510D	2851	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0084800115028520D	2852	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0084800115028530D	2853	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0084800115028540D	2854	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0084800115028550D	2855	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		482MH0084800115028560D	2856	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	482MH0019300115028570D	2857	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4282 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2849-2856 - best focus image product
		482MH0019300115028580D	2858	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4282 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2849-2856 - range map product
		482MH0019300115028590D	2859	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4282 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2839-2846 - best focus image product
		482MH0019300115028600D	2860	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4282 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2839-2846 - range map product
		482MH0019300115028610D	2861	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4282 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2829-2836 - best focus image product
482MH0019300115028620D	2862	target March_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4282 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2829-2836 - range map product		

Sol 4289 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-Aug-24
camera position	2
total parent images	65
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	77

MAHLI image of the DRT + brushed target Eichorn_Pinnacle and the target Thousand_Island_Lake. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00190	Eichorn_Pinnacle after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4289MH0019000015028630CD	2863	autoFocus sub-frame for target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4289MH00190001502864CD	2864	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mNI00196	Eichorn_Pinnacle after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4289MH003360001502865CD	2865	autoFocus sub-frame for target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4289MH00336001502866CD	2866	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4289MH003360021502867CD	2867	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502868CD	2868	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360031502869CD	2869	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360031502870CD	2870	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360031502871CD	2871	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360031502872CD	2872	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360031502873CD	2873	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360031502874CD	2874	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00196	Eichorn_Pinnacle after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4289MH003360001502875CD	2875	autoFocus sub-frame for target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4289MH00336001502876CD	2876	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4289MH003360021502877CD	2877	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502878CD	2878	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502879CD	2879	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502880CD	2880	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502881CD	2881	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502882CD	2882	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502883CD	2883	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH003360021502884CD	2884	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00873	Eichorn_Pinnacle after DRT ~2 cm standoff	4289MH0008730001502885CD	2885	autoFocus sub-frame for target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4289MH000873001502886CD	2886	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		4289MH0008730021502887CD	2887	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008730021502888CD	2888	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008730021502889CD	2889	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008730021502890CD	2890	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008730021502891CD	2891	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008730021502892CD	2892	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008730021502893CD	2893	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008730021502894CD	2894	target Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00862	Thousand_Island_Lake ~25 cm standoff	4289MH0008620001502895CD	2895	autoFocus sub-frame for target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
		4289MH000862001502896CD	2896	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
		4289MH0008620021502897CD	2897	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4289MH0008620021502898CD	2898	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008620021502899CD	2899	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008620021502900CD	2900	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008620021502901CD	2901	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008620021502902CD	2902	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008620021502903CD	2903	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH0008620021502904CD	2904	target Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00885	Thousand_Island_Lake stereo-1 ~15 cm standoff	4289MH0008850001502905CD	2905	autoFocus sub-frame for target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm
		4289MH000885001502907CD	2907	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm
		4289MH000885001502908CD	2908	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4289MH000885001502909CD	2909	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502910CD	2910	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502911CD	2911	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502912CD	2912	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502913CD	2913	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502914CD	2914	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502915CD	2915	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00885	Thousand_Island_Lake stereo-2 ~14 cm standoff	4289MH000885001502917CD	2917	autoFocus sub-frame for target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		4289MH000885001502918CD	2918	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		4289MH000885001502919CD	2919	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4289MH000885001502920CD	2920	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502921CD	2921	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502922CD	2922	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502923CD	2923	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502924CD	2924	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502925CD	2925	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4289MH000885001502926CD	2926	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4289MH000885001502927CD	2927	target Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mNH00163	Focus Merge	4289MH00163000150292800	2928	target_Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2920-2927 - best focus image product
		4289MH001630001502929500	2929	target_Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2920-2927 - range map product
		4289MH001630001502930800	2930	target_Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2909-2916 - best focus image product
		4289MH001630001502931500	2931	target_Thousand_Island_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2909-2916 - range map product
		4289MH001630001502932800	2932	target_Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2898-2905 - best focus image product
		4289MH001630001502933500	2933	target_Thousand_Island_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2898-2905 - range map product
		4289MH001630001502934800	2934	target_Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2887-2894 - best focus image product
		4289MH001630001502935500	2935	target_Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2887-2894 - range map product
		4289MH001630001502936800	2936	target_Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2877-2884 - best focus image product
		4289MH001630001502937500	2937	target_Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2877-2884 - range map product
		4289MH001630001502938800	2938	target_Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2867-2874 - best focus image product
		4289MH001630001502939500	2939	target_Eichorn_Pinnacle - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4289 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2867-2874 - range map product

updated: 03_September_2024

Sol 4293 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	8 Sep 24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4293 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALLE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	4293MH001630001503004N00	3004	target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2996-3003 - best focus image product
		4293MH001630001503005S00	3005	target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2996-3003 - range map product
		4293MH001630001503006R00	3006	target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2986-2993 - best focus image product
		4293MH001630001503007S00	3007	target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2986-2993 - range map product
		4293MH001630001503008N00	3008	target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2976-2983 - best focus image product
		4293MH001630001503009S00	3009	target Upper_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2976-2983 - range map product
		4293MH001630001503010N00	3010	target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2944-2971 - best focus image product
		4293MH001630001503011S00	3011	target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2944-2971 - range map product
		4293MH001630001503012R00	3012	target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2954-2961 - best focus image product
		4293MH001630001503013S00	3013	target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2954-2961 - range map product
		4293MH001630001503014R00	3014	target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2944-2951 - best focus image product
		4293MH001630001503015S00	3015	target Lower_Boy_Scout_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4291 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2944-2951 - range map product

Sol 4294 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	4-Sep-24
camera position	2
total parent images	63
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	74

MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target Erin_Lake and the target Picture_Puzzle. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00290	Erin_Lake after DRT ~24 cm standoff	429MH0001900001503016C00	3016	autofocus sub-frame for target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		429MH000190001503017C00	3017	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00268	Erin_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	429MH0001680001503018C00	3018	autofocus sub-frame for target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		429MH000168001503019C00	3019	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		429MH0001680021503020C00	3020	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503021C00	3021	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503022C00	3022	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503023C00	3023	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503024C00	3024	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503025C00	3025	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503026C00	3026	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503027C00	3027	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00268	Erin_Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	429MH0001680001503028C00	3028	autofocus sub-frame for target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		429MH000168001503029C00	3029	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		429MH0001680021503030C00	3030	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503031C00	3031	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503032C00	3032	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503033C00	3033	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503034C00	3034	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503035C00	3035	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503036C00	3036	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0001680021503037C00	3037	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Erin_Lake after DRT ~15 mm standoff	429MH0003020001503038C00	3038	autofocus sub-frame for target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		429MH000302001503039C00	3039	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		429MH0003020021503040C00	3040	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003020021503041C00	3041	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003020021503042C00	3042	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003020021503043C00	3043	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003020021503044C00	3044	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003020021503045C00	3045	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003020021503046C00	3046	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003020021503047C00	3047	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Picture_Puzzle ~24 cm standoff	429MH0003590001503048C00	3048	autofocus sub-frame for target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm
		429MH000359001503049C00	3049	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm
		429MH0003590021503050C00	3050	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003590021503051C00	3051	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003590021503052C00	3052	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003590021503053C00	3053	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003590021503054C00	3054	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003590021503055C00	3055	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003590021503056C00	3056	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0003590021503057C00	3057	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Picture_Puzzle stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	429MH0002240001503058C00	3058	autofocus sub-frame for target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		429MH000224001503059C00	3059	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm
		429MH0002240021503060C00	3060	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503061C00	3061	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503062C00	3062	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503063C00	3063	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503064C00	3064	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503065C00	3065	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503066C00	3066	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503067C00	3067	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Picture_Puzzle stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	429MH0002240001503068C00	3068	autofocus sub-frame for target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		429MH000224001503069C00	3069	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm
		429MH0002240021503070C00	3070	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503071C00	3071	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503072C00	3072	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503073C00	3073	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503074C00	3074	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503075C00	3075	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503076C00	3076	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		429MH0002240021503077C00	3077	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mNH00163	Focus Merge	4294MH00163000150307800	3078	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3070-3077 - best focus image product
		4294MH001630001503079500	3079	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3070-3077 - range map product
		4294MH001630001503080000	3080	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3060-3067 - best focus image product
		4294MH001630001503081500	3081	target Picture_Puzzle - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3060-3067 - range map product
		4294MH001630001503082000	3082	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3050-3057 - best focus image product
		4294MH001630001503083500	3083	target Picture_Puzzle - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3050-3057 - range map product
		4294MH001630001503084000	3084	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3040-3047 - best focus image product
		4294MH001630001503085500	3085	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3040-3047 - range map product
		4294MH001630001503086000	3086	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3030-3037 - best focus image product
		4294MH001630001503087500	3087	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3030-3037 - range map product
		4294MH001630001503088000	3088	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3020-3027 - best focus image product
		4294MH001630001503089500	3089	target Erin_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4294 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3020-3027 - range map product

updated: 10_September_2024

Sol 4295 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)		5-Sep-24		
camera position		75		
total parent images		7		
focus merges performed		7		
total focus merge products		14		
total parent images + focus merge products		84		
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Campfire_Lake and Gemini. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00359	Campfire_Lake ~25 cm standoff	4295MH003590011503090C00	3090	autofocus sub-frame for target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4295MH003590011503091C00	3091	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4295MH003590211503092C00	3092	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503093C00	3093	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590211503094C00	3094	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503095C00	3095	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590211503096C00	3096	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503097C00	3097	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590211503098C00	3098	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503099C00	3099	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Campfire_Lake APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	4295MH002240011503100C00	3100	autofocus sub-frame for target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4295MH002240011503101C00	3101	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4295MH002240011503102C00	3102	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503103C00	3103	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503104C00	3104	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503105C00	3105	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503106C00	3106	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503107C00	3107	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503108C00	3108	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503109C00	3109	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Campfire_Lake APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	4295MH002240011503110C00	3110	autofocus sub-frame for target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4295MH002240011503111C00	3111	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4295MH002240011503112C00	3112	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503113C00	3113	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503114C00	3114	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503115C00	3115	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503116C00	3116	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503117C00	3117	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503118C00	3118	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503119C00	3119	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Campfire_Lake APXS spot 1 ~55 mm standoff	4295MH002240011503120C00	3120	autofocus sub-frame for target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4295MH002240011503121C00	3121	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4295MH002240011503122C00	3122	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503123C00	3123	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503124C00	3124	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503125C00	3125	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503126C00	3126	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503127C00	3127	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503128C00	3128	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503129C00	3129	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Gemini ~25 cm standoff	4295MH003590011503130C00	3130	autofocus sub-frame for target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm
		4295MH003590011503131C00	3131	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm
		4295MH003590211503132C00	3132	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503133C00	3133	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590211503134C00	3134	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503135C00	3135	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590211503136C00	3136	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503137C00	3137	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590211503138C00	3138	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH003590011503139C00	3139	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Gemini stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4295MH002240011503140C00	3140	autofocus sub-frame for target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4295MH002240011503141C00	3141	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4295MH002240011503142C00	3142	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503143C00	3143	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503144C00	3144	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503145C00	3145	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503146C00	3146	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503147C00	3147	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503148C00	3148	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH002240011503149C00	3149	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00224	Gemini stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4295MH0002400150315000	3150	autofocus sub-frame for target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4295MH00024001503151000	3151	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4295MH00024001503152000	3152	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH00024001503153000	3153	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH00024001503154000	3154	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH00024001503155000	3155	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH00024001503156000	3156	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH00024001503157000	3157	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH00024001503158000	3158	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4295MH00024001503159000	3159	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00171	Focus Merges	4295MH00017000150316000	3160	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3152-3159 - best focus image product
		4295MH000170001503161500	3161	target Gemini - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3152-3159 - range map product
		4295MH000170001503162000	3162	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3142-3149 - best focus image product
		4295MH000170001503163500	3163	target Gemini - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3142-3149 - range map product
		4295MH000170001503164000	3164	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3132-3139 - best focus image product
		4295MH000170001503165500	3165	target Gemini - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3132-3139 - range map product
		4295MH000170001503166000	3166	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3122-3129 - best focus image product
		4295MH000170001503167500	3167	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3122-3129 - range map product
		4295MH000170001503168000	3168	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3112-3119 - best focus image product
		4295MH000170001503169500	3169	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3112-3119 - range map product
		4295MH000170001503170000	3170	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3102-3109 - best focus image product
		4295MH000170001503171500	3171	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3102-3109 - range map product
		4295MH000170001503172000	3172	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3092-3099 - best focus image product
		4295MH000170001503173500	3173	target Campfire_Lake - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4295 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3092-3099 - range map product

updated: 23_September_2024

Sol 4297 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	9 Sep 24
camera position	6
total parent images	95
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	95

MAHLI image of the targets Big_Bird_Lake and Big_Baldy.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL, DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00865	Big_Bird_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4297MH000865001503174200	3174	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm		
		4297MH000865001503175200	3175	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm		
		4297MH000865001503176200	3176	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000865001503177200	3177	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000865001503178200	3178	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000865001503179200	3179	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000865001503180200	3180	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000865001503181200	3181	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000865001503182200	3182	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000865001503183200	3183	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000306001503184200	3184	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm		
		4297MH000306001503185200	3185	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm		
		4297MH000306001503186200	3186	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000306001503187200	3187	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00306	Big_Bird_Lake stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	4297MH000306001503188200	3188	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000306001503189200	3189	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000306001503190200	3190	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000306001503191200	3191	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000306001503192200	3192	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000306001503193200	3193	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00306	Big_Bird_Lake stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	4297MH000306001503194200	3194	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
				4297MH000306001503195200	3195	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
				4297MH000306001503196200	3196	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000306001503197200	3197	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000306001503198200	3198	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000306001503199200	3199	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000306001503200200	3200	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000306001503201200	3201	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4297MH000306001503202200	3202			target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4297MH000306001503203200	3203			target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00855	Big_Baldy ~24 cm standoff			4297MH000855001503204200	3204	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm
				4297MH000855001503205200	3205	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm
				4297MH000855001503206200	3206	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000855001503207200	3207	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4297MH000855001503208200	3208	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000855001503209200	3209	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000855001503210200	3210	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000855001503211200	3211	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000855001503212200	3212	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000855001503213200	3213	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00383	Big_Baldy stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4297MH000383001503214200	3214	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
				4297MH000383001503215200	3215	target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
				4297MH000383001503216200	3216	target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000383001503217200	3217	target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4297MH000383001503218200	3218			target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4297MH000383001503219200	3219			target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4297MH000383001503220200	3220			target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4297MH000383001503221200	3221			target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4297MH000383001503222200	3222			target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4297MH000383001503223200	3223			target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00383	Big_Baldy stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff			4297MH000383001503224200	3224	autofocus sub-frame for target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				4297MH000383001503225200	3225	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				4297MH000383001503226200	3226	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4297MH000383001503227200	3227	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4297MH000383001503228200	3228	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000383001503229200	3229	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000383001503230200	3230	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000383001503231200	3231	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000383001503232200	3232	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4297MH000383001503233200	3233	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 09_September_2024

Sol 4298 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	8 Sep 24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4297 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000163	Focus Merges	4298MH00163000150234400	3234	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3226-3233 - best focus image product
		4298MH00163000150233500	3235	target Big_Baldy - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3226-3233 - range map product
		4298MH00163000150233600	3236	target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3218-3223 - best focus image product
		4298MH00163000150233750	3237	target Big_Baldy - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3216-3223 - range map product
		4298MH00163000150233800	3238	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3206-3213 - best focus image product
		4298MH00163000150233950	3239	target Big_Baldy - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3206-3213 - range map product
		4298MH0016300015024000	3240	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3196-3203 - best focus image product
		4298MH0016300015024150	3241	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3196-3203 - range map product
		4298MH0016300015024200	3242	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3186-3193 - best focus image product
		4298MH0016300015024350	3243	target Big_Bird_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3186-3193 - range map product
		4298MH0016300015024400	3244	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3176-3183 - best focus image product
		4298MH0016300015024500	3245	target Big_Bird_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4297 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3176-3183 - range map product

mH00886	Boneyard_Meadow stereo-1 -35 cm standoff	4300MH00886001503308C00	3308	autofocus sub-frame for target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm
		4300MH00886001503309C00	3309	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm
		4300MH00886001503310C00	3310	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503311C00	3311	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503312C00	3312	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503313C00	3313	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503314C00	3314	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503315C00	3315	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503316C00	3316	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4300MH00886001503317C00	3317	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00886	Boneyard_Meadow stereo-2 -35 cm standoff	4300MH00886001503318C00	3318	autofocus sub-frame for target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm
		4300MH00886001503319C00	3319	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm
		4300MH00886001503320C00	3320	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503321C00	3321	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503322C00	3322	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503323C00	3323	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503324C00	3324	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503325C00	3325	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4300MH00886001503326C00	3326	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4300MH00886001503327C00	3327	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 12_September_2024

Sol 4301 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	11-Sep-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4300 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00170	Focus Merges	4301MH0017000150332890	3328	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3320-3327 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150332950	3329	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3320-3327 - range map product
		4301MH0017000150333090	3330	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3310-3317 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150333150	3331	target Boneyard_Meadow - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3310-3317 - range map product
		4301MH0017000150333290	3332	target Pond_Lily_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3300-3307 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150333350	3333	target Pond_Lily_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3300-3307 - range map product
		4301MH0017000150333490	3334	target Pond_Lily_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3290-3297 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150333550	3335	target Pond_Lily_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3290-3297 - range map product
		4301MH0017000150333690	3336	target Pond_Lily_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3280-3287 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150333750	3337	target Pond_Lily_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3280-3287 - range map product
		4301MH0017000150333890	3338	target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3260-3275 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150333950	3339	target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3260-3275 - range map product
		4301MH0017000150334090	3340	target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 17 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3250-3265 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150334150	3341	target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 17 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3250-3265 - range map product
		4301MH0017000150334290	3342	target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3240-3255 - best focus image product
		4301MH0017000150334350	3343	target Window_Cliffs - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4300 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3240-3255 - range map product

updated: 23_September_2024

Sol 4302 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	12-Sep-24
camera position	5
total parent images	51
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	61

MAHLI imaged the targets Lucy_Foot_Pass and Sandy_Meadow. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00855	Lucy_Foot_Pass ~25 cm standoff	4302MH008550011503440C0	3344	autofocus sub-frame for target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm
		4302MH008550011503450C0	3345	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm
		4302MH008550011503460C0	3346	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008550011503470C0	3347	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008550011503480C0	3348	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008550011503490C0	3349	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008550011503500C0	3350	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008550011503510C0	3351	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008550011503520C0	3352	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008550011503530C0	3353	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503540C0	3354	autofocus sub-frame for target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4302MH003080011503550C0	3355	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		4302MH003080011503560C0	3356	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503570C0	3357	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00358	Lucy_Foot_Pass Stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	4302MH003080011503580C0	3358	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503590C0	3359	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503600C0	3360	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503610C0	3361	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503620C0	3362	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503630C0	3363	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503640C0	3364	autofocus sub-frame for target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4302MH003080011503650C0	3365	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		4302MH003080011503660C0	3366	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503670C0	3367	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503680C0	3368	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503690C0	3369	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503700C0	3370	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003080011503710C0	3371	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4302MH003080011503720C0	3372	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4302MH003080011503730C0	3373	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00357	Lucy_Foot_Pass ~25 mm standoff	4302MH003570011503740C0	3374	autofocus sub-frame for target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm
		4302MH003570011503750C0	3375	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm
		4302MH003570011503760C0	3376	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003570011503770C0	3377	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003570011503780C0	3378	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003570011503790C0	3379	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003570011503800C0	3380	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003570011503810C0	3381	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003570011503820C0	3382	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH003570011503830C0	3383	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4302MH008620011503840C0	3384	autofocus sub-frame for target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm
		4302MH008620011503850C0	3385	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm
		4302MH008620011503860C0	3386	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4302MH008620011503870C0	3387	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4302MH008620011503880C0	3388	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4302MH008620011503890C0	3389	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4302MH008620011503900C0	3390	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4302MH008620011503910C0	3391	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4302MH008620011503920C0	3392	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4302MH008620011503930C0	3393	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4302MH008620011503940C0	3394	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00888	Focus Merges	4302MH008880011503950C0	3395	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3387-3394 - best focus image product
		4302MH008880011503960C0	3396	target Sandy_Meadow - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3387-3394 - range map product
		4302MH008880011503970C0	3397	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3376-3383 - best focus image product
		4302MH008880011503980C0	3398	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3376-3383 - range map product
		4302MH008880011503990C0	3399	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3366-3373 - best focus image product
		4302MH008880011504000C0	3400	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3366-3373 - range map product
		4302MH008880011504010C0	3401	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3356-3363 - best focus image product
		4302MH008880011504020C0	3402	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3356-3363 - range map product
		4302MH008880011504030C0	3403	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3346-3353 - best focus image product
		4302MH008880011504040C0	3404	target Lucy_Foot_Pass - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4302 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3346-3353 - range map product

mH00297	College_Rock stereo-2 -5 cm standoff	430MH0002970001503474C00	3471	autofocus sub-frame for target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		430MH0002970011503472C00	3472	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		430MH0002970021503473C00	3473	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0002970021503474C00	3474	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0002970021503475C00	3475	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0002970021503476C00	3476	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0002970021503477C00	3477	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0002970021503478C00	3478	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0002970021503479C00	3479	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0002970021503480C00	3480	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00405	College_Rock -15 mm standoff	430MH000406001503481C00	3481	autofocus sub-frame for target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm
		430MH0004060011503482C00	3482	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm
		430MH0004060021503483C00	3483	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0004060021503484C00	3484	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0004060021503485C00	3485	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0004060021503486C00	3486	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0004060021503487C00	3487	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0004060021503488C00	3488	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0004060021503489C00	3489	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		430MH0004060021503490C00	3490	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 16_September_2024

Sol 4306 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16-Sep-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	8 CDPID
total focus merge products	16 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products	16

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4304 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000170	Focus Merges	4306MH00170001503491900	3491	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3483-3490 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503492500	3492	target College_Rock - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3483-3490 - range map product
		4306MH00170001503493900	3493	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3473-3480 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503494500	3494	target College_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3473-3480 - range map product
		4306MH00170001503495900	3495	target College_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3463-3470 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503496500	3496	target College_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3463-3470 - range map product
		4306MH00170001503497900	3497	target College_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3453-3460 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503498500	3498	target College_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3453-3460 - range map product
		4306MH00170001503499900	3499	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3443-3450 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503500500	3500	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3443-3450 - range map product
		4306MH00170001503501900	3501	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3433-3440 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503502500	3502	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3433-3440 - range map product
		4306MH00170001503503900	3503	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3423-3430 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503504500	3504	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3423-3430 - range map product
		4306MH00170001503505900	3505	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3413-3420 - best focus image product
		4306MH00170001503506500	3506	target Wales_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4304 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3413-3420 - range map product

updated: 03_October_2024

Sol 4307 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-Sep-24
camera position	4
total parent images	59
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	69

MAHLI images of the targets Grasshopper_Flat and Frog_Lake. The focus stack images were merged as well.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00678	Grasshopper_Flat ~26 cm standoff	4307MH0006780011503507020	3507	autofocus sub-frame for target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm		
		4307MH0006780011503508020	3508	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm		
		4307MH0006780011503509020	3509	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4307MH0006780011503510020	3510	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006780011503511020	3511	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006780011503512020	3512	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006780011503513020	3513	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006780011503514020	3514	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006780011503515020	3515	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006780011503516020	3516	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006780011503517020	3517	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00698	Grasshopper_Flat stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4307MH0006980011503518020	3518	autofocus sub-frame for target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4307MH0006980011503519020	3519	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4307MH0006980011503520020	3520	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure
4307MH0006980011503521020	3521			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4307MH0006980011503522020	3522			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4307MH0006980011503523020	3523			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4307MH0006980011503524020	3524			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4307MH0006980011503525020	3525			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4307MH0006980011503526020	3526			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4307MH0006980011503527020	3527			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4307MH0006980011503528020	3528			target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00698	Grasshopper_Flat stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff			4307MH0006980011503529020	3529	autofocus sub-frame for target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				4307MH0006980011503530020	3530	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				4307MH0006980011503531020	3531	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4307MH0006980011503532020	3532	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006980011503533020	3533	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006980011503534020	3534	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006980011503535020	3535	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006980011503536020	3536	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006980011503537020	3537	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006980011503538020	3538	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0006980011503539020	3539	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00706	Frog_Lake mosaic position 1 of 2 ~25 cm standoff	4307MH0007060011503540020	3540	autofocus sub-frame for target Frog_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
				4307MH0007060011503541020	3541	target Frog_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
				4307MH0007060011503542020	3542	target Frog_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00706	Frog_Lake mosaic position 2 of 2 ~25 cm standoff	4307MH0007060011503543020	3543	autofocus sub-frame for target Frog_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		4307MH0007060011503544020	3544	target Frog_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm		
		4307MH0007060011503545020	3545	target Frog_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00299	Frog_Lake stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4307MH0002990011503546020	3546	autofocus sub-frame for target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4307MH0002990011503547020	3547	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4307MH0002990011503548020	3548	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503549020	3549	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503550020	3550	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503551020	3551	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503552020	3552	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503553020	3553	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503554020	3554	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503555020	3555	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00299	Frog_Lake stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4307MH0002990011503556020	3556	autofocus sub-frame for target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4307MH0002990011503557020	3557	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm		
		4307MH0002990011503558020	3558	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503559020	3559	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503560020	3560	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503561020	3561	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503562020	3562	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503563020	3563	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503564020	3564	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4307MH0002990011503565020	3565	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00227	Focus Merges	4307MH0002270001150356600	3566	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3558-3565 - best focus image product		
		4307MH0002270001150356700	3567	target Frog_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3558-3565 - range map product		
		4307MH0002270001150356800	3568	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3548-3555 - best focus image product		
		4307MH0002270001150356900	3569	target Frog_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3548-3555 - range map product		
		4307MH0002270001150357000	3570	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3532-3539 - best focus image product		
		4307MH0002270001150357100	3571	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3532-3539 - range map product		
		4307MH0002270001150357200	3572	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3521-3528 - best focus image product		
		4307MH0002270001150357300	3573	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3521-3528 - range map product		
		4307MH0002270001150357400	3574	target Grasshopper_Flat - stereo-1 - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3510-3517 - best focus image product		
		4307MH0002270001150357500	3575	target Grasshopper_Flat - standoff near 26 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4307 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3510-3517 - range map product		

updated: 03_October_2024

Sol 4309 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	18-Sep-24	
		camera position	4	Image ID:
		total parent images	33	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	3	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	6	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT + brushed target The_Ministar and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002190	The_Ministar after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4309MH00190001503576C00	3576	autoFocus sub-frame for target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4309MH00190001503577C00	3577	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN002168	The_Ministar after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4309MH001680021503578C00	3578	autoFocus sub-frame for target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4309MH00168001503579C00	3579	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4309MH001680021503580C00	3580	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503581C00	3581	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH001680021503582C00	3582	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503583C00	3583	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH001680021503584C00	3584	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503585C00	3585	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH001680021503586C00	3586	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503587C00	3587	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002168	The_Ministar after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4309MH001680021503588C00	3588	autoFocus sub-frame for target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4309MH00168001503589C00	3589	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4309MH001680021503590C00	3590	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503591C00	3591	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH001680021503592C00	3592	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503593C00	3593	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH001680021503594C00	3594	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503595C00	3595	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH001680021503596C00	3596	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00168001503597C00	3597	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002743	The_Ministar after DRT ~15 mm standoff	4309MH007430021503600C00	3598	autoFocus sub-frame for target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4309MH00743001503599C00	3599	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4309MH007430021503600C00	3600	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00743001503601C00	3601	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH007430021503602C00	3602	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00743001503603C00	3603	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH007430021503604C00	3604	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00743001503605C00	3605	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH007430021503606C00	3606	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4309MH00743001503607C00	3607	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN002193	Focus Merges	4309MH00193001503608C00	3608	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4309 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3600-3607 - best focus image product
		4309MH00193001503609C00	3609	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4309 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3600-3607 - range map product
		4309MH00193001503610C00	3610	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4309 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3590-3597 - best focus image product
		4309MH00193001503611C00	3611	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4309 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3590-3597 - range map product
		4309MH00193001503612C00	3612	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4309 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3580-3587 - best focus image product
4309MH00193001503613C00	3613	target The_Ministar - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4309 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3580-3587 - range map product		

Sol 4311 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	21-Sep-24			
		camera position	77	Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
		total parent images	0	CDPID:		
		focus merges performed	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total focus merge products	0			
		total parent images + focus merge products	77			
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Aeolian_Buttres, the DRT-brushed target Cherry_Ridge, and the REMS UV Sensor.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00889	Aeolian_Buttres ~24 cm standoff	4311MH0008890011503614C00	3614	autoFocus sub-frame for target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm		
		4311MH0008890011503615C00	3615	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm		
		4311MH0008890011503616C00	3616	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4311MH0008890011503617C00	3617	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0008890011503618C00	3618	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0008890011503619C00	3619	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0008890011503620C00	3620	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0008890011503621C00	3621	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0008890011503622C00	3622	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0008890011503623C00	3623	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0008890011503624C00	3624	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00723	Aeolian_Buttres stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4311MH0007230011503625C00	3625	autoFocus sub-frame for target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
				4311MH0007230011503626C00	3626	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
				4311MH0007230011503627C00	3627	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
4311MH0007230011503628C00	3628			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH0007230011503629C00	3629			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH0007230011503630C00	3630			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH0007230011503631C00	3631			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH0007230011503632C00	3632			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH0007230011503633C00	3633			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH0007230011503634C00	3634			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH0007230011503635C00	3635			target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00723	Aeolian_Buttres stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff			4311MH0007230011503636C00	3636	autoFocus sub-frame for target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				4311MH0007230011503637C00	3637	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				4311MH0007230011503638C00	3638	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		4311MH0007230011503639C00	3639	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0007230011503640C00	3640	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0007230011503641C00	3641	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0007230011503642C00	3642	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0007230011503643C00	3643	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0007230011503644C00	3644	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0007230011503645C00	3645	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH0007230011503646C00	3646	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00190	Cherry_Ridge after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4311MH00019000011503647C00	3647	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
				4311MH00019000011503648C00	3648	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		mNI00168	Cherry_Ridge after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4311MH00016800011503649C00	3649	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
4311MH00016800011503650C00	3650			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
4311MH00016800011503651C00	3651			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00016800011503652C00	3652			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00016800011503653C00	3653			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00016800011503654C00	3654			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00016800011503655C00	3655			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00016800011503656C00	3656			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00016800011503657C00	3657			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00016800011503658C00	3658			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00168	Cherry_Ridge after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff			4311MH00016800011503659C00	3659	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4311MH00016800011503660C00	3660	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4311MH00016800011503661C00	3661	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4311MH00016800011503662C00	3662	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00016800011503663C00	3663	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH00016800011503664C00	3664	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH00016800011503665C00	3665	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH00016800011503666C00	3666	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH00016800011503667C00	3667	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4311MH00016800011503668C00	3668	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00302	Cherry_Ridge after DRT APXS spot 2 ~2 cm standoff	4311MH00030200011503669C00	3669	autoFocus sub-frame for target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
				4311MH00030200011503670C00	3670	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm
				4311MH00030200011503671C00	3671	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4311MH00030200011503672C00	3672	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4311MH00030200011503673C00	3673			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00030200011503674C00	3674			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00030200011503675C00	3675			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00030200011503676C00	3676			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00030200011503677C00	3677			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4311MH00030200011503678C00	3678			target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

Continued on Next Page...

mNH00168	Cherry_Ridge after DRT APX3 spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4311MH00168001503679C00	3679	autofocus sub-frame for target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4311MH00168001503680C00	3680	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4311MH00168001503681C00	3681	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00168001503682C00	3682	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00168001503683C00	3683	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00168001503684C00	3684	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00168001503685C00	3685	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00168001503686C00	3686	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00168001503687C00	3687	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4311MH00168001503688C00	3688	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNH00095	REM3 UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	4311MH00095001503689C00	3689	autofocus sub-frame for REM3 UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		4311MH00095001503690C00	3690	REM3 UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation

updated: 23 September 2024

Sol 4312 - MAHI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Sep-24
camera position	25
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	34

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPOD: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels

summary of MAHI activities
 Focus stack images from Sol 4312 were merged. MAHI images > 360° of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPOD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN0080	Focus Merges	4312MH0008000015036919K00	3691	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3681-3688 - best focus image product
		4312MH0008000015036925K00	3692	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3681-3688 - range map product
		4312MH0008000015036930K00	3693	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3671-3678 - best focus image product
		4312MH0008000015036945K00	3694	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3671-3678 - range map product
		4312MH0008000015036950K00	3695	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3661-3668 - best focus image product
		4312MH0008000015036965K00	3696	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3661-3668 - range map product
		4312MH0008000015036970K00	3697	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3651-3658 - best focus image product
		4312MH0008000015036985K00	3698	target Cherry_Ridge - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3651-3658 - range map product
		4312MH0008000015036990K00	3699	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3639-3646 - best focus image product
		4312MH0008000015037005K00	3700	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3639-3646 - range map product
		4312MH0008000015037010K00	3701	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3629-3635 - best focus image product
		4312MH0008000015037025K00	3702	target Aeolian_Buttres - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3629-3635 - range map product
		4312MH0008000015037030K00	3703	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3617-3624 - best focus image product
		4312MH0008000015037045K00	3704	target Aeolian_Buttres - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4311 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3617-3624 - range map product
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4312MH00076900115037050I	3705	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4312MH00077000115037060I	3706	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4312MH00077100115037070I	3707	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	4312MH00077200115037080I	3708	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4312MH00076900115037090I	3709	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4312MH00077000115037100I	3710	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4312MH00077100115037110I	3711	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	4312MH00077200115037120I	3712	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4312MH00076900115037130I	3713	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4312MH00077000115037140I	3714	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4312MH00077100115037150I	3715	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	4312MH00077200115037160I	3716	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4312MH00076900115037170I	3717	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4312MH00077000115037180I	3718	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4312MH00077100115037190I	3719	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	4312MH00077200115037200I	3720	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 124 cm
mN00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4312MH00076900115037210I	3721	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mN00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4312MH00077000115037220I	3722	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 112 cm
mN00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4312MH00077100115037230I	3723	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mN00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	4312MH00077200115037240I	3724	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 4312 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 124 cm

updated: 09_October_2024

Sol 4314 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Sep-24
camera position	3
total parent images	35
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Burst_Rock and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN000359	Burst_Rock 25 cm standoff	4314MH0003900015037250D	3725	autofocus sub-frame for target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm
		4314MH0003900015037260D	3726	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm
		4314MH0003900015037270D	3727	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH0003900015037280D	3728	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH0003900015037290D	3729	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH0003900015037300D	3730	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH0003900015037310D	3731	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH0003900015037320D	3732	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH0003900015037330D	3733	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH0003900015037340D	3734	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000368	Burst_Rock stereo-1 5 cm standoff	4314MH00016800015037350D	3735	autofocus sub-frame for target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4314MH00016800015037360D	3736	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4314MH00016800015037370D	3737	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037380D	3738	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037390D	3739	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037400D	3740	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037410D	3741	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037420D	3742	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037430D	3743	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037440D	3744	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000368	Burst_Rock stereo-2 5 cm standoff	4314MH00016800015037450D	3745	autofocus sub-frame for target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4314MH00016800015037460D	3746	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4314MH00016800015037470D	3747	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037480D	3748	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037490D	3749	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037500D	3750	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037510D	3751	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037520D	3752	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037530D	3753	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4314MH00016800015037540D	3754	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN000393	Focus Merges	4314MH00019300015037550D	3755	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4314 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3747-3754 - best focus image product
		4314MH00019300015037560D	3756	target Burst_Rock - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4314 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3747-3754 - range map product
		4314MH00019300015037570D	3757	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4314 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3737-3744 - best focus image product
		4314MH00019300015037580D	3758	target Burst_Rock - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4314 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3737-3744 - range map product
		4314MH00019300015037590D	3759	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4314 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3727-3734 - best focus image product
		4314MH00019300015037600D	3760	target Burst_Rock - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4314 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3727-3734 - range map product

updated: 17_October_2024

Sol 4316 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Sep-24
camera position	6
total parent images	65
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	13
total parent images + focus merge products	74

MAHLI images of the targets Aster_Lake and Beryi_Lake. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00359	Aster_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4316MH00359001503761C00	3761	autofocus sub-frame for target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm		
		4316MH00359001503762C00	3762	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm		
		4316MH003590021503763C00	3763	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH003590021503764C00	3764	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH003590021503765C00	3765	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH003590021503766C00	3766	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH003590021503767C00	3767	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH003590021503768C00	3768	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH003590021503769C00	3769	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH003590021503770C00	3770	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00878	Aster_Lake stereo-1 ~9 cm standoff	4316MH00878001503771C00	3771	autofocus sub-frame for target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
				4316MH00878001503772C00	3772	target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
				4316MH008780021503773C00	3773	target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4316MH008780021503774C00	3774			target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008780021503775C00	3775			target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008780021503776C00	3776			target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008780021503777C00	3777			target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008780021503778C00	3778			target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008780021503779C00	3779			target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008780021503780C00	3780			target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00878	Aster_Lake stereo-2 ~9 cm standoff			4316MH00878001503781C00	3781	autofocus sub-frame for target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
				4316MH00878001503782C00	3782	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
				4316MH008780021503783C00	3783	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4316MH008780021503784C00	3784	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH008780021503785C00	3785	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH008780021503786C00	3786	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH008780021503787C00	3787	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH008780021503788C00	3788	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH008780021503789C00	3789	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH008780021503790C00	3790	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00865	Beryi_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4316MH00865001503791C00	3791	autofocus sub-frame for target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
				4316MH00865001503792C00	3792	target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
				4316MH008650021503793C00	3793	target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4316MH008650021503794C00	3794			target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008650021503795C00	3795			target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008650021503796C00	3796			target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008650021503797C00	3797			target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008650021503798C00	3798			target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008650021503799C00	3799			target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH008650021503800C00	3800			target Beryi_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00152	Beryi_Lake stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff			4316MH00152001503801C00	3801	autofocus sub-frame for target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4316MH00152001503802C00	3802	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
				4316MH001520021503803C00	3803	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4316MH001520021503804C00	3804	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH001520021503805C00	3805	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH001520021503806C00	3806	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH001520021503807C00	3807	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH001520021503808C00	3808	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH001520021503809C00	3809	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4316MH001520021503810C00	3810	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00152	Beryi_Lake stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4316MH00152001503811C00	3811	autofocus sub-frame for target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4316MH00152001503812C00	3812	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				4316MH001520021503813C00	3813	target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4316MH001520021503814C00	3814			target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH001520021503815C00	3815			target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH001520021503816C00	3816			target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH001520021503817C00	3817			target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH001520021503818C00	3818			target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH001520021503819C00	3819			target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4316MH001520021503820C00	3820			target Beryi_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

Continued on Next Page...

mnh00163	Focus Merge	4316MH001630001503821900	3821	target Bery_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3813-3820 - best focus image product
		4316MH001630001503822500	3822	target Bery_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3813-3820 - range map product
		4316MH001630001503823800	3823	target Bery_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3803-3810 - best focus image product
		4316MH001630001503824500	3824	target Bery_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3803-3810 - range map product
		4316MH001630001503825900	3825	target Bery_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3793-3800 - best focus image product
		4316MH001630001503826500	3826	target Bery_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3793-3800 - range map product
		4316MH001630001503827800	3827	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3783-3790 - best focus image product
		4316MH001630001503828500	3828	target Aster_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3783-3790 - range map product
		4316MH001630001503829800	3829	target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3773-3780 - best focus image product
		4316MH001630001503830500	3830	target Aster_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3773-3780 - range map product
		4316MH001630001503831800	3831	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3763-3770 - best focus image product
		4316MH001630001503832500	3832	target Aster_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4316 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3763-3770 - range map product

Sol 4318 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	04-Sep-2019(19)
camera position	11
total parent images	111
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	111

MAHLI imaged the targets Angora_Mountain, Moonlight_Lake and Cloud_Canyon. MAHLI also imaged the MAHLI and APXS calibration targets.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00876	Angora_Mountain ~23 cm standoff	4318MH008760011503833C00	3833	autofocus sub-frame for target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm		
		4318MH008760011503834C00	3834	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm		
		4318MH008760011503835C00	3835	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH008760011503836C00	3836	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH008760011503837C00	3837	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH008760011503838C00	3838	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH008760011503839C00	3839	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH008760011503840C00	3840	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH008760011503841C00	3841	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH008760011503842C00	3842	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503843C00	3843	autofocus sub-frame for target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm		
		4318MH0002400011503844C00	3844	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm		
		4318MH0002400011503845C00	3845	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503846C00	3846	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00224	Angora_Mountain stereo-1 ~3 cm standoff	4318MH0002400011503847C00	3847	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503848C00	3848	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503849C00	3849	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503850C00	3850	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503851C00	3851	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503852C00	3852	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503853C00	3853	autofocus sub-frame for target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm		
		4318MH0002400011503854C00	3854	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm		
		4318MH0002400011503855C00	3855	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503856C00	3856	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503857C00	3857	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503858C00	3858	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503859C00	3859	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503860C00	3860	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00224	Angora_Mountain stereo-2 ~3 cm standoff	4318MH0002400011503861C00	3861	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH0002400011503862C00	3862	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007060011503863C00	3863	autofocus sub-frame for target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 25 cm		
		4318MH007060011503864C00	3864	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 25 cm		
		4318MH007060011503865C00	3865	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		mNI00740	Moonlight_Lake stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4318MH007400011503866C00	3866	autofocus sub-frame for target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4318MH007400011503867C00	3867	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
				4318MH007400011503868C00	3868	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
				4318MH007400011503869C00	3869	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4318MH007400011503870C00	3870	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4318MH007400011503871C00	3871	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4318MH007400011503872C00	3872	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4318MH007400011503873C00	3873	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
				4318MH007400011503874C00	3874	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4318MH007400011503875C00	3875			target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4318MH007400011503876C00	3876			target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4318MH007400011503877C00	3877			autofocus sub-frame for target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
4318MH007400011503878C00	3878			target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
4318MH007400011503879C00	3879			target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00740	Moonlight_Lake stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4318MH007400011503880C00	3880	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007400011503881C00	3881	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007400011503882C00	3882	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007400011503883C00	3883	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007400011503884C00	3884	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007400011503885C00	3885	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007400011503886C00	3886	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007400011503887C00	3887	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007100011503888C00	3888	autofocus sub-frame for target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm		
		4318MH007100011503889C00	3889	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm		
		4318MH007100011503890C00	3890	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4318MH007100011503891C00	3891	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007100011503892C00	3892	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4318MH007100011503893C00	3893	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4318MH007100011503894C00	3894	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack				
4318MH007100011503895C00	3895	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack				
4318MH007100011503896C00	3896	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack				
4318MH007100011503897C00	3897	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack				
4318MH007100011503898C00	3898	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack				
mNI00706	Cloud_Canyon ~25 cm standoff	4318MH007060011503899C00	3899	autofocus sub-frame for target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm		
		4318MH007060011503900C00	3900	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm		
		4318MH007060011503901C00	3901	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		

mnh00699	Cloud_Canyon stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	431BMH00699001503902C00	3902	autofocus sub-frame for target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		431BMH00699001503903C00	3903	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		431BMH00699001503904C00	3904	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		431BMH00699001503905C00	3905	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00699001503906C00	3906	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00699001503907C00	3907	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00699001503908C00	3908	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00699001503909C00	3909	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00699001503910C00	3910	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00699001503911C00	3911	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00699001503912C00	3912	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mnh00699	Cloud_Canyon stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	431BMH00699001503913C00	3913	autofocus sub-frame for target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				431BMH00699001503914C00	3914	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				431BMH00699001503915C00	3915	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
431BMH00699001503916C00	3916			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
431BMH00699001503917C00	3917			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
431BMH00699001503918C00	3918			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
431BMH00699001503919C00	3919			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
431BMH00699001503920C00	3920			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
431BMH00699001503921C00	3921			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
431BMH00699001503922C00	3922			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
431BMH00699001503923C00	3923			target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mnh00794	Cloud_Canyon ~1 cm standoff			431BMH00794001503924C00	3924	autofocus sub-frame for target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm
				431BMH00794001503925C00	3925	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm
				431BMH00794001503926C00	3926	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		431BMH00794001503927C00	3927	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00794001503928C00	3928	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00794001503929C00	3929	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00794001503930C00	3930	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00794001503931C00	3931	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00794001503932C00	3932	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00794001503933C00	3933	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		431BMH00794001503934C00	3934	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mnh00371	MAHLI cal target - centered on bar target - 5 cm working distance	431BMH00371001503935C00	3935	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
				431BMH00371001503936C00	3936	MAHLI calibration target - bar target - near 5 cm working distance
		mnh00372	MAHLI cal target - centered on cent target - 5 cm working distance	431BMH00372001503937C00	3937	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance
431BMH00372001503938C00	3938			MAHLI calibration target - cent target - near 5 cm working distance		
mnh00374	MAHLI cal target + wheel + surface 30 cm working distance from target	431BMH00374001503939C00	3939	autofocus sub-frame for MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target		
		431BMH00374001503940C00	3940	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - focus on calibration target		
		431BMH00374001503941C00	3941	MAHLI calibration target and wheel and Mars surface - calibration target near 30 cm working distance - manual focus at infinity		
mnh00373	APXS cal target ~5 cm standoff	431BMH00373001503942C00	3942	autofocus sub-frame for APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm		
		431BMH00373001503943C00	3943	APXS calibration target - standoff near 5 cm		

updated: 30_September_2024

Sol 4319 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29-Sep-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0 <small>black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received</small>
focus merges performed	9
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	18
Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4318 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00536	Focus Merges	4319MH000536000102944800	3944	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3927-3934 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102945500	3945	target Cloud_Canyon - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3927-3934 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102946800	3946	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3916-3923 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102947500	3947	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3916-3923 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102948800	3948	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3905-3912 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102949500	3949	target Cloud_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3905-3912 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102950800	3950	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3891-3898 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102951500	3951	target Moonlight_Lake - standoff near 15 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3891-3898 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102952800	3952	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3880-3887 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102953500	3953	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3880-3887 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102954800	3954	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3869-3876 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102955500	3955	target Moonlight_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3869-3876 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102956800	3956	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3855-3862 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102957500	3957	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3855-3862 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102958800	3958	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3845-3852 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102959500	3959	target Angora_Mountain - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3845-3852 - range map product
		4319MH000536000102960800	3960	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3835-3842 - best focus image product
		4319MH000536000102961500	3961	target Angora_Mountain - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4318 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3835-3842 - range map product

updated: 21_October_2024

Sol 4321 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	1-20-24-04-24
camera position	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Flat_Note_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPVID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Flat_Note_Lake ~25 cm standoff	4321MH001900011503962C00	3962	autoFocus sub-frame for target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
		4321MH001900011503963C00	3963	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 25 cm
mN00196	Flat_Note_Lake stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4321MH003360021503964C00	3964	autoFocus sub-frame for target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4321MH003360021503965C00	3965	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4321MH003360021503966C00	3966	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503967C00	3967	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503968C00	3968	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503969C00	3969	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503970C00	3970	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503971C00	3971	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503972C00	3972	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503973C00	3973	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00196	Flat_Note_Lake stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4321MH003360021503974C00	3974	autoFocus sub-frame for target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4321MH003360021503975C00	3975	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4321MH003360021503976C00	3976	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503977C00	3977	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503978C00	3978	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503979C00	3979	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503980C00	3980	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503981C00	3981	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503982C00	3982	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH003360021503983C00	3983	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Flat_Note_Lake ~1 cm standoff	4321MH008480011503984C00	3984	autoFocus sub-frame for target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm
		4321MH008480011503985C00	3985	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm
		4321MH008480011503986C00	3986	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH008480011503987C00	3987	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH008480011503988C00	3988	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH008480011503989C00	3989	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH008480011503990C00	3990	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH008480011503991C00	3991	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH008480011503992C00	3992	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4321MH008480011503993C00	3993	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	4321MH001930011503994N00	3994	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4321 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3986-3993 - best focus image product
		4321MH001930011503995N00	3995	target Flat_Note_Lake - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4321 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3986-3993 - range map product
		4321MH001930011503996N00	3996	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4321 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3976-3983 - best focus image product
		4321MH001930011503997N00	3997	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4321 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3976-3983 - range map product
		4321MH001930011503998N00	3998	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4321 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3966-3973 - best focus image product
		4321MH001930011503999N00	3999	target Flat_Note_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4321 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3966-3973 - range map product

updated: 21_October_2024

Sol 4323 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	3-Oct-24
camera position:	8
total parent images:	25
focus merges performed:	2
total focus merge products:	4
total parent images + focus merge products:	29

MAHLI imaged the target Sub_Dome and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CCPFD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Sub_Dome ~25 cm standoff	4323MH00190001150400C00	4000	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sub_Dome - standoff near 25 cm
		4323MH00190001150400I00	4001	target Sub_Dome - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Sub_Dome stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4323MH001680021150400C00	4002	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4323MH001680021150400I00	4003	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4323MH001680021150400K00	4004	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150400L00	4005	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150400M00	4006	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150400N00	4007	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150400O00	4008	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150400P00	4009	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150400Q00	4010	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150400R00	4011	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Sub_Dome stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4323MH001680021150401C00	4012	autoFocus sub-frame for target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4323MH001680021150401I00	4013	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4323MH001680021150401K00	4014	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150401L00	4015	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150401M00	4016	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150401N00	4017	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150401O00	4018	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150401P00	4019	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150401Q00	4020	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4323MH001680021150401R00	4021	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	4323MH0002650001150402N00	4022	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4323 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4014-4021 - best focus image product
		4323MH0002650001150402S00	4023	target Sub_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4323 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4014-4021 - range map product
		4323MH0002650001150402U00	4024	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4323 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4004-4011 - best focus image product
		4323MH0002650001150402V00	4025	target Sub_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4323 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4004-4011 - range map product

updated: 22_October_2024

Sol 4325 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	6-Oct-24
camera position	6
total parent images	95
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	95

MAHLI imaged the target Kidney_Lake, the target Pumice_Flat and the DRT in POS archive products. **Image ID:** black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in POS archive product labels

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00705	Kidney_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4325MH00070600011504026C00	4026	autofocus sub-frame for target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 24 cm		
		4325MH0007060011504027C00	4027	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 24 cm		
		4325MH00070600211504028C00	4028	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00699	Kidney_Lake ~4 cm standoff	4325MH00069900011504029C00	4029	autofocus sub-frame for target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm		
		4325MH00069900111504030C00	4030	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm		
		4325MH00069900211504031C00	4031	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4325MH00069900311504032C00	4032	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00069900411504033C00	4033	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00069900511504034C00	4034	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00069900611504035C00	4035	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00069900711504036C00	4036	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00069900811504037C00	4037	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00069900911504038C00	4038	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00069901011504039C00	4039	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00706	Pumice_Flat ~23 cm standoff	4325MH00070600011504040C00	4040	autofocus sub-frame for target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 23 cm
				4325MH00070600111504041C00	4041	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 23 cm
4325MH00070600211504042C00	4042			target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00834	Pumice_Flat ~35 mm standoff	4325MH00083400011504043C00	4043	autofocus sub-frame for target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm		
		4325MH00083400111504044C00	4044	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm		
		4325MH00083400211504045C00	4045	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		4325MH00083400311504046C00	4046	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00083400411504047C00	4047	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00083400511504048C00	4048	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00083400611504049C00	4049	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00083400711504050C00	4050	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00083400811504051C00	4051	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00083400911504052C00	4052	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00083401011504053C00	4053	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00190	Ribbon_Fall after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4325MH00019000011504054C00	4054	autofocus sub-frame for target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
				4325MH00019000111504055C00	4055	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Ribbon_Fall after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4325MH00033600011504056C00	4056	autofocus sub-frame for target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4325MH00033600111504057C00	4057	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		4325MH00033600211504058C00	4058	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00033600311504059C00	4059	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00033600411504060C00	4060	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00033600511504061C00	4061	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00033600611504062C00	4062	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00033600711504063C00	4063	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00033600811504064C00	4064	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00033600911504065C00	4065	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00336	Ribbon_Fall after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4325MH00033600011504066C00	4066	autofocus sub-frame for target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4325MH00033600111504067C00	4067	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				4325MH00033600211504068C00	4068	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4325MH00033600311504069C00	4069			target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4325MH00033600411504070C00	4070			target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4325MH00033600511504071C00	4071			target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4325MH00033600611504072C00	4072			target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4325MH00033600711504073C00	4073			target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4325MH00033600811504074C00	4074			target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4325MH00033600911504075C00	4075			target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00848	Ribbon_Fall after DRT ~1 cm standoff			4325MH00084800011504076C00	4076	autofocus sub-frame for target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
				4325MH00084800111504077C00	4077	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
				4325MH00084800211504078C00	4078	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4325MH00084800311504079C00	4079	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00084800411504080C00	4080	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00084800511504081C00	4081	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00084800611504082C00	4082	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00084800711504083C00	4083	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00084800811504084C00	4084	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		4325MH00084800911504085C00	4085	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 08_October_2024

Sol 4326 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	7-Oct-24	Image ID:	
camera position:	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	0	CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	5	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	10		
total parent images + focus merge products:	10		

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4325 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00891	Focus Merges	4326MH000891000109408600	4086	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4078-4085 - best focus image product
		4326MH000891000109408750	4087	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4078-4085 - range map product
		4326MH000891000109408800	4088	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4068-4075 - best focus image product
		4326MH000891000109408950	4089	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4068-4075 - range map product
		4326MH000891000109409000	4090	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4058-4065 - best focus image product
		4326MH000891000109409150	4091	target Ribbon_Fall - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4058-4065 - range map product
		4326MH000891000109409200	4092	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4046-4053 - best focus image product
		4326MH000891000109409350	4093	target Pumice_Flat - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4046-4053 - range map product
		4326MH000891000109409400	4094	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4032-4039 - best focus image product
		4326MH000891000109409550	4095	target Kidney_Lake - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4325 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4032-4039 - range map product

updated: 09_October_2024

Sol 4328 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0-04-24
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4327 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00133	Focus Merges	4328MH001530001504144800	4144	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4136-4143 - best focus image product
		4328MH001530001504145500	4145	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4136-4143 - range map product
		4328MH001530001504146800	4146	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4126-4133 - best focus image product
		4328MH001530001504147500	4147	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4126-4133 - range map product
		4328MH001530001504148800	4148	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4110-4117 - best focus image product
		4328MH001530001504149500	4149	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4110-4117 - range map product
		4328MH001530001504150800	4150	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4100-4107 - best focus image product
		4328MH001530001504151500	4151	target Pincushion_Peak - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX8 spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4327 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4100-4107 - range map product

updated: 14_October_2024

Sol 4332 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19_Oct_24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4331 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N0013	Focus Merges	4332MH00153000109420R00	4300	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4192-4199 - best focus image product
		4332MH00153000109420I500	4201	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4192-4199 - range map product
		4332MH00153000109420R00	4202	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4182-4189 - best focus image product
		4332MH00153000109420S500	4203	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4182-4189 - range map product
		4332MH00153000109420R00	4204	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4166-4173 - best focus image product
		4332MH00153000109420S500	4205	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4166-4173 - range map product
		4332MH00153000109420R00	4206	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4156-4163 - best focus image product
		4332MH00153000109420S500	4207	target Midnight_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4331 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4156-4163 - range map product

updated: 21_October_2024

Sol 4334 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15-Oct-24
camera position	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Dollar_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Dollar_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4334MH0001900001504208CD	4208	autoFocus sub-frame for target Dollar_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4334MH0001900001504209CD	4209	target Dollar_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4334MH0003360001504210CD	4210	autoFocus sub-frame for target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
mN00336	Dollar_Lake stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4334MH0003360001504211CD	4211	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4334MH0003360001504212CD	4212	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4334MH0003360001504213CD	4213	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4334MH0003360001504214CD	4214	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4334MH0003360001504215CD	4215	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4334MH0003360001504216CD	4216	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4334MH0003360001504217CD	4217	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4334MH0003360001504218CD	4218	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4334MH0003360001504219CD	4219	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00336	Dollar_Lake stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4334MH0003360001504220CD
4334MH0003360001504221CD	4221			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
4334MH0003360001504222CD	4222			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4334MH0003360001504223CD	4223			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4334MH0003360001504224CD	4224			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4334MH0003360001504225CD	4225			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4334MH0003360001504226CD	4226			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4334MH0003360001504227CD	4227			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4334MH0003360001504228CD	4228			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4334MH0003360001504229CD	4229			target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	4334MH0002650001504230ND	4230	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4334 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4222-4229 - best focus image product
		4334MH0002650001504231SD	4231	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4334 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4222-4229 - range map product
		4334MH0002650001504232ND	4232	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4334 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4212-4219 - best focus image product
		4334MH0002650001504233SD	4233	target Dollar_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4334 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4212-4219 - range map product

updated: 22_October_2024

Sol 4336 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-Oct-24
camera position	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Jumble_Lake and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Jumble_Lake *23 cm standoff	4336MH001900011504234C0D	4234	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jumble_Lake - standoff near 23 cm
		4336MH001900011504235C0D	4235	target Jumble_Lake - standoff near 23 cm
		4336MH001900011504236C0D	4236	autoFocus sub-frame for target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
mN00182	Jumble_Lake stereo-1 *35 mm standoff	4336MH001820011504237C0D	4237	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		4336MH001820011504238C0D	4238	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4336MH001820011504239C0D	4239	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4336MH001820011504240C0D	4240	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4336MH001820011504241C0D	4241	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4336MH001820011504242C0D	4242	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4336MH001820011504243C0D	4243	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4336MH001820011504244C0D	4244	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4336MH001820011504245C0D	4245	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00182	Jumble_Lake stereo-2 *4 cm standoff	4336MH001820011504246C0D
4336MH001820011504247C0D	4247			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
4336MH001820011504248C0D	4248			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
4336MH001820011504249C0D	4249			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
4336MH001820011504250C0D	4250			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
4336MH001820011504251C0D	4251			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
4336MH001820011504252C0D	4252			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
4336MH001820011504253C0D	4253			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4336MH001820011504254C0D	4254			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
4336MH001820011504255C0D	4255			target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	4336MH002050001504256R0D	4256	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4336 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4248-4255 - best focus image product
		4336MH002050001504257S0D	4257	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4336 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4248-4255 - range map product
		4336MH002050001504258R0D	4258	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4336 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4238-4245 - best focus image product
		4336MH002050001504259S0D	4259	target Jumble_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4336 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4238-4245 - range map product

Sol 4338 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	18-Oct-24	
		camera position	85	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	84	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Polly_Dome, the target Noble_Canyon, and the DRT-brushed target Chapel_Lake.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Polly_Dome ~24 cm standoff	4338MH001900011504260C00	4300	autofocus sub-frame for target Polly_Dome - standoff near 24 cm
		4338MH001900011504261C00	4261	target Polly_Dome - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Polly_Dome stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4338MH001680011504262C00	4262	autofocus sub-frame for target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4338MH001680011504263C00	4263	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4338MH001680011504264C00	4264	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504265C00	4265	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504266C00	4266	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504267C00	4267	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504268C00	4268	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504269C00	4269	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504270C00	4270	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504271C00	4271	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Polly_Dome stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4338MH001680011504272C00	4272	autofocus sub-frame for target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4338MH001680011504273C00	4273	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4338MH001680011504274C00	4274	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504275C00	4275	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504276C00	4276	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504277C00	4277	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504278C00	4278	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504279C00	4279	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504280C00	4280	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH001680011504281C00	4281	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00359	Noble_Canyon ~24 cm standoff	4338MH003590011504282C00	4282	autofocus sub-frame for target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4338MH003590011504283C00	4283	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm
		4338MH003590011504284C00	4284	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003590011504285C00	4285	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003590011504286C00	4286	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003590011504287C00	4287	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003590011504288C00	4288	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003590011504289C00	4289	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003590011504290C00	4290	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003590011504291C00	4291	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00673	Noble_Canyon stereo-1 ~45 cm standoff	4338MH006730011504292C00	4292	autofocus sub-frame for target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm
		4338MH006730011504293C00	4293	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm
		4338MH006730011504294C00	4294	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504295C00	4295	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504296C00	4296	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504297C00	4297	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504298C00	4298	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504299C00	4299	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504300C00	4300	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504301C00	4301	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00673	Noble_Canyon stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4338MH006730011504302C00	4302	autofocus sub-frame for target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4338MH006730011504303C00	4303	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4338MH006730011504304C00	4304	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504305C00	4305	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504306C00	4306	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504307C00	4307	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504308C00	4308	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504309C00	4309	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504310C00	4310	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH006730011504311C00	4311	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Chapel_Lake after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4338MH001900011504312C00	4312	autofocus sub-frame for target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
		4338MH001900011504313C00	4313	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
mN00336	Chapel_Lake after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4338MH003360011504314C00	4314	autofocus sub-frame for target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4338MH003360011504315C00	4315	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4338MH003360011504316C00	4316	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003360011504317C00	4317	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003360011504318C00	4318	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003360011504319C00	4319	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003360011504320C00	4320	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003360011504321C00	4321	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003360011504322C00	4322	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH003360011504323C00	4323	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00336	Chapel Lake after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4338MH00336001504324C00	4334	autofocus sub-frame for target Chapel Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4338MH00336001504325C00	4335	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4338MH00336001504326C00	4336	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00336001504327C00	4337	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00336001504328C00	4338	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00336001504329C00	4339	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00336001504330C00	4330	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00336001504331C00	4331	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00336001504332C00	4332	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00336001504333C00	4333	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00848	Chapel Lake after DRT ~1 cm standoff	4338MH00848001504334C00	4334	autofocus sub-frame for target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4338MH00848001504335C00	4335	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4338MH00848001504336C00	4336	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00848001504337C00	4337	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00848001504338C00	4338	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00848001504339C00	4339	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00848001504340C00	4340	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00848001504341C00	4341	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00848001504342C00	4342	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4338MH00848001504343C00	4343	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 21_October_2024

Sol 4339 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	20-04-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	16

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4338 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1000170	Focus Merges	4339MH0017000150434400	4344	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4336-4343 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150434500	4345	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4336-4343 - range map product
		4339MH0017000150434600	4346	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4326-4333 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150434700	4347	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4326-4333 - range map product
		4339MH0017000150434800	4348	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4316-4323 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150434900	4349	target Chapel_Lake - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4316-4323 - range map product
		4339MH0017000150435000	4350	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4304-4311 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150435100	4351	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4304-4311 - range map product
		4339MH0017000150435200	4352	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4294-4301 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150435300	4353	target Noble_Canyon - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4294-4301 - range map product
		4339MH0017000150435400	4354	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4284-4291 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150435500	4355	target Noble_Canyon - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4284-4291 - range map product
		4339MH0017000150435600	4356	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4274-4281 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150435700	4357	target Polly_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4274-4281 - range map product
		4339MH0017000150435800	4358	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4264-4271 - best focus image product
		4339MH0017000150435900	4359	target Polly_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4338 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4264-4271 - range map product

updated: 24_April_2025

Sol 4341 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Oct-24
camera position	0
total parent images	43
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	43

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Chuck_Pass.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Chuck_Pass after DRT ~24 cm standoff	4341MH0019000011504360C00	4360	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
		4341MH001900011504361C00	4361	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00336	Chuck_Pass after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4341MH0033600011504362C00	4362	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4341MH003360011504363C00	4363	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4341MH0033600211504364C00	4364	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600311504365C00	4365	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600411504366C00	4366	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600511504367C00	4367	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600611504368C00	4368	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600711504369C00	4369	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600811504370C00	4370	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600911504371C00	4371	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Chuck_Pass after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4341MH003360011504372C00	4372	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4341MH0033600211504373C00	4373	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4341MH0033600311504374C00	4374	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600411504375C00	4375	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600511504376C00	4376	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600611504377C00	4377	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600711504378C00	4378	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600811504379C00	4379	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600911504380C00	4380	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033601011504381C00	4381	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00848	Chuck_Pass after DRT APXS spot 2 ~15 mm standoff	4341MH0084800011504382C00	4382	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm
		4341MH008480011504383C00	4383	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm
		4341MH0084800211504384C00	4384	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0084800311504385C00	4385	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0084800411504386C00	4386	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0084800511504387C00	4387	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0084800611504388C00	4388	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0084800711504389C00	4389	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0084800811504390C00	4390	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0084800911504391C00	4391	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Chuck_Pass after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	4341MH0033600011504392C00	4392	autofocus sub-frame for target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4341MH003360011504393C00	4393	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4341MH0033600211504394C00	4394	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600311504395C00	4395	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600411504396C00	4396	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600511504397C00	4397	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600611504398C00	4398	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600711504399C00	4399	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600811504400C00	4400	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4341MH0033600911504401C00	4401	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 25_October_2024

Sol 4342 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Oct-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4341 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100013	Focus Merges	4342MH0015300010440200	4402	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4394-4401 - best focus image product
		4342MH0015300010440350	4403	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4394-4401 - range map product
		4342MH0015300010440400	4404	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4384-4391 - best focus image product
		4342MH0015300010440550	4405	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4384-4391 - range map product
		4342MH0015300010440600	4406	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4374-4381 - best focus image product
		4342MH0015300010440750	4407	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4374-4381 - range map product
		4342MH0015300010440800	4408	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4364-4371 - best focus image product
		4342MH0015300010440950	4409	target Chuck_Pass - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4341 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4364-4371 - range map product

Sol 4345 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	26-Oct-24	
		camera position	72	Image ID:
		total parent images	0	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	0	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	72	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI acquired a 3x1 mosaic on Reef_Lake and MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Mount_Brewer.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALISE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN0855	Reef_Lake mosaic position 1 of 3 ~24 cm standoff	4345MH00855001150410200	4410	autofocus sub-frame for target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4345MH00855001150441100	4411	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4345MH00855001150412100	4412	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150441300	4413	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150414200	4414	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150441500	4415	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150416200	4416	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150441700	4417	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150418200	4418	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150441900	4419	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN0855	Reef_Lake mosaic position 2 of 3 ~24 cm standoff	4345MH00855001150420200	4420	autofocus sub-frame for target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4345MH00855001150442100	4421	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm
		4345MH00855001150422200	4422	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150442300	4423	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150424200	4424	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150424500	4425	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150426200	4426	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150427000	4427	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150428200	4428	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150429200	4429	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN0855	Reef_Lake mosaic position 3 of 3 ~23 cm standoff	4345MH00855001150430200	4430	autofocus sub-frame for target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm
		4345MH00855001150443100	4431	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm
		4345MH00855001150432200	4432	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150443300	4433	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150434200	4434	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150435200	4435	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150436200	4436	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150437000	4437	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150438200	4438	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00855001150439200	4439	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN0090	Mount_Brewer after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4345MH00190001150440200	4440	autofocus sub-frame for target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		4345MH00190001150441100	4441	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN0068	Mount_Brewer after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	4345MH00168001150442200	4442	autofocus sub-frame for target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4345MH00168001150443100	4443	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4345MH00168001150444200	4444	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150445200	4445	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150446200	4446	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150447200	4447	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150448200	4448	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150449200	4449	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150450200	4450	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150451100	4451	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN0068	Mount_Brewer after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	4345MH00168001150452200	4452	autofocus sub-frame for target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4345MH00168001150453100	4453	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4345MH00168001150454200	4454	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150455200	4455	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150456200	4456	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150457200	4457	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150458200	4458	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150459200	4459	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150460200	4460	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150461100	4461	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN0074	Mount_Brewer after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	4345MH00743001150462200	4462	autofocus sub-frame for target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4345MH00743001150463100	4463	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		4345MH00743001150464200	4464	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00743001150465200	4465	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00743001150466200	4466	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00743001150467200	4467	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00743001150468200	4468	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00743001150469200	4469	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00743001150470200	4470	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00743001150471100	4471	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mNH00168	Mount_Brewer after DRF APX3 spot 1 ~5cm standoff	4345MH0016800150447200	4472	autofocus sub-frame for target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4345MH00168001150447300	4473	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4345MH00168001150447400	4474	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150447500	4475	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150447600	4476	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150447700	4477	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150447800	4478	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150447900	4479	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150448000	4480	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4345MH00168001150448100	4481	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 28_October_2024

Sol 4346 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27-Oct-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4345 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN002171	Focus Merges	4346MH00017J0001S04482N00	4482	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4474-4481 - best focus image product
		4346MH00017J0001S04483S00	4483	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4474-4481 - range map product
		4346MH00017J0001S04484R00	4484	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4464-4471 - best focus image product
		4346MH00017J0001S04485S00	4485	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4464-4471 - range map product
		4346MH00017J0001S04486R00	4486	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4454-4461 - best focus image product
		4346MH00017J0001S04487S00	4487	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4454-4461 - range map product
		4346MH00017J0001S04488R00	4488	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4444-4451 - best focus image product
		4346MH00017J0001S04489S00	4489	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4444-4451 - range map product
		4346MH00017J0001S04490R00	4490	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4432-4439 - best focus image product
		4346MH00017J0001S04491S00	4491	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4432-4439 - range map product
		4346MH00017J0001S04492R00	4492	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4422-4429 - best focus image product
		4346MH00017J0001S04493S00	4493	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4422-4429 - range map product
		4346MH00017J0001S04494R00	4494	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4412-4419 - best focus image product
		4346MH00017J0001S04495S00	4495	target Reef_Lake - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4412-4419 - range map product

updated: 30_October_2024

Sol 4348 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29-Oct-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	6

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 4345 were merged again; this happened because a fault occurred onboard the rover that prevented acquisition and merge of new MAHLI data planned for the DRT-brushed target Red_Meadow.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00289	Focus Merges	4348MH00193000104496R00	4496	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4474-4481 - best focus image product
		4348MH00193000104497S00	4497	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4474-4481 - range map product
		4348MH00193000104498R00	4498	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4464-4471 - best focus image product
		4348MH00193000104499S00	4499	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4464-4471 - range map product
		4348MH00193000104500R00	4500	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4454-4461 - best focus image product
		4348MH00193000104501S00	4501	target Mount_Brewer - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APX3 spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 3 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4345 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4454-4461 - range map product

updated: 19_November_2024

Sol 4350 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	21-Oct-24	
		camera positions	6	Image ID:
		total parent images	64	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	6	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	12	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	70	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Ladder_Lake and the CRT brushed target Red_Meadow (brushed on Sol 4348). The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Ladder_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4350MH0019000110495020C0	4502	autofocus sub-frame for target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4350MH0019000110495030C0	4503	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
mN00168	Ladder_Lake Stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	4350MH0016800110495040C0	4504	autofocus sub-frame for target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4350MH0016800110495050C0	4505	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		4350MH0016800110495060C0	4506	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495070C0	4507	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495080C0	4508	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495090C0	4509	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495100C0	4510	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495110C0	4511	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495120C0	4512	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495130C0	4513	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Ladder_Lake Stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	4350MH0016800110495140C0	4514	autofocus sub-frame for target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4350MH0016800110495150C0	4515	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		4350MH0016800110495160C0	4516	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495170C0	4517	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495180C0	4518	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495190C0	4519	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495200C0	4520	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495210C0	4521	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495220C0	4522	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0016800110495230C0	4523	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Ladder_Lake ~5 mm standoff	4350MH0074300110495240C0	4524	autofocus sub-frame for target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm
		4350MH0074300110495250C0	4525	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm
		4350MH0074300110495260C0	4526	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0074300110495270C0	4527	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0074300110495280C0	4528	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0074300110495290C0	4529	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0074300110495300C0	4530	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0074300110495310C0	4531	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0074300110495320C0	4532	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0074300110495330C0	4533	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Reds_Meadow after Sol 4348 DRT ~25 cm standoff	4350MH0019000110495340C0	4534	autofocus sub-frame for target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4350MH0019000110495350C0	4535	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Reds_Meadow after Sol 4348 DRT Stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4350MH0033600110495360C0	4536	autofocus sub-frame for target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4350MH0033600110495370C0	4537	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4350MH0033600110495380C0	4538	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495390C0	4539	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495400C0	4540	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495410C0	4541	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495420C0	4542	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495430C0	4543	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495440C0	4544	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495450C0	4545	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Reds_Meadow after Sol 4348 DRT Stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4350MH0033600110495460C0	4546	autofocus sub-frame for target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4350MH0033600110495470C0	4547	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4350MH0033600110495480C0	4548	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495490C0	4549	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495500C0	4550	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495510C0	4551	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495520C0	4552	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495530C0	4553	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495540C0	4554	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0033600110495550C0	4555	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00864	Reds_Meadow after Sol 4348 DRT ~15 mm standoff	4350MH0086400110495560C0	4556	autofocus sub-frame for target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4350MH0086400110495570C0	4557	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm
		4350MH0086400110495580C0	4558	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0086400110495590C0	4559	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0086400110495600C0	4560	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0086400110495610C0	4561	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0086400110495620C0	4562	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0086400110495630C0	4563	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0086400110495640C0	4564	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4350MH0086400110495650C0	4565	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mnh00163	Focus Merge	4350MH001630001504566900	4566	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4558-4565 - best focus image product
		4350MH001630001504567500	4567	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 15 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4558-4565 - range map product
		4350MH001630001504568900	4568	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4548-4555 - best focus image product
		4350MH001630001504569500	4569	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4548-4555 - range map product
		4350MH001630001504570900	4570	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4538-4545 - best focus image product
		4350MH001630001504571500	4571	target Reds_Meadow - after sol 4348 dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4538-4545 - range map product
		4350MH001630001504572900	4572	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4526-4533 - best focus image product
		4350MH001630001504573500	4573	target Ladder_Lake - standoff near 5 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4526-4533 - range map product
		4350MH001630001504574900	4574	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4516-4523 - best focus image product
		4350MH001630001504575500	4575	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4516-4523 - range map product
		4350MH001630001504576900	4576	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4506-4513 - best focus image product
		4350MH001630001504577500	4577	target Ladder_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 4350 with MEL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4506-4513 - range map product

Sol 4352 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	2-Nov-24
camera position	32
total parent images	93
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	93

MAHLI image of the target Stag_Dome, the DRT-brushed target Eureka_Valley and the target Black_Bear_Lake.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00876	Stag_Dome ~24 cm standoff	4352MH0008760021504578000	4578	autofocus sub-frame for target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm
		4352MH0008760021504579000	4579	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm
		4352MH0008760021504580000	4580	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008760021504581000	4581	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008760021504582000	4582	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008760021504583000	4583	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008760021504584000	4584	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008760021504585000	4585	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008760021504586000	4586	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008760021504587000	4587	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504588000	4588	autofocus sub-frame for target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH000240021504589000	4589	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH000240021504590000	4590	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504591000	4591	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Stag_Dome stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4352MH000240021504592000	4592	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504593000	4593	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504594000	4594	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504595000	4595	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504596000	4596	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504597000	4597	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504598000	4598	autofocus sub-frame for target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH000240021504599000	4599	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH000240021504600000	4600	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504601000	4601	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504602000	4602	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504603000	4603	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504604000	4604	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH000240021504605000	4605	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4352MH000240021504606000	4606	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4352MH000240021504607000	4607	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00190	Eureka_Valley after DRT ~25 cm standoff	4352MH0001900021504608000	4608	autofocus sub-frame for target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		4352MH0001900021504609000	4609	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00336	Eureka_Valley after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	4352MH0003360021504610000	4610	autofocus sub-frame for target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4352MH0003360021504611000	4611	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		4352MH0003360021504612000	4612	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504613000	4613	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504614000	4614	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504615000	4615	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504616000	4616	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504617000	4617	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504618000	4618	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504619000	4619	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504620000	4620	autofocus sub-frame for target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4352MH0003360021504621000	4621	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		4352MH0003360021504622000	4622	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504623000	4623	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00336	Eureka_Valley after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	4352MH0003360021504624000	4624	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504625000	4625	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504626000	4626	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504627000	4627	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504628000	4628	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0003360021504629000	4629	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008480021504630000	4630	autofocus sub-frame for target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4352MH0008480021504631000	4631	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		4352MH0008480021504632000	4632	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008480021504633000	4633	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008480021504634000	4634	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008480021504635000	4635	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008480021504636000	4636	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		4352MH0008480021504637000	4637	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
4352MH0008480021504638000	4638	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
4352MH0008480021504639000	4639	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

Continued on Next Page...

mH00359	Black_Bear_Lake ~24 cm standoff	4352MH00359001504640C0	4640	autofocus sub-frame for target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4352MH00359001504641C0	4641	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm
		4352MH00359001504642C0	4642	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00359001504643C0	4643	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00359001504644C0	4644	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00359001504645C0	4645	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00359001504646C0	4646	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00359001504647C0	4647	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00359001504648C0	4648	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00359001504649C0	4649	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in B-image relative focus stack
mH00152	Black_Bear_Lake stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	4352MH00152001504650C0	4650	autofocus sub-frame for target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH00152001504651C0	4651	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH00152001504652C0	4652	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504653C0	4653	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504654C0	4654	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504655C0	4655	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504656C0	4656	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504657C0	4657	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504658C0	4658	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504659C0	4659	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in B-image relative focus stack
mH00152	Black_Bear_Lake stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	4352MH00152001504660C0	4660	autofocus sub-frame for target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH00152001504661C0	4661	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		4352MH00152001504662C0	4662	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504663C0	4663	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504664C0	4664	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504665C0	4665	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504666C0	4666	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504667C0	4667	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504668C0	4668	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in B-image relative focus stack
		4352MH00152001504669C0	4669	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in B-image relative focus stack

updated: 04_November_2024

Sol 4353 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	3-Nov-24
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	9
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	18

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 4352 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00536	Focus Merges	4353MH0005360001404670R00	4670	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4662-4669 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404671S00	4671	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4662-4669 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404672R00	4672	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4652-4659 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404673S00	4673	target Black_Bear_Lake - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4652-4659 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404674R00	4674	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4642-4649 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404675S00	4675	target Black_Bear_Lake - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4642-4649 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404676R00	4676	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4632-4639 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404677S00	4677	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4632-4639 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404678R00	4678	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4622-4629 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404679S00	4679	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4622-4629 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404680R00	4680	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4612-4619 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404681S00	4681	target Eureka_Valley - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4612-4619 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404682R00	4682	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4602-4607 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404683S00	4683	target Stag_Dome - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4602-4607 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404684R00	4684	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4592-4597 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404685S00	4685	target Stag_Dome - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4592-4597 - range map product
		4353MH0005360001404686R00	4686	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4582-4587 - best focus image product
		4353MH0005360001404687S00	4687	target Stag_Dome - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 4352 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4582-4587 - range map product

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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